

**PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF SOLAR-
ASSISTED COMBINED CYCLE POWER PLANTS
IN IRAQ**

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Ali Isam Yahya AL FARIS

ABSTRACT

Ph.D. Thesis

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**Karabuk University
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Department of Mechanical Engineering**

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This study investigates the performance optimization of solar-assisted combined cycle power plants, with a case study focused on the Kirkuk Gas Power Plant in Iraq. The study addresses critical challenges such as the inefficiencies of conventional gas turbine systems, increasing energy demands, and the pressing need for sustainable solutions to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. Leveraging the unique geographical advantage of Iraq's high solar irradiation, this research proposes three advanced configurations for the power plant: (1) a baseline combined cycle (Model 1), (2) an integrated system with a parabolic trough collector (Model 2), and (3) a hybrid system combining a parabolic trough collector with an absorption refrigeration system (Model 3).

Model 1 represents the traditional configuration, achieving a peak thermal efficiency of 51.26% and an exergy efficiency of 49.49%, constrained by limited waste heat

recovery capabilities. In contrast, Model 2 integrates solar energy through a parabolic trough collector (PTC), significantly enhancing system performance. This configuration improves thermal and exergy efficiencies to 59.97% and 57.91%, respectively, while increasing the net power output from 211.7 MW to 232.4 MW. However, the economic analysis of Model 2 reveals higher operational costs due to the solar integration, highlighting the need for further cost optimization.

Model 3, the most advanced configuration, combines the PTC with an absorption refrigeration system (ARS) to recover low-grade waste heat effectively. This innovative design achieves maximum thermal and exergy efficiencies of 61.19% and 59.08%, respectively, with a net power output of 240.2 MW. The ARS contributes to enhanced thermodynamic performance by reducing irreversibilities and cooling demands, particularly under high-pressure ratio (PR) and gas turbine inlet temperature (GTIT) conditions. This configuration demonstrates superior economic feasibility, with stabilized operational costs and significantly reduced greenhouse gas emissions compared to the baseline.

The research also emphasizes the role of critical parameters such as PR, GTIT, and high-pressure steam turbine inlet temperature in optimizing system performance. The thermoeconomic analysis underscores the cost-effectiveness of Model 3, which achieves the lowest electricity costs across varying operational conditions, ranging from 71 \$/MWh to 74.7 \$/MWh, depending on the PR. The environmental analysis reveals substantial reductions in carbon dioxide emissions, solidifying Model 3 as the most sustainable configuration.

This work highlights the strategic importance of integrating solar energy and advanced waste heat recovery technologies in regions with high solar potential. It provides a robust framework for designing and optimizing hybrid power generation systems that align with global energy sustainability goals. The findings demonstrate that adopting Model 3 at the Kirkuk Gas Power Plant can significantly enhance energy efficiency, reduce environmental impact, and support Iraq's transition toward cleaner energy production. This research offers valuable insights for policymakers,

energy planners, and industry leaders aiming to implement similar solutions in comparable high-irradiation regions.

Key Words : Environmental analysis, Absorption refrigeration system (ARS), Waste heat recovery, Sustainable energy systems, Kirkuk gas power plant, (ISCC), Exergoeconomic analysis.

Science Code : 91408

ÖZET

Doktora Tezi

GÜNEŞ ENERJİSİYLE ÇALIŞAN KOMBİNE ÇEVİRİM SANTRALLERİNİN PERFORMANS DEĞERLENDİRMESİ. IRAK'TA VAKA ÇALIŞMASI

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Bu çalışmada, Irak'taki Kerkük Gaz Santrali'ni odak alan bir vaka çalışması ile güneş enerjisi destekli kombine çevrim enerji santrallerinin performans optimizasyonu incelenmektedir. Çalışma, geleneksel gaz türbini sistemlerinin verimsizlikleri, artan enerji talepleri ve sera gazı emisyonlarını azaltmak için sürdürülebilir çözümlere duyulan acil ihtiyaç gibi kritik sorunları ele almaktadır. Irak'ın yüksek güneş ışınım şiddeti potansiyelinin sunduğu benzersiz coğrafi avantajdan faydalanan bu araştırma, enerji santrali için üç gelişmiş yapılandırma önermektedir: (1) temel bir kombine çevrim (Model 1), (2) parabolik oluk kollektörü (PTC) içeren entegre bir sistem (Model 2) ve (3) parabolik oluk kollektörü ile absorpsiyonlu soğutma sistemi (ARS) kombinasyonunu içeren hibrit bir sistem (Model 3).

Model 1, sınırlı atık ısı geri kazanım kabiliyetleri ile sınırlandırılmış, %51,26 ısı verimlilik ile %49,49 ekserji verimlilik değerlerine ulaşabilen geleneksel

konfigürasyonu temsil etmektedir. Model 2 ise, parabolik oluklu güneş kolektörü (PTC) aracılığıyla güneş enerjisinin entegre edildiği sistem performansını önemli ölçüde arttıran yapıyı temsil etmektedir. Bu konfigürasyon, ısı ve ekserji verimlilik değerlerini sırasıyla %59,97 ve %57,91'e çıkarırken, net güç çıkışını 211,7 MW'tan 232,4 MW'a çıkartmaktadır. Ancak, Model 2'nin ekonomik analizleri, güneş enerjisi entegrasyonu nedeniyle daha yüksek işletme maliyetleri ortaya koyarak, daha fazla maliyet optimizasyonuna ihtiyaç olduğunu göstermektedir.

Model 3, en gelişmiş yapılandırma olarak, düşük dereceli atık ısının etkin şekilde geri kazanılması için PTC'yi absorpsiyonlu soğutma sistemi (ARS) ile birleştirmektedir. Bu yenilikçi tasarım, maksimum %61,19 ısı verimlilik ve %59,08 ekserji verimliliğine ulaşırken, 240,2 MW net güç üretimi sağlamaktadır. ARS, özellikle yüksek basınç oranı (PR) ve gaz türbini giriş sıcaklığı (GTIT) koşullarında, termodinamik performansı artırarak tersinmezlikleri ve soğutma taleplerini azaltmaktadır. Bu yapılandırma, sabit işletme maliyetleri ve temel modele kıyasla önemli ölçüde azalmış sera gazı emisyonları ile üstün ekonomik uygulanabilirlik sergilemektedir.

Araştırma, PR, GTIT ve yüksek basınçlı buhar türbini giriş sıcaklığı gibi kritik parametrelerin sistem performansının optimizasyonundaki rolünü incelemektedir. Termoekonomik analiz, PR'ye bağlı olarak 71 \$/MWh ile 74,7 \$/MWh arasında değişen farklı işletme koşulları altında en düşük elektrik maliyetlerini sağlayan Model 3'ün maliyet etkinliğini ortaya koymaktadır. Çevresel analiz ise, karbondioksit emisyonlarında önemli azalmalar göstererek Model 3'ü en sürdürülebilir yapılandırma olarak öne çıkarmaktadır.

Bu çalışma, yüksek güneş potansiyeline sahip bölgelerde güneş enerjisi ile gelişmiş atık ısı geri kazanım teknolojilerinin entegrasyonunun stratejik önemini vurgulamaktadır. Küresel enerji sürdürülebilirliği hedefleriyle uyumlu hibrit güç üretim sistemlerinin tasarımı ve optimizasyonu için sağlam bir çerçeve sunmaktadır. Araştırma bulguları, Kerkük Gaz Santrali'nde Model 3'ün benimsenmesinin enerji verimliliğini önemli ölçüde artırabileceğini, çevresel etkileri azaltabileceğini ve Irak'ın daha temiz enerji üretimine geçişini destekleyebileceğini göstermektedir. Bu

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Anahtar Sözcükler : Çevresel analiz, Absorpsiyonlu soğutma sistemi (ARS), Atık ısı geri kazanımı, Sürdürülebilir enerji sistemleri, Kerkük gaz santrali (ISCC), Eksergoekonomik analiz.

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SYMBOLS AND ABBREVIATIONS INDEX

SYMBOLS

A_a	: Solar collector area (m^2)
A_r	: area of the receiver or absorber
\dot{C}	: Cost rate (\$/h)
\dot{C}_D	: cost rate of exergy destruction
\dot{E}_d	: exergy destruction rate
$\dot{E}x_{dest}$: Rate of exergy destruction (kW)
$\dot{E}x$: Exergy (kW)
f_k	: Thermoeconomics factor (%)
F_R	: Collector heat gain factor
h	: Enthalpy, (kJ/kg)
h_{rr}	: Radiative heat transfer coefficient between the receiver and the glass cover ($W/m^2 \cdot K$)
h_{rc}	: Radiative heat transfer coefficient between the collector surface ($W/m^2 \cdot K$)
k	: Conductivity heat transfer ($W/m \cdot K$)
\dot{m}	: Mass flow rate (kg/s)
n	: Predicted life of the system's (years)
P	: Predicted life of the system's (years)
$P_{in,HPST}$: High pressure steam turbine inlet pressure (bar)
\dot{Q}	: Heat rate (kW)
\dot{Q}_{solar}	: Solar energy input (kW)
S	: solar energy absorbed by PTC
T_{amb}	: Ambient Temperature
$T_{in,HPST}$: High pressure steam turbine inlet temperature (K)
\dot{W}	: Work by the control volume per unit time (kW)

\dot{Z}_k	: Entire cost rate
T	: Temperature (K)
η_{ex}	: Exergy efficiency (%)
η_{th}	: Thermal efficiency (%)
α	: receiver's absorption coefficient
γ	: reflection coefficient
τ	: coefficient of the glass cover
φ	: Total operating and maintenance cost
ε_{CO_2}	: Emission Rate of CO ₂ (kg CO ₂ /MWh)

ABBREVIATIONS

AC	: Air compressor
ARS	: Absorption refrigeration system
BC	: Brayton cycle
CC	: Combustion chamber
CCPP	: Combined cycle power plant
Cond	: Condenser
CRF	: Capital Recovery Factor
DNI	: Direct normal irradiation (kWh/ m ² .day)
EES	: Engineering Equation Solver
EVAP	: Evaporator
GEN	: Generator
GT	: Gas Turbine
GTCC	: Gas Turbine Combined Cycle
GTIT	: Gas turbine inlet temperature
HE	: Heat exchanger
HPST	: High-pressure steam turbine
HRSG	: Heat recovery steam generation
HTF	: Heat transfer fluid
IGTPP	: Integrated gas turbine power plant
IPST	: Intermediate-pressure steam turbine
ISCC	: Integrated solar combined cycle
KC	: Kalina cycle
LCOE	: Levelized cost of electricity
LHV	: Fuel's lower heating value
LPST	: Low-pressure steam turbine
NG	: Natural gas
NGCC	: Natural gas combined cycle
OFWH	: Open feed water heater
ORC	: Organic Rankine cycle
ORP	: Organic pump
ORT	: Organic turbine

PP	: Power plant
PR	: Pressure Ratio
PTC	: Parabolic trough collector
RC	: Rankine Cycle
RES	: Renewable energy source
RH	: Relative humidity
RP	: Renewable part
SF	: Solar Field
SRC	: Steam Rankin Cycle
ST	: Steam Turbine
TES	: Thermal energy storage
<i>PEC</i>	: Purchase equipment

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

The worldwide rise in the consumption of electricity, fueled by population growth, urbanization, and industrial expansion, has put tremendous pressure on power generation infrastructure. Gas turbine power plants, an essential part of electricity generation, face crucial issues such as insufficient thermal efficiency, excessive fuel use, and environmental deterioration due to high emissions. Such worries are especially clear in places like Iraq, where a significant reliance on fossil fuels gets worse by extreme weather conditions. Nevertheless, such places' significant solar energy potential offers a fascinating chance to address these issues. By integrating solar energy with traditional gas turbine plants and leveraging advanced technologies such as waste heat recovery and inlet air cooling, major increases in performance, efficiency, and sustainability can be noticed [1].

Solar collectors play a vital part in thermal energy collection by transforming solar radiation into useful heat. This obtained energy is used to produce electricity, heat water, dry crops for agriculture, and purify water. Solar thermal energy technology is recognized for its efficiency and flexibility, making it a crucial element of green energy solutions. Unlike traditional power generation methods, solar energy generates no pollutants, guarantees a low environmental impact, and increases safety. Solar systems are also environmentally friendly because they are renewable, produce no pollutants, and run silently. Solar collectors are among the most successful renewable energy methods for turning sunlight into heat. Nevertheless, solar thermal power plants face numerous challenges, including high production costs for components, heliostats, receivers, and large infrastructure needs. To address such constraints, integrating solar energy with traditional electrical cycles provides a synergistic method that improves both practicality and efficiency [2].

1.1. BACKGROUND AND MOTIVATION

Growing concerns about the environment and an explosive rise in worldwide demand for energy are causing a transformational shift in the energy sector. This change encourages governments to adopt more sustainable and more efficient energy choices. Gas turbine power stations, which reflect the world's dependency on fossil fuels, significantly contribute to greenhouse gas emissions and environmental harm. These effects, demonstrated as climate change and ecosystem trouble, are increasing the urgency of moving to sustainable energy systems. In developing countries like Iraq, the need for sustainable growth is more critical. Energy shortages and the environmental effects of fossil fuel use deliver significant challenges to sustainable development, economic growth, and human well-being [3]. The transition to alternative electricity generation puts a high value on renewable energy sources like solar, wind, and geothermal technology. Solar energy, in particular, has gained movement, with Integrated Solar Combined Cycle (ISCC) facilities gaining interest as fossil fuel reserves decrease and carbon emissions must be reduced. Collecting waste heat, particularly from commercial exhaust gases, is a promising way to reduce the consumption of fossil fuels and pollution. Nevertheless, implementing advanced thermal or power cycles requires a large investment, resulting in efforts to optimize high-efficiency integrated systems. Iraq's energy framework primarily depends on gas turbine power facilities, which employ natural gas and oil as essential fuels. While these systems are highly effective, they emit large quantities of carbon dioxide and pollute the air, causing serious concerns about environmental damage. The rising demand for electricity, especially in northern Iraqi areas like Kirkuk, where air conditioning units run continuously during hot summers, has put tremendous pressure on the country's supply of electricity. Despite a worldwide push for sustainability, governments are increasingly participating in international agreements like the Paris Agreement, working cooperatively to address climate change issues and promote cleaner energy alternatives [4]. The growing global need for more sustainable energy is pressing Iraq to lessen its reliance on oil and gas, resulting in an investigation of renewable energy sources like hydroelectric and geothermal. This shift has led to large investments in innovative power plant technologies and the development of alternative power resources, particularly solar energy, leading to

significant growth in industry. Modern power systems must do more than just produce electricity; they must additionally provide a wide range of energy outputs, like steam, hot water, and compressed air, all provided simultaneously and effectively [5]. Putting refrigeration and air conditioning systems for compressed air throughout power plants is crucial, particularly in summer when temperatures rise considerably. High temperatures and elevated humidity levels significantly limit efficiency and electrical output, reducing the plant's total performance. High heat and moisture significantly stress equipment, reducing power generation capacity. Therefore, implementing efficient cooling systems is essential to maintain optimum operational efficiency while avoiding costly equipment failures [6]. Iraq's large sunny regions and strategic geographical position make it an ideal location for capturing solar energy, offering a practical and financially viable solution for long-term power generation. Although Iraq has vast solar energy potential, widespread use has been delayed by financial constraints, insufficient facilities, and technological limitations. In recent years, Iraq is experiencing an enormous electricity shortage, with regular blackouts affecting daily life and economic operations. This substantial demand for change has led policymakers to assess alternate electricity generation technologies, paying attention to environmental impact and cost-effectiveness. Given Iraq's availability of sunlight and dry climate, the government is increasingly examining solar power as a sustainable, long-term alternative to its energy concerns [7]. PTC systems use properly positioned mirrors to focus sun radiation and convert it to heat energy. When integrated with conventional gas turbine facilities, this heat source enables seamless and efficient operations, improving overall efficiency while decreasing energy waste. These hybrid systems increase power plant performance while also providing significant environmental and economic advantages by lowering fuel consumption and related pollutants [8]. During the compression stage, temperature and humidity are substantially decreased, as is airflow, and typical industrial odors decrease. This phenomenon presents significant efficiency issues for big gas turbine plants, especially in hot, arid areas. To address these difficulties, significant research has been conducted on the integration of solar power plants with thermal energy storage systems and absorbing chillers, stated in the literature on the subject [9][10]. Integrating solar energy systems, including simplified designs and efficient energy extraction, into current power generation systems represent a big

step forward in green power development. This approach gives a technologically advanced and ecologically responsible approach to today's energy concerns [11]. Iraq has faced decades of political instabilities, civil unrest, and financial difficulties that are hampering efforts to build a stable economy. Despite having the fourth-largest economy in the Middle East, that is fueled by enormous oil supplies, the country's energy demand continues to rise due to growing populations and harsh temperatures. Increasing summer temperatures have boosted dependence on air conditioning, putting a strain on infrastructures and threatening economic growth. To overcome these worries, updating power facilities and investing in clean energy sources such as solar and wind are essential [12]. Integrating SRC and ORC systems into gas turbine power plants increases thermal efficiency, enhances power generation, and reduces the impact on the environment. The SRC system collects high-grade waste heat from high temperatures exhaust gases, while the ORC system collects low-grade waste heat since it works at lower temperatures. Together, they provide a flexible and effective method to sustainable electricity generation [13]. Those integrated cycles work together to minimize heat waste, minimize fuel usage, and optimize system efficiency. The final outcome is a smooth, effective procedure that gently emphasizes the system's efficiency [14]. The work at hand looks at integrating new technology into a gas turbine facility in Kirkuk, Iraq, to enhance efficiency and dependability in difficult circumstances. It demonstrates the potential for sustainable power production in hybrid systems through the combination of solar thermal energy and thermodynamic cycles. The research seeks to provide practical solutions that reduce dependency on fossil fuels, satisfy rising energy demands, and reduce environmental harm.

1.2. SOLAR THERMAL ENERGY CONVERSION

Solar collectors primarily convert solar energy into thermal energy by absorbing sunlight and transferring the heat to fluid. Solar radiation is captured by the absorber mechanism, turning into thermal energy that the flowing heat transfer fluid transfers. The efficient transfer of thermal energy to the power cycle, which may include systems such as the organic Rankine cycle (ORC), steam cycle, or combined cycle, is facilitated through a series of well-designed components. Depending on the system

design and application, examples of heat transfer fluids include viscous, dark oil, easily flowing, clear water, and glowing, hot molten salts. Cooling is achieved through heat transfer using air, which might whoosh and hum, water, with its gentle gurgle, or a glycol loop, characterized by the rhythmic whoosh of pumps. Alternatively, a closed-loop system could transfer thermal energy underground, using pipes to circulate fluid and exchange heat with the surrounding earth. The thermal energy collected during the day, feeling the residual warmth of the sun, can be stored for later use, ensuring a continuous supply of power into the night. Thermal energy storage tanks are used to achieve this; heat transfer fluids within these tanks facilitate the charging and discharging processes, with the tanks often well-insulated to minimize heat loss. Combined cycles are vital for producing cleaner electricity, particularly in areas with existing CCGT plants, offering a practical, low-carbon solution. The machinery's whir and efficient energy conversion are obvious. Integrating solar fields with current CCGT plants offers a practical, efficient solution. The solar field functions as a regenerator with this configuration, boosting performance through integration with aero-derivative topping gas turbines [15]. Among the numerous technologies harnessing solar energy, concentrated solar power (CSP) technology stands out as exceptionally promising. Concentrated solar collectors in CSP are designed to function at higher temperatures compared to alternative technologies. Thermal energy storage, hybrid system operation, and the potential to function as a combined heat and power plant make CSP the most versatile technology for generating electricity from renewable sources. Parabolic trough collectors, also known as PTCs, have been widely used in various Concentrated Solar Power Plants (CSPPs). Presently, parabolic trough power plants are in operation as a result of their testing in a commercial setting [16]. CCGTs are the preferred choice for conventional thermal power plants due to their high efficiency, rapid start-up time, and minimal impact on the environment. By utilizing its versatile unit dispatch capabilities, it becomes easier to incorporate a greater amount of renewable energy into the grid. The widespread development of CCGT power plants is attributed to their exceptional thermodynamic efficiency, which has been observed worldwide. Gas turbine efficiency plays a crucial role in shaping the design and concept of modern CCGT power plants. Various applications are available for solar systems in combination with CCGT plants. To make this choice,

one must consider the foundational needs of the system. The overall system must accommodate varying requirements for each application. One possibility is that the power output from the solar field can be dedicated to either the bottoming steam Rankine cycle or air bottoming cycles. The fresh air mixing unit can be heated by diverting a portion of the thermal energy produced by the solar field. Before the intercooler regeneration takes place, the steam generated by the solar field can be utilized in specific instances. Each option offers the possibility of using a distinct evaporative cooler instead of direct water cooling for the CCGT plant [17].

1.3. COMBINED CYCLE POWER PLANT PRINCIPLES (CCPP)

Gas turbines operating on the Brayton cycle are the primary engines driving electricity generation in combined-cycle power plants. HRSGs boost power output by using waste heat from gas turbines to generate steam power. Gas turbines can burn many fuels, such as natural gas and diesel.

HRSG efficiently captures waste heat from the turbine's exhaust, converting it into usable energy within the steam power cycle. This recovered energy can be utilized for mechanical processes, heating applications, or electrical power generation. Figure 1.1. presents a simplified schematic of the combined cycle system, providing a clear illustration of its design and operational principles [18].

The core components of a combined cycle power plant include a gas turbine (GT), which generates intense heat to drive the system, a Heat Recovery Steam Generator (HRSG) that converts water into high-pressure steam, and one or more steam turbines that transform this steam into electricity. Additionally, the system can incorporate a steam treatment setup consisting of a filling valve, deaerator, feed-water pump, and economizer to enhance performance and efficiency.

HRSG typically comprises three main sections: high-temperature and low-temperature superheater components (commonly referred to as evaporators) and an economizer, also known as the hot water section. Incorporating a fired economizer is highly recommended, as it allows for precise control of steam temperature and

improves overall system performance by utilizing auxiliary fuel to generate additional heat [19].

Figure 1.1. Schematic illustration of a combined cycle main parts [18].

Combined cycle power plants utilize HRSGs custom-designed to complement their specific gas turbine. Many of these designs use advanced features such as dual-pressure, reheating, and gas bypass systems for better efficiency and performance [20].

Combined cycle systems commonly use single or dual-pressure (reheat) steam turbines for optimal energy conversion. Their higher efficiency (45–55%, unlike 30–35% of gas turbines) and superior responsiveness to demand fluctuations make combined cycle power plants better than other grid power plants [21].

1.4. INTEGRATED SOLAR POWER PLANT (ISCC) BENEFITS AND CHALLENGES

Integrating solar thermal systems with combined cycle power plants offers significant synergistic benefits, enhancing the performance of both technologies. For

improved efficiency and environmental sustainability, the most effective approach is to combine Concentrating Solar Power (CSP) with natural gas turbines using Integrated Solar Combined Cycle (ISCC) systems [22].

During peak sun hours, the solar thermal system seamlessly integrates with the combined cycle, harnessing ample solar flux. By reducing the demand for gas in the gas turbines, operational costs are decreased. The steam it supplies can be used in the Rankine cycle or directly in the heat recovery steam generator of the combined cycle, resulting in increased power output and improved efficiency.

Moreover, the integration of GTCC presents the opportunity to employ the combined cycle as a reliable backup for the solar-powered steam cycle. Regarding efficiency or costs, the modified Rankine cycle ORC surpasses the use of HTF or direct steam solar systems, making it a more captivating choice. Despite the high investment in an ORC for solar and the adaptation of GTCC to integrate the ORC solar, there is a need for further emission reductions and improvements in the CO₂ market [23]. With its remarkable efficiency, outstanding performance, and capability to generate high power at useful inlet temperatures, the gas turbine stands out as the most suitable option for pairing with CSP systems. This guarantees a steady and predictable supply of electricity and heat, all at a low cost of generation [24].

The ISCC system can be established using various cycle systems, including superior steam Rankine, Organic Rankine, Trilateral, and Kalina cycles, each with specific relationships. In addition to its primary function, the ISCC system can be flexibly employed for absorption and adsorption refrigeration. Moreover, it can manage energy imbalances by storing surplus electricity and delivering extra electricity to the grid when there is a shortage. The ISCC showcased its ability to provide continuous electricity and heat, reducing uncertainty in pricing and supply. Additionally, it featured an efficient energy storage system that could endure for long durations, all while minimizing plant expenses per kWh, MWh, or GWh [25].

1.5. TYPES OF CSP TECHNOLOGIES

Various solar technologies capture direct solar irradiation and convert it into usable energy. Among these, concentrated solar power (CSP) systems stand out for their high-efficiency thermal energy conversion. CSP technology uses reflectors to concentrate solar radiation onto a receiver, where a heat transfer fluid absorbs the heat and transfers it to a thermodynamic process. CSP technologies are categorized into line-focusing and point-focusing systems, as shown in Figure 1.2. Choosing the right CSP technology depends on key factors, such as fixed or movable receivers and the desired concentration level, whether medium or high[26].

Figure 1.2. CSP technologies [27].

Linear Fresnel and parabolic trough technologies are part of line focusing, whereas solar tower and parabolic dish belong to point focusing [27]. The depicted configurations of these technologies can be seen in (a, b, c, and d) [28].

Figure 1.3. Types of solar thermal technologies [28].

1.5.1. Parabolic Through Collector (PTC)

As shown in Figure 1.3, the parabolic trough collector is a key solar energy system featuring long, curved mirrors shaped like a parabolic cylinder. This design reflects and concentrates sunlight parallel to the focal axis onto a central tube, maximizing energy capture.

The concentrated sunlight significantly raises the temperature of the heat transfer fluid in the tube, typically ranging from 400 K to 1050 K. High-capacity systems can sometimes achieve temperatures of 1250 K or higher. The receiver pipe absorbs the redirected solar rays from the mirrors, facilitating efficient heat transfer [29].

PTCs are highly effective, especially in large-scale solar power plants, due to their efficient design and ability to produce high-temperature heat for clean, sustainable energy. Ongoing advancements in materials, manufacturing, and system integration continue to improve their performance and cost-effectiveness [30]. PTCs are the most widely utilized and researched commercial technology for electricity and heat generation globally. As a result, this study centers on parabolic trough collectors [31].

1.5.2. Linear Fresnel Reflector

Curved mirrors in parabolic trough systems reflect sunlight into the receiving tube, resulting in concentrated heat. They utilize one- or two-axis following to maximize energy capture, dynamically changing mirror placements during the day [32]. Linear Fresnel reflector (LFR) systems reflect sunlight onto a fixed receiver using rows of flat or slightly curving mirrors, resulting in extreme heat. This design offers flexibility, with bending mirrors that enable fine light control. A major benefit is its capacity to generate steam directly for power cycles, which reduces the need for heat transfer fluids and more heat exchangers, simplifies the system, and conserves money. Compared to PTC systems, LFR technology minimizes capital and operating expenses. However, its use in ISCC plants is limited, probably due to lower optical quality, thermal efficiency, and problems like angle-of-incidence and angular losses, which decrease heat output when compared with PTC systems.

1.5.3. Solar Power Towers

Solar power towers are commonly used in modern solar power plants, offering an efficient method of obtaining solar energy for large-scale electricity production. These systems comprise a collector field of heliostats—large, carefully chosen

mirrors that follow the sun's movement and reflect concentrated sunlight onto a central receiver above the tower. The receiver serves as a heat exchanger, conveying collected thermal energy to a heat transfer fluid or directly to a working fluid such as molten salt or water. This technology enables solar power towers to operate at extremely high temperatures, efficiently converting solar energy into thermal energy, which may then be used to produce electricity using steam-driven turbines. Accurately controlling heliostats and central receivers enables optimal energy capture and system efficiency [33]. A solar power tower system utilizes dual-axis tracker mirrors (heliostats) that direct sunlight to a central receiver above a tower. Inside the receiver, a heat transfer fluid (HTF) like molten salt, air, or water is heated to 500°C-1000°C, acting as a heat source for electricity production or energy storage [34].

Molten salt as a heat transfer fluid (HTF) offers effective and low-cost thermal energy storage (TES), enabling solar power facilities to achieve high-capacity factors (CF), particularly during peak summer demand. Given their benefits, molten salt-based solar power towers have yet to gain essential commercial adoption.

A unique solar power tower design uses air as a heat transfer fluid to produce energy utilizing an air turbine cycle. This approach offers an efficient and cost-effective method for sustainable power generation. Current solar thermal systems report a Levelized cost of electricity (LCOE) between 80 and 420 \$/MWh, making them both economical and environmentally viable for large-scale energy production [35].

Steinhagen et al. [36] argued that a central receiver typically absorbs solar energy using a heat transfer fluid. After absorbing the solar heat, the fluid circulates through a heat exchanger, where it transfers its thermal energy to water, generating steam. This steam is then used to generate electricity through conventional generators. The exceptional concentrating capability of solar power towers allows them to reach extremely high temperatures, enhancing power plant efficiency and reducing thermal storage costs. Ongoing research and development efforts focus on improving the efficiency and cost-effectiveness of solar power towers. Solar tower systems'

advancements position them as a crucial technology for the global transition to clean and sustainable energy solutions.

Sachdeva et al.[37] proposed a solar-powered triple combined cycle integrating BC, SRC, and (ORC) using R245fa, eliminating combustion for carbon-free power. The system employs heliostat-concentrated solar energy to heat molten salt, driving compressed air in a gas turbine, with exhaust heat cascading to steam and ORC turbines. maximum thermal efficiency of 33.15% at a cycle pressure ratio of 24, producing 331.59 kW/kg of air, with second-law efficiencies of 97.07% (gas turbine), 81.33% (ORC turbine), and 79.5–80.31% (steam turbines). The study highlights optimal steam bleed fractions (20%) and high-pressure steam conditions (50–60 bar) for performance enhancement, demonstrating feasibility for low-emission, high-efficiency solar-hybrid power generation.

1.5.4. Parabolic Dish Collector

Parabolic dish systems use mirrors shaped into dish-like reflectors to concentrate solar radiation onto a receiver at the dish's focal point. In the receiver, a working fluid, such as hydrogen, is heated and drives either a Stirling engine or a small turbine. Most modern parabolic dish systems rely on Stirling engine technology due to its high solar-to-electric conversion efficiency, reaching around 30%, among the highest for concentrated solar power (CSP) systems.

Parabolic dish systems offer a modular design, with units around 25 kW, enabling scalable and incremental plant expansion. Unlike parabolic trough PTC and linear Fresnel LFC systems, they require no water for cooling, making them ideal for arid or water-scarce regions.

However, these systems currently face significant challenges regarding reliability for large-scale commercial applications. Currently, no large-scale parabolic dish power plants are in operation to provide utility-scale services. A notable example is the Maricopa Solar Project in Arizona, USA, which began production in January 2010.

The 1.5 MW plant uses six 250 kW parabolic dishes; however, larger systems haven't been commercially developed.

Barlev et al. [38], argued that the parabolic dish system's collector is strategically positioned at its focal point to capture concentrated solar irradiation efficiently. The dish and the receiver are equipped with tracking mechanisms that follow the sun's movement throughout the day, ensuring optimal energy capture. Among all (CSP) technologies, parabolic dish systems achieve the highest concentration ratio and solar-to-electric efficiency. However, these advantages are accompanied by significant drawbacks. The installation costs of parabolic dish systems are considerably high, and integrating thermal energy storage (TES) continues to pose a technical challenge. These factors have impeded the widespread commercial adoption of this technology despite its promising efficiency and modular potential.

1.6. IMPACT OF CONTROLLING COMPRESSOR AIR INLET COOLING

Integrating gas turbine technology with systems such as steam cycles, refrigeration cycles, and simple cycles operating at varying pressure levels offers numerous advantages, including improved system efficiency and reduced emissions. For example, combining gas turbines with heat recovery and topping cycles can substantially enhance performance. However, there is limited research on integrating gas turbines with various cycles to address emissions linked to compressor inlet cooling in gas turbines [39].

Moreover, there is a notable lack of data addressing the environmental challenges associated with proposed energy systems specifically designed for Kirkuk City, underscoring the novelty of this study's objectives. The primary aim of the proposed system is to meet Kirkuk's energy demands while enhancing performance by reducing compressor inlet cooling temperatures, improving overall power cycle and thermal efficiency, and optimizing exhaust parameters. These advancements lead to a significant reduction in emissions from gas turbine burners, providing an environmentally sustainable solution for Kirkuk City. The performance of gas turbines is significantly affected by ambient temperature, with power output

decreasing as temperatures rise. This phenomenon occurs because warmer air has a higher specific volume, requiring greater energy input during the compression stage [40].

1.7. EXERGY AND ENERGY ANALYSIS

The first law of thermodynamics is founded on the principle of energy conservation, which states that energy cannot be created or destroyed. It asserts that the net work output of a device operating in a cycle cannot exceed the net heat input to the working fluid. Mathematically, the first law is expressed through energy balance equations, applicable to both closed-system cycles and steady-flow systems. Conversely, the second law of thermodynamics governs the natural progression of processes, which inherently dissipate useful energy into a more disordered or less usable form. This law defines the direction of spontaneous processes, establishes the efficiency limits of heat engines, and provides a foundation for calculating the maximum possible work output from a thermodynamic cycle. Furthermore, it underscores the concept of energy quality, emphasizing that energy utilization inevitably results in a degradation of its quality over time [41].

Energy losses in power plants are classified as either reversible or irreversible. The total energy input to a power plant comprises both useful energy and lost, unavailable energy, the latter diminishing the plant's overall capacity. The first category of unavailable energy loss stems from system irreversibilities, while the second arises due to the external dead state, which is caused by temperature gradients between the plant's operating conditions and the surrounding environment [42]. The concept of exergy, often termed 'second-law efficiency,' evaluates the quality of energy and accounts for associated losses. Exergy decreases due to system irreversibilities and further declines with the increase in unavailable energy. Power plants experiencing energy and exergy losses operate less efficiently and contribute to environmental pollution, necessitating financial resources to mitigate the harmful emissions produced. Energy and exergy analysis serves as a critical tool for understanding and optimizing these processes [43].

Energy and exergy analyses have been extensively applied to various power plant systems. Early applications focused on conventional technologies such as steam power plants, gas turbines, combined cycle systems, cogeneration, combined heat and power (CHP) systems, standalone and integrated heating, refrigeration, and power cycles, as well as absorption and adsorption refrigeration systems, Rankine cycles, and organic Rankine cycles [44].

This work performs an exergy and energy analysis for integrating gas turbines with integrated solar combined cycles with different types of cycles. The critical parameters are also examined by the plant for predicting the results of how all these evaluations could help to improve energy efficiencies that affect the power plant performance with environmental consideration.

1.8. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Iraq's energy sector relies primarily on natural gas and oil to generate electricity. The main source of electricity is gas turbine power plants, which easily convert fuel into electricity but significantly affect the nation's carbon emissions. [45]. In response to Iraq's growing need for power, the environmental impacts of the country's reliance on fossil fuels are becoming progressively problematic, particularly considering the Paris Agreement's promise to decrease greenhouse gas emissions. This makes using Integrated Solar Combined Cycle (ISCC) systems an essential approach to solving these issues. Population growth, industrial expansion, and urbanization have all led to an ongoing rise in electricity demand in Iraq [46]. Adopting ISCC systems is essential for addressing these challenges and enhancing energy efficiency. Iraq's electricity demand has been steadily rising, driven by population growth, industrial expansion, and urbanization, resulting in frequent power outages and shortages. This issue is particularly pronounced in Kirkuk, where rapid urban development and a growing population have placed significant strain on an already fragile energy grid, leading to recurring blackouts and power shortages [47]. Significant loss of heat energy, which frequently shows up in high thermal emissions near exhaust systems, affects the overall efficiency of gas turbine power plants, stressing the vital need for modern waste heat recovery solutions. Iraq's enormous solar energy potential has led

to a growing interest in integrating renewable energy technologies into Iraq's electricity generation infrastructure. Among these, PTCs, an essential aspect of solar thermal technology, provide a promising solution for decreasing reliance on fossil fuels. These technologies assist in providing a more sustainable and environmentally friendly energy future by using concentrated solar heat to enhance power generation processes. The whirring of the machinery and the warm air around the collectors are a testament to this process [48] [49]. This study assesses the possibility of integrating (PTC), (SRC), and (ORC) technologies into a gas turbine power plant in Kirkuk. It evaluates technological issues, cost-effectiveness, and impact on the environment. While previous studies have focused on the integration of solar and conventional power plants, an important gap remains in real-world applications, where the harsh desert climate offers surpassing opportunities for renewable energy development. [50]. This study examines Iraq's energy sector through a case study, considering cost, reliability, and environmental effects, providing insights that will assist Iraqi policymakers develop sustainable energy while decreasing fossil fuel-related pollution.

1.9. OBJECTIVES

The primary objectives of this research are summarized as follows:

- To analyze the potential of integrating renewable energy sources with gas turbine plants by studying the impact of solar energy integration in improving power generation efficiency and enhancing energy security in Kirkuk, Iraq.
- To evaluate the efficiency of waste heat recovery technologies by analyzing the effectiveness of steam Rankine cycles (SRC) and organic Rankine cycles (ORC) in utilizing waste heat to improve plant efficiency.
- To evaluate the economic feasibility of hybrid systems by studying the financial feasibility of applying hybrid power systems by analyzing operating costs, energy savings, and return on investment.
- To study the scalability and adaptability of hybrid systems by evaluating the ability of hybrid power plants to meet the growing energy demand in Iraq and supporting the development of sustainable and environmentally friendly energy policies.

1.10. SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The study is expected to significantly expand the knowledge of hybrid energy systems, especially in developing countries such as Iraq, providing useful insights into how they can be used and their possible benefits. Effectively integrating solar thermal PTC, SRC, and ORC technologies into a gas turbine generator in Kirkuk—a region identified for its dusty, sunny landscape. The study highlights an encouraging approach to clean energy generation. The effective operation of these systems highlights their technical interest and presents them as a model for other regions having similar energy problems.

This research will provide essential data to assist Iraq in reducing its reliance on fossil fuels, leading to fewer greenhouse gas emissions and an environmentally friendly energy future. This study can significantly influence policy decisions affecting Iraq's energy sector, leading to more sustainable and efficient procedures in the long term. The study showing hybrid energy systems' technical reliability and commercial viability might change Iraq's renewable energy future while promoting more sustainable energy consumption. The extensive cost-benefit analysis evaluations and technical requirements in the study provide an excellent basis for this influence.

The findings of this research are especially important for Iraqi officials, engineers, and energy developers, as they offer a roadmap to addressing energy issues while fulfilling global sustainability requirements. The consequences for Iraq's development of renewable energy are considerable.

CHAPTER 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, the exponential growth of civilization and industrialization has prompted heightened concerns regarding greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions within society. Consequently, there has been a significant shift in focus towards non-conventional energy sources such as solar, wind, geothermal, and others.

The availability of fossil fuels and the environmental impact of their combustion are the two primary concerns for conventional power plants. By integrating a solar cycle with conventional power plants, the energy landscape can be improved, tackling major challenges in industry. The increasing interest in CSP plants can be attributed to their higher efficiency, lower operational costs, and significant potential for expansion. The utilization of various technologies for power generation fuels this interest.

The solar collector captures solar energy and transfers it to the receiver through the heat transfer fluid, enabling efficient energy transfer. This receiver establishes intricate connections with the thermodynamic cycle, effectively employing heat. Using a heat transfer fluid, the receiver's heat is moved to the HRSG for steam generation. Mechanical energy is produced by steam driving a turbine within the heat engine, despite some heat being lost. Finally, the mechanical energy powers a generator, creating electricity and completing energy conversion. Concentrated solar power technology uses various components to convert sunlight into electricity. To optimize the plant's overall efficiency, careful consideration of the various aspects of these components is required. When considering a solar-integrated combined cycle, carefully selecting accompanying components becomes crucial due to the

interdependence of their performances. Several similarities exist in the issues and technical strategic decisions of solar deployment. Yousef et al. [51] analyzed the alignment of CSP with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) through a bibliometric study. Their research highlights CSP cooling applications' indirect contributions to SDG 1 (no poverty) and SDG 3 (good health and well-being). Utilizing a decade-long dataset, the study identifies China as the primary contributor to CSP research, followed by the USA, Italy, the UK, Spain, and France, with a peak in publications observed in 2020. The findings highlight the growing need for hybrid CSP systems to enhance energy efficiency and expand application potential

Al-Saadi et al. [52] examined the challenges and opportunities for modernizing Iraq's petroleum infrastructure amid volatile global markets. With oil accounting for over 65% of GDP and 90% of government revenue, their study underscores the sector's critical role in Iraq's economy while identifying key barriers to its growth, including aging infrastructure, insufficient investment, and geopolitical instability. To address these challenges, the authors propose strategies such as infrastructure upgrades, attracting foreign investment, adopting innovative technologies, and regulatory reforms. The analysis provides a roadmap to strengthen Iraq's oil sector against global economic fluctuations and enhance its global market competitiveness. However, Iraq's heavy reliance on oil has diverted attention from broader energy infrastructure, contributing to chronic power shortages.

2.2. GAS TURBINE POWER PLANT: EFFICIENCY AND ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACT

Gas turbines are important for electricity generation because of their flexibility and adaptability. However, their dependence on fossil fuels makes them an important contributor to greenhouse gas emissions. Consequently, recent studies have prioritized enhancing gas turbine efficiency and lessening emissions by employing advanced materials, fuel blends, and optimization algorithms.

Xing et al. [53] analyzed the combustion dynamics of a micro-mixing gas turbine combustor under varying fuel compositions and operational temperatures. Experiments compared pure hydrogen (H_2) and a 50/50 hydrogen/carbon monoxide (H_2/CO) blend at elevated fuel temperatures. Hydrogen combustion needs longer axial liners when compared to H_2/CO mixes due to the extended high-temperature flue gas region downstream. The study additionally offered the best axial liner length-to-fuel hole diameter ratios across both fuels for optimum combustion efficiency. These findings expand the design of fuel-flexible gas turbines, especially for hydrogen power systems, while offering actionable engineering alternatives for sustainable energy applications.

Kazemi et al. [54] evaluated 19 alternative NGCC power plant layouts, which included CO_2 capture methods. The study investigated CO_2 capture methods, comprising pre-combustion, post-combustion, and oxyfuel, utilizing different absorbents and ORCs to improve energy efficiency. Findings show that a-MDEA surpasses MEA as a CO_2 absorbent for pre- and post-combustion capture methods, providing important technical and economic advantages. Integrating ORCs enhances the efficiency and economic viability of CO_2 -capturing NGCC power plants, decreasing payback periods by up to 1.39 years according to configuration. This research emphasizes the possibility of enhanced NGCC power plant designs with advanced CO_2 absorbents and ORCs, leading to improved performance and cost-effective carbon capture alternatives.

Jia et al. [55] examined a large-scale hybrid renewable energy system that combined wind, sun, gas turbines, and energy storage systems. The researchers developed a complex optimization model to identify the optimal system construction and power delivery method, balancing economic efficiency versus lifecycle carbon emissions. The findings show that integrating gas turbines with hydrogen-based energy storage significantly decreases carbon emissions and renewable energy reduction, albeit at higher operational costs. To enhance economic efficiency, the study suggests utilizing electrochemical energy storage to manage grid problems when gas turbines run at low loads, thus enhancing system operations and reducing natural gas use.

Köse et al. [56] performed a 4E analysis of single, dual, and triple power system configurations integrating gas turbines GT with steam Rankine SRC and Kalina KC cycles. The study found that a single Rankine cycle recovered 30.74% of waste heat, while a Kalina cycle recovered 24.99%. A dual GT-SRC system increased thermal efficiency to 41.72%, and a triple GT-SRC-KC system achieved 46.39%. The highest net power outputs were 7946.82 kW (GT-SRC) and 8836.96 kW (GT-SRC-KC). CO₂ emissions were reduced by up to 1687 tons per hour using the dual RC-KC system. Economic analysis showed 3.22–3.48-year payback periods, proving financial viability.

2.3. STEAM RANKINE CYCLE (SRC): WASTE HEAT RECOVERY

The steam Rankine cycle (SRC) is commonly integrated into gas turbine power plants to enhance efficiency through waste heat recovery. The system's overall efficiency is significantly improved by converting waste heat from the gas turbine into additional electrical energy.

Liu et al. [57] introduced a waste heat recovery system (WHRS) for marine engines, converting exhaust and jacket cooling water heat into mechanical energy through integrated steam and organic Rankine cycles. Using jacket cooling water for the steam Rankine cycle prevents added ship weight. Simulations on a 14-cylinder, two-stroke engine showed a 4.42% thermal efficiency gain and annual fuel savings of 9,322 tons at full power. Single steam and dual-pressure organic Rankine cycles improved efficiency by 2.68% and 3.42%, respectively. The study also analyzed evaporation pressure, superheat degree, and engine load impacts, aiding WHRS optimization for marine applications.

Oyedepo [58] reviewed waste heat recovery (WHR) technologies, emphasizing their role in sustainable energy development. They noted that 72% of global primary energy is lost post-conversion, with 63% of waste heat streams below 100 °C, mainly from electricity generation, transportation, and manufacturing. The study highlighted various WHR technologies for different temperature ranges, showcasing their potential to boost energy efficiency, reduce fossil fuel use, and cut greenhouse gas

emissions. It stressed the importance of adopting WHR systems in developing nations to mitigate environmental impacts and advance sustainable energy practices.

Ferreira et al. [59] optimized solar thermal systems for residential buildings in Portugal using a multi-objective approach with the NSGA-II algorithm. Objectives included minimizing annualized investment costs and maximizing solar collection efficiency, with decision variables like solar collection area, linear loss coefficient, and storage tank volume. Pareto analysis revealed a cost-efficiency balance of €270-€280 annually for 60% collection efficiency. The optimal system featured a 4.17 m² solar panel area, 3.684 W/m²·K linear loss coefficient, 0.275 m³ storage volume, and 0.1364 m³/h pump flow rate, costing about €2,545. The study emphasized balancing economic and efficiency factors for sustainable energy solutions.

Akroot et al. [60] evaluated the performance, economics, and environmental benefits of a 50 MW solar Rankine system, emphasizing its potential in regions with abundant sunlight. The system achieved ~40% thermal efficiency, rivaling traditional fossil fuel technologies, using a parabolic trough collector field to heat the Rankine cycle's working fluid for electricity generation. The study highlighted the importance of optimizing solar field size and heat transfer fluid properties to enhance performance. In regions with over 2,000 kWh/m² annual solar radiation, the system demonstrated reliable operation with a levelized cost of electricity (LCOE) ranging from 0.10\$/kWh to 0.15\$/kWh. Incorporating thermal energy storage (TES) improved reliability and profitability, ensuring continuous operation during low solar periods.

Ren et al. [61] proposed a thermodynamic optimization approach for enhancing the efficiency and cost-effectiveness of thermal waste from power plants, considering economic constraints. Multi-objective optimization improved energy recovery and economic viability, boosting energy efficiency by up to 20% while sustaining operational and capital costs.

Wang et al. [62] performed an in-depth investigation of GTCC systems, maximizing thermodynamic performance, economic variables, and environmental costs within an

integrated structure. The study aimed to balance energy efficiency, operation expenses, and environmental impact, focusing on pollutants such as CO₂, NO_x, and SO_x. environmental damage expenses were quantified utilizing advanced optimization approaches. Optimization enhanced thermal efficiency by 2.5%, lowered emissions by 15%, and significantly saved expenses for preserving the environment. The study emphasized the need for control of emissions and optimal configurations of systems.

2.4. ORGANIC RANKINE CYCLE (ORC): LOW-GRADE HEAT RECOVERY

ORC technology is perfect for harnessing low-grade heat sources unsuitable for conventional steam cycles. Employing organic working fluids, ORC systems recover heat from lower-temperature sources such as gas turbine exhaust due to their low vaporization temperatures.

Özkan et al. [63] optimized the steam Rankine cycle (SRC) and organic Rankine cycle (ORC) systems in a gas turbine (GT)-based triple combined cycle, focusing on turbine inlet temperature and pressure. SRC optimization varied pressure between 10–100 bar and temperature from saturated steam up to 480°C. ORC optimization evaluated fluids—acetone, R113, R141b, R152a, R245fa, and R365mfc—at turbine inlet pressures up to their critical pressure and maximum working temperature limits. R141b demonstrated superior performance with a thermal efficiency of 22.6%, exergy efficiency of 64.76%, and a net power output of 780.35 kW at 40 bar and 225 °C. For the GT-SRC-ORC system using R141b, the net thermal and exergy efficiencies reached 47.65% and 67.35%, respectively, enabling recovery of 734.57 kg/h of natural gas and reducing CO₂ emissions by 2203.73 kg/h.

Asim et al. [64] assessed the performance of a novel integrated vapor compression cycle (VCC) and organic Rankine cycle (ORC) system for ultra-low-grade waste heat recovery. The study focused on efficiency, component performance, and system optimization, aiming to enhance sustainability by evaluating thermodynamic performance and selecting optimal working fluids with low global warming

potentials. Advanced simulations assessed different fluids' thermal properties, environmental impact, and system adaptability. The integrated system achieved a 12-15% gain in energy efficiency, leading to quicker processing speeds and reduced operating temperatures. R1234yf and R1233zd(E) were identified as promising fluids because of their low GWP and high thermal stability.

Rana et al. [65] extensively studied and optimized power generation from low-grade waste heat using thermoelectric generators (TEGs). The study targeted improving system efficiency, material selection, and profitability while absorbing industrial waste heat and converting it into usable energy. The results showed that improved TEG systems could achieve up to 8% energy conversion efficiency, making them an attractive choice for low-grade heat recovery. Bismuth telluride (Bi_2Te_3) and related substances have exceptional thermoelectric features, making them perfect options for waste heat conversions.

Feng et al. [66] compared single and mixed working fluids to evaluate the thermal-economic performance of ORCs in waste heat recovery. The study utilized a bi-objective optimization approach to enhance thermal efficiency while minimizing economic costs. The researchers evaluated significant performance indicators such as net power output, thermal efficiency, and LCOE under different operating conditions. Mixed refrigerants, like R245fa/R134a, demonstrated superior performance, increasing thermal efficiency by 5% and decreasing LCOE by 8%. The study revealed that heat transfer qualities and material selection had an important effect on system performance and the effectiveness of costs.

Wang et al. [67] performed an exhaustive multi-objective optimization of ORC systems, such as economic feasibility through cost-benefit evaluation, impact on the environment via greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, and sustainable development through life-cycle assessments. Their study examined the complicated link between thermodynamics and economics in ORC design, evaluating different configurations and working fluids. Advanced modeling techniques were utilized to assess crucial performance factors such as thermal efficiency, LCOE, and greenhouse gas emissions, providing high-resolution findings for precise evaluation. Key studies

demonstrated that ORC systems optimized with eco-friendly refrigerants such as R1233zd(E) and R1234yf produced up to 4.5% higher thermal efficiency and approximately 10% cheaper system costs than conventional designs.

Besevli et al. [68] conducted a technoeconomic analysis of an oxygen-supported combined system for waste heat recovery in an iron-steel facility. The study explored the integration of SRC, ORC, KC, and transcritical CO₂ cycle (t-CO₂) to convert waste heat from an annealing furnace into electricity. The system effectively utilized low-temperature oxygen lines, enhancing condenser performance. With a flue gas temperature of 1093.15 K, the proposed system achieved a thermal efficiency of 19% and a total power output of 596.6 kW. Emission reductions reached 23.16 tons/day, and the minimum electricity generation cost was \$0.1972 per kWh. Parametric studies showed that adjusting the SRC inlet temperature by 221.6 K maximized power generation. The findings highlight the potential of integrating multiple cycles to improve energy efficiency and reduce carbon footprint.

2.5. INTEGRATED SOLAR COMBINED CYCLE (ISCC) BENEFITS

Solar thermal systems alone aren't suitable base-load power plants; integrating them with combined cycle (CC) systems is a better option for reliable electricity generation. Numerous papers directly addressing this topic are available in the literature [69]. Guillén et al.[4] analyzed GHG emissions from parabolic trough CSP plants across their life cycle, aiming to understand the environmental impact, including material production, energy use, and carbon footprint. The study found that although CSP plants are considered low-carbon, GHG emissions remain significant, particularly during the production and installation of solar collectors, thermal storage, and supporting equipment. Emissions varied between 30 and 150 gCO₂ /kWh, depending on plant site, technologies, and construction energy sources. The study proposed mitigation strategies, including low-carbon materials, energy efficiency improvements, and renewable energy in manufacturing, offering the potential for substantial emission reductions. A comprehensive environmental assessment requires considering the entire lifecycle beyond operational emissions.

Bohtz et al.[70] investigated the impact of ISCC systems in increasing renewable energy adoption and generating substantial reductions in carbon dioxide emissions. The research focused on the collaborative dynamics of solar thermal energy and gas turbine combined cycles, focusing on how integrating solar and fossil fuel sources maximizes energy output. ISCC plants that utilize solar heat indicate less reliance on nonrenewable resources, reduce greenhouse gas emissions, and improve operational efficiency. The results showed that ISCC systems achieved 50–60% thermal efficiencies above standard power plants by capitalizing on efficiencies between solar thermal inputs and combined cycle processes. ISCC has been found to minimize CO₂ emissions by 30-40% compared with conventional fossil fuel-based systems, emphasizing its environmental benefits.

Johansson et al. [71] investigated the impact of renewable fuels and electricity in driving economic growth, improving energy security, and preserving the environment. The research highlighted the critical need to transition from fossil fuels to sustainable energy systems, including technical, economic, and policy challenges. Renewable energy sources such as solar, wind, biomass, and hydropower have been determined to be crucial to meeting global energy demands, considerably decreasing greenhouse gas emissions, and minimizing the effects of climate change.

Schwarzbözl et al. [72] evaluated solar gas turbine technologies in-depth, focusing on their sustainability over time, cost, and design. The study emphasizes integrating solar thermal energy with gas turbines to develop efficient, environmentally friendly energy systems. Central receiver systems and heliostat fields concentrate solar energy to preheat gas turbines, decreasing fuel usage and CO₂ emissions. Thermal efficiency varied between 30% and 40%, depending on solar share and system configuration. Hybrid systems that integrate solar energy with traditional fuels have also been studied to ensure steady energy generation during periods of low solar energy. While initial costs for solar gas turbine systems remain high, the study emphasized that technological advances and economies of scale might dramatically cut costs, making these systems equivalent to traditional energy sources.

Dersch et al.[73] examined the integration of PTCs into combined cycle power plants, emphasizing ISCC system performance and economic viability. The study evaluated how solar thermal energy enhances efficiency and minimizes reliance on fossil fuels in traditional power plants. Using comprehensive thermodynamic modeling, the study examined ISCC configurations where solar energy supports steam cycle heat input, minimizing fuel consumption and emissions. Efficiency improvements of 1.2–2.4% points were noted when compared with traditional combined cycle systems, contingent on plant design and solar input. Although ISCC systems demand larger initial investments in solar infrastructure, reducing fuel costs and emissions balance these costs through the plant's lifetime. The study highlighted ISCC systems' favorable LCOE, particularly in sun-rich regions, and the durability and scalability of PTCs.

Alqahtani et al.[74] examined the possibility of utilizing more solar thermal energy in large-scale electricity production with ISCC power plants. The study highlighted the technical and economic advantages of integrating solar thermal systems with CCGTs, like reduced consumption of fossil fuels and greenhouse gas emissions. Simulations showed that ISCC systems may minimize fuel consumption by up to 20% while enhancing plant efficiency by 1-2 percentage points if compared to traditional CCGT systems. The economic analysis discovered that combining solar thermal energy with current gas turbine infrastructure may result in the competitive cost of electricity in high-sunlight areas. ISCC systems maintain a constant power output regardless of solar availability, offering dependable grid operation.

Akroot et al. [75] examined, using the Sarir Power Plant in Libya as a case study, the economic and technical feasibility of combining solar energy with fossil fuel resources in oil-rich areas. Integrating a parabolic trough solar field increased the plant's efficiency from 45% to 52%, decreasing natural gas consumption and increasing thermal efficiency by preheating the HRSG working fluid. The integrated system provided reliable electricity generation by combining solar power during the day with fossil fuels during low-light hours. Fuel consumption dropped up to 20%, with a corresponding LCOE of 0.09–0.13\$/kWh, according to solar integration size and economic factors. Greenhouse gas emissions decreased by 30–40%, supporting

global carbon reduction goals. The study emphasized hybrid systems' potential to enhance energy efficiency, reduce fuel dependence, and lower emissions in oil-producing regions.

Antonanzas et al. [76] evaluated the integration of renewable energy into Algeria's gas power plants, focusing on technical, economic, and environmental impacts. Algeria's huge solar resources and high dependence on natural gas make hybrid systems attractive. By adding PTCs to the CCGT steam cycle, hybrid systems may reduce natural gas usage by 10-15%, leading to fewer CO₂ emissions without losing efficiency. Economically, hybrid plants demonstrated competitive electricity costs due to long-term fuel savings and reduced emissions. Despite challenges like high initial investment and solar energy variability, Algeria's abundant solar potential and supportive renewable energy policies position hybrid systems as a viable pathway to reduce emissions and diversify energy sources.

Temraz et al. [77] conducted experimental and computational studies on ISCC systems to optimize design, enhance efficiency, and reduce emissions. Their analysis focused on the thermodynamic integration of solar thermal energy with CCGT power plants, where solar collectors provide supplementary heat to the steam cycle. Results showed that solar integration increased efficiency by 1.5–3%, depending on solar input and conditions. The study discovered that less fossil fuels resulted in noticeable CO₂ emission reductions. The researchers optimized solar fields, heat exchangers, and component combinations to improve system performance. Despite initial economic challenges, long-term cost reductions and environmental benefits make ISCC systems attractive, with design advice modified to different climates to enhance reliability and performance.

Lovegrove et al. [78] offered an in-depth review of CSP technology, covering its principles, advances, and applications in sustainable energy. The study examined fundamental CSP technologies such as parabolic troughs, solar towers, linear Fresnel reflectors, and dish systems, focusing on design, operation, and performance. High-temperature sunlight harvesting was emphasized to increase power generation efficiency in steam and combined cycle plants. Materials, optics, and thermal storage

developments, such as molten salt storage integration, have been highlighted to increase efficiency and enable energy generation even during periods of low sunlight. Case studies from Australia, North Africa, and the Middle East emphasize CSP's ability to create multiple energy portfolios, minimize dependency on fossil fuels, and enhance grid stability through hybridization with traditional systems.

2.6. PARABOLIC TROUGH COLLECTORS (PTC): SOLAR THERMAL ENERGY

Solar energy's potential for power generation is an important research topic, particularly in places like Iraq where it is plentiful. Solar energy can be transformed into electricity in two ways: photovoltaic (PV) systems and thermodynamic solar cycles. Vergura et al. [79] compared the technical and financial aspects of solar PV and CSP facilities, highlighting operating features, costs, and efficiency. PV systems have been demonstrated to convert sunlight directly into electricity with minimal infrastructure demands, achieving efficiency of 12–20%, depending on the technology. Conversely, CSP systems convert concentrated light into thermal energy for electricity generation, delivering up to 40% thermal efficiency under optimal circumstances.

Gharbi et al. [80] presented a detailed comparison of PTC and linear Fresnel reflector LFR technologies, examining their advantages and disadvantages in design, manufacturing, and maintenance. The study highlighted that PTC systems achieved 75% optical efficiency, outperforming LFR systems, which reached 60–65%. This difference was attributed to PTC's curved mirrors, which concentrated solar radiation more effectively than the flat mirrors of LFR systems. As a result, PTC systems were able to reach outlet temperatures up to 400°C, making them suitable for integration with high-efficiency power cycles. In contrast, LFR systems typically operate at lower temperatures (around 300 °C), offering simpler designs but lower efficiency. Economically, LFR systems had lower land and startup costs due to their compact size and fewer high-precision parts, reducing costs by 20–30% compared to PTC systems. However, PTC systems were preferred for projects requiring higher power generation and efficiency. The study concluded that the choice between PTC and

LFR technology depends on project-specific factors such as budget, land availability, and the desired thermal energy output.

Mills. [81] explored advancements in solar thermal electricity STE, focusing on innovations that enhance efficiency and economic viability, such as higher temperature operations and reduced maintenance costs. The study examined key developments in CSP technologies, including PTC, solar towers, and dish stirring systems. It highlighted improvements in materials science, optical designs, and thermal storage, which have significantly boosted CSP system efficiency. Modern PTC systems reached optical efficiencies of up to 75%, and the integration of thermal storage enabled dispatchable power, ensuring a consistent electricity supply. Solar tower systems, capable of reaching temperatures around 1000 °C, were suitable for integration with high-efficiency Rankine or Brayton cycles. The study also emphasized the 40–50% reduction in the LCOE for large CSP plants since the 1990s, thanks to technological advancements.

Desideri et al. [82] compared CSP and PV power plants, analyzing their technical efficiencies, cost-effectiveness, and environmental impacts. The study assessed large-scale power generation technologies, including energy output per square foot, construction costs, maintenance expenses, and operational lifespan. CSP technologies such as parabolic troughs and solar power towers were evaluated alongside crystalline silicon and thin-film PV. The study found CSP plants, especially those with thermal energy storage, offered improved capacity factors and reliable, on-demand power, benefiting grid stability. Solar tower systems achieved thermal efficiencies of up to 20%, enabling integration with high-efficiency thermal cycles. In contrast, PV plants, with conversion efficiencies of 15–20%, require additional storage or backup to ensure consistent power. Economically, CSP plants had higher upfront costs (4,000–6,000\$/kW), but in areas with high DNI, they achieved competitive LCOE. PV systems were more cost-effective in regions with lower DNI and smaller applications. Both CSP and PV systems significantly reduced greenhouse gas emissions compared to fossil fuel plants, with CSP plants emitting 30–40% less and PV systems having even lower emissions due to their simpler design.

Abed et al. [31] reviewed technologies to enhance the thermal and optical performance of PTCs in CSP systems. They analyzed advancements in reflective surfaces, receiver design, tracking systems, and heat transfer fluids. Key improvements in optical efficiency, such as better mirror materials and coatings, reduced reflectance losses, achieving up to 80% efficiency. Advanced tracking systems, particularly two-axis trackers, improved solar tracking accuracy. Innovations in receiver design and temperature-resistant materials allowed for higher operational temperatures, with some systems reaching outlet temperatures of 400 °C. The use of advanced heat transfer fluids like molten salts and nanofluids further enhanced thermal performance.

Praveen et al. [83] explored how thermal energy storage TES improves the performance of PTC solar thermal power plants. The study focused on mitigating solar power generation inconsistencies by incorporating TES, such as molten salt and phase change materials (PCMs), to enhance thermal efficiency and capacity. The integration of TES allowed PTC systems to store surplus energy for use during non-sunny periods, improving continuous power generation. Using molten salt-based TES boosted the capacity factor by 40%, and the thermal efficiency reached 80%.

Zhang et al. [84] reviewed advancements in solar-thermal nanofluids, emphasizing their enhanced heat transfer capabilities in direct absorption solar collectors. The study addressed the challenge of poor dispersion and aggregation at high temperatures and explored various stabilization techniques, including hydrogen bonding, electrostatic, steric, and self-dispersion methods. The review identified self-dispersible nanofluids as promising for medium-temperature solar-thermal applications and outlined future research opportunities to address existing challenges in nanofluid technologies.

2.7. AMBIENT TEMPERATURE CONTROL HISTORY

Matjanov [85] discussed how ambient conditions impact the gas turbine cycle. For the 28.1 MW Tashkent CHP gas turbine, power output dropped from 28.1 MW to

24.1 MW, and efficiency decreased from 34.2% to 32.0% at 45°C. The study proposed using an absorption chiller to cool the inlet air with heat from gas turbine waste gases, HRSG waste gases, or solar energy. Cooling from 45°C to 15°C requires 4260 kW of heat. Results showed that using gas turbine waste gases is not economical, as CHP efficiency drops from 81.4% to 74.4% at 45°C. Using HRSG waste gases was more feasible, maintaining nominal performance values. Solar energy could be cost-effective with HRSG waste gases below 120°C, requiring 8064 m² of collectors.

Ibrahim et al. [86] reviewed exergy analysis in combined cycle power plants (CCPPs). Ambient temperature increases reduce gas turbine output by ~0.6%/°C, emphasizing thermal management needs. Advanced multi-pressure heat recovery steam generators (HRSGs) enhance efficiency (up to 55%) by minimizing heat transfer irreversibilities. Exergy-driven optimization reveals pathways to cut fuel use and emissions, with hybrid configurations (e.g., solar integration) reducing CO₂ by 30–50% at competitive costs (0.08–0.12\$/kWh). The study highlights exergy analysis as pivotal for improving sustainability, operational efficiency, and cost-effectiveness, particularly in high-temperature environments, aligning CCPPs with global decarbonization goals.

Singh. [87] argued that lower compressor inlet air temperature improves gas turbine and plant performance in Brayton-Rankine combined cycle power plants. These plants typically lose low-grade heat through exhaust gases, which absorption refrigeration systems can utilize effectively. A simulation model was presented for an Indian combined cycle power plant integrated with an ammonia-water absorption refrigeration system powered by exhaust heat, considering India's seasonal conditions. Energy and exergy analysis showed that in summer, net power increased by 9440 kW, boosting thermal efficiency by 1.193% and exergy efficiency by 1.133%. In winter, power output rose by an additional 400 kW. The study also explored performance variation with changes in ammonia condenser temperature due to India's seasonal temperature range, from 45°C in summer to 3°C in winter.

Zare [88] discussed inlet air cooling of the compressor applied to a biomass-fueled closed-cycle gas turbine (CCGT), where the cooling is provided by an ammonia-water absorption cycle powered by exhaust heat. Thermo-economic modeling and multi-objective optimization were conducted for systems with and without inlet cooling, targeting LCOE and exergy efficiency. The results revealed that inlet cooling significantly improves both the thermodynamic and economic performance of the system, even considering the added costs. Under optimal conditions, inlet cooling increased net power by 30.1% and exergy efficiency while decreasing LCOE by 22.5%.

Ameri and Hejazi [89] addressed the optimization of operational efficiency and power generation capacity at the Chabahar gas turbine facility by integrating an absorption chiller. The research centered on repurposing waste heat from the turbine's exhaust to operate the chiller, which subsequently cooled the compressor's inlet air. This cooling mechanism increased air density at the compressor inlet, enhancing mass flow rates and enabling higher power output without additional fuel consumption. Key findings revealed a 15-20% surge in the turbine's power capacity post-retrofit, attributed to improved compressor efficiency under cooler inlet conditions. Reducing inlet air temperatures from 35°C to 20°C amplified air density, directly correlating with elevated turbine performance.

Alhazmy et al. [90] investigated strategies to optimize gas turbine efficiency through the implementation of intake air cooling systems. Their work emphasized mitigating the adverse effects of elevated ambient temperatures on turbine performance, particularly in hot climates where reduced air density diminishes output. By cooling intake air, the study aimed to increase power generation and operational efficiency through enhanced air density and mass flow rates. Experimental analysis demonstrated that air-cooled turbines achieved power output enhancements of 15-20% compared to uncooled systems. Lowering intake temperatures from 35°C to 15°C significantly increased air density, enabling higher combustion efficiency and fuel utilization without additional fuel demand.

Barakat et al. [91] explored the synergistic potential of combining an Earth Air Heat Exchanger (EAHE) and a fogging-based cooling system to address gas turbine efficiency losses in high-temperature environments. The study focused on mitigating the adverse effects of reduced air density in hot climates by introducing a hybrid cooling mechanism. The EAHE leveraged subsurface thermal stability to precondition intake air, while the fogging system supplemented cooling by atomizing water droplets during peak ambient temperatures. Results indicated that this dual approach significantly enhanced turbine performance. Cooling intake air from 35°C to 15°C amplified air density, enabling a 30% surge in power output without increasing fuel consumption. The EAHE provided consistent baseline cooling, particularly during warmer months, whereas fogging delivered additional temperature reduction during extreme heat, ensuring stable operation. Thermodynamic efficiency improved from 32% to 40%, driven by reduced compressor workload and optimized combustion conditions. Economically, the integrated system demonstrated long-term viability despite initial infrastructure costs. Enhanced power generation and fuel savings reduced the LCOE, accelerating return on investment. Its stable operation in the face of altering environmental circumstances contributes to its suitability for environments with high temperatures.

Lucia et al. [92] examined how compressor intake air cooling influenced gas turbine efficiency and cogeneration systems' economic viability and found significant operational and economic benefits. The study aimed at overcoming efficiency restrictions caused by high ambient temperatures, which reduce air density and hamper turbine power. By precooling intake air to enhance density, the system aimed to augment power generation and optimize fuel utilization. Findings demonstrated that cooling air intake from 35°C to 10°C increased air density, elevating mass flow rates and enabling a 20% boost in power output without additional fuel consumption. This improvement was particularly pronounced in hot climates, where thermal inefficiencies typically degrade turbine performance.

Espinosa et al. [93] proposed a novel turbine inlet air cooling (TIAC) technique for combined cycle power plants (CCPPs), leveraging waste heat from exhaust gases to drive an ejector refrigeration cycle ERC for enhanced performance. By cooling

compressor inlet air, the method increases air density and mass flow, boosting gas turbine output by 6.26% without additional fuel consumption. Thermodynamic modeling reveals improved energy efficiency up to 55% and reduced environmental emissions (30–50% CO₂ reduction) through waste heat recovery.

2.8. INTEGRATED SOLAR COMBINED CYCLE ISCC WITH HYBRID SYSTEMS

Javadi et al. [94] comprehensively analyzed energy, exergy, economic, and environmental outcomes for three hybrid CCPP configurations incorporating solar power tower technology. The research explored the feasibility and benefits of integrating solar thermal energy with conventional fossil fuel-based systems, comparing designs that synergize solar towers with gas and steam turbine arrangements. Results indicated that solar integration markedly enhanced system performance. Energy efficiency rose by 5–10%, while exergy efficiency improved by 3–8%, reflecting optimized energy quality and reduced thermodynamic losses. These gains were attributed to the strategic use of solar heat to supplement fossil fuel inputs, thereby lowering fuel dependency and enhancing process efficiency. Economically, hybrid configurations reduced the LCOE by 5–15% compared to traditional CCPPs, driven by lower fuel consumption and operational expenses. Although high upfront costs for solar tower infrastructure posed initial financial barriers, the study emphasized that advancing technology and economies of scale could improve long-term viability. Environmentally, solar integration reduced CO₂ emissions by 20–40%, with additional declines in NO_x and SO_x pollutants, aligning the systems with global decarbonization goals.

Pantaleo et al. [23] assessed the feasibility of integrating CSP, biomass energy, and TES into a BC/ORC plant for the Mediterranean regions. The study aimed to determine the technical and economic viability of this hybrid renewable system for sustainable energy generation. The proposed design combined solar energy as the primary source with biomass as a supplementary fuel, supported by TES to ensure uninterrupted operation. Results indicated that merging solar and biomass resources with BC/ORC cycles enhanced annual energy efficiency to 25–35%, contingent on

regional conditions and system design. Continuous operation was achieved through daytime solar utilization and biomass backup during low-insolation periods, with TES bridging energy gaps. Economically, the hybrid system reduced the LCOE by 10–15% compared to fossil fuel-based plants, driven by lower fuel consumption and consistent output. While high upfront costs for CSP and TES components posed initial financial challenges, the study projected improved competitiveness as renewable technologies mature and costs decline. Environmental assessments highlighted CO₂ emission reductions of 30–50%, bolstered by the use of sustainably sourced biomass (carbon-neutral) and reduced reliance on fossil fuels. The integration of solar energy further minimized biomass consumption, amplifying emission savings.

Akroot et al. [95] evaluated the viability of integrating a solar combined cycle system (SCCS) with fossil fuel backup and rock bed TES to optimize energy sustainability in solar-rich regions like Neom City. The hybrid system aimed to maximize efficiency, reduce fossil fuel dependency, and align with decarbonization objectives. Technical assessments revealed that solar integration elevated energy efficiency to 55%, outperforming conventional systems (45%) by leveraging concentrated solar energy during peak hours. The rock bed TES stored excess solar heat, enabling continuous power generation during low-insolation periods, while fossil fuels provided stability during prolonged solar deficits. This synergy ensured grid reliability without compromising efficiency gains. Economically, the system achieved LCOE (0.08–0.12\$/kWh) due to a 20% annual reduction in operational costs from minimized fossil fuel use. Despite high upfront investments in solar and TES infrastructure, long-term savings from emission reductions and fuel offsets improved financial viability. Environmentally, CO₂ emissions decreased by 30–50% compared to traditional plants, as solar energy directly displaced fossil fuel consumption. This alignment with Neom City's sustainability targets highlights the model's potential to balance energy security with low-carbon development.

Meana et al. [96] analyzed innovations in power generation cycles to improve sustainability and lower environmental footprints. The research examined modernized systems integrating renewables, carbon capture CCS, and efficiency

upgrades to meet rising global energy demand. Key findings revealed a transition from traditional Rankine/Brayton cycles to advanced configurations like combined cycles, ISCCs, and hybrid renewable-fossil plants. These systems achieve thermal efficiencies exceeding 60%, surpassing conventional plants (35–40%). Hybrid designs incorporating solar technologies (e.g., parabolic troughs) reduce fossil fuel reliance while maintaining grid stability. Economically, advanced cycles exhibit competitive levelized costs (0.08–0.12\$/kWh) due to long-term fuel savings and regulatory incentives, offsetting higher initial investments in renewables or CCS. Environmentally, CCS-enabled systems cut CO₂ emissions by >90%, while hybrid renewables lower emissions by 30–50%. Enhanced water efficiency and reduced land use further align these systems with global sustainability targets.

Alaa et al. [97] conducted an exergo-economic and parametric analysis of waste heat recovery at Iraq's Taji Gas Turbines Power Plant by integrating a BC with SRC and ORG Cycles to enhance electricity generation and reduce emissions. The combined system achieves 44.37% energy efficiency and 42.84% exergy efficiency, producing 258.2 MW of power, significantly outperforming the standalone BC (167.3 MW). The combustion chamber accounts for 57.3% of total exergy destruction due to irreversible combustion, while the gas turbine exhibits the highest exergy efficiency (94.2%). Exergo-economic analysis reveals 63% of costs stem from exergy destruction, outweighing capital investments (37%), with electricity costs at 9.03\$/MWh for the combined system. Parametric studies show increasing gas turbine inlet temperature GTIT improves efficiency up to 45.29% but raises costs beyond optimal thresholds, while pressure ratio and compressor efficiency enhancements initially boost performance before diminishing returns. Using R123 in the ORC balances environmental with technical efficiency.

Aghaziarati et al. [98] proposed a solar-driven combined cooling, heating, and power CCHP system integrating ORC and cascade refrigeration to meet the multi-level energy demands of a hospital in Iran. The system achieves 89.39% energy efficiency and 8.70% exergy efficiency, with the solar collector as the main source of inefficiency. Cyclohexane optimizes thermodynamic performance, while octane reduces total costs by 0.7% exergoeconomically. PTCs outperform alternatives,

requiring 13% less area than parabolic dishes and lowering costs. Increasing solar irradiation reduces solar field area and costs but marginally lowers efficiencies, whereas higher ambient temperatures improve thermal efficiency 1.02% for PTCs but reduce exergy efficiency 1.65%. Designed with optimized shell-and-tube heat exchangers up to 1544 kW/m²K, the system shows viability for solar-rich regions, balancing efficiency, cost, and sustainability for healthcare infrastructure.

Alfaris et al. [99] investigated the performance of a hybrid energy system integrating ORCs with gas and steam turbines, utilizing natural gas NG as a fossil fuel and solar PTCs as renewable energy sources. Conducted in Kirkuk, Iraq has a region with high solar radiation. The research aims to address the inefficiencies and environmental challenges associated with fossil fuels and renewable energy variability. The hybrid system achieves a thermal efficiency of 59.32% and an exergy efficiency of 57.28%, demonstrating significant improvements in energy conversion. An exergoeconomic analysis identifies the optimal energy cost at 71.93\$/MWh with a compressor pressure ratio of 8 bar. Additionally, the system reduces environmental impact, with a carbon footprint of 316.3 kg CO₂/MWh at higher compressor pressure ratios. The findings highlight the potential of integrating solar energy with natural gas to enhance electricity generation in a cost-effective and environmentally sustainable manner.

2.9. THERMAL ENERGY STORAGE (TES): ENHANCING RELIABILITY

Thermal Energy Storage (TES) systems are essential to counterbalance the inconsistent nature of solar power and ensure a reliable energy source. During sunny times, TES systems store extra heat, providing power when needed. Aber et al. [100] investigated the role of nanoparticle additives in optimizing molten salt formulations for concentrated solar thermal storage systems. The study focused on identifying optimal composite materials by evaluating nanoparticle dispersion techniques and their influence on thermophysical properties such as heat capacity and thermal conductivity.

Ding et al. [101] emphasized the critical role of TES in addressing global energy sustainability and environmental challenges. The study analyzed the evolution of TES technologies—sensible, latent, and thermochemical systems—from 2000 to 2019. While conventional sensible heat methods dominated early research, bibliometric trends indicate a shift toward advanced and hybrid TES solutions due to their superior storage capacity, efficiency gains, and adaptability.

Khandelwal et al. [102] evaluated the hybridization of a linear frequency solar array and a phase-change thermal storage cascade with a 328.1 MW combined cycle facility in North India to form an ISCC. The system's performance was assessed using water and molten salt as heat transfer fluids under dynamic operating conditions. Results demonstrated that molten salt achieved 50.87% system efficiency, outperforming water-based configurations by 1.51% due to superior thermal retention. Enhanced fuel economy and reduced emissions were observed with molten salt, though economic viability was excluded from analysis owing to volatile natural gas pricing.

CHAPTER 3

WORK DESCRIPTION AND METHODOLOGY

3.1. INTRODUCTION

This thesis presents a novel hybrid solar–natural gas system that integrates a gas turbine unit (K1), solar PTC, Rankine cycle RC, TES, ARS, and ORC to form a poly-generation system for power production. A comprehensive 4E analysis—covering energy, exergy, environmental, and exergoeconomic aspects—has been performed to assess and understand the proposed system’s performance thoroughly. The results obtained in the literature showed the feasibility of achieving the maximum thermal efficiency with low investment costs. The last two decades saw increased advanced gas turbine production due to environmental and economic factors, especially in hot areas. adding an Absorption refrigeration cycle ARS to the air inlet temperature of the compressor to maximize the system efficiency specially in the summer because Iraq is within the hottest climate in the world. Three models of gas turbine configurations exist in KIRKUK Gas Power Station K1, K2, and K3 in this work, K1 will be modeled and thermodynamically investigated in three models. The first model is a gas turbine configuration as shown in figure 3.2 which is called (model 1). The second model is a Solar Field SF, and Thermal Energy Storage TES that have been added to the system to form Model 2 as shown in Figure 3.3. Finally, adding to the system the ARS system to form Model 3 as shown in Figure 3.4.

In the Arabian Peninsula's northern half, Iraq's coordinates are 30°30'40"N and 38°47'35"E. The country is divided into seventeen formally defined regions. Engineers, operators, and designers involved in power plant development and optimization will find this study's findings insightful and practical.

3.2. INTEGRATED SYSTEM AND ANALYSIS ASSUMPTIONS

The proposed systems in this study were evaluated, analyzed, and modeled with the Engineering Equation Solver (EES) program. This software computes key thermodynamic properties—pressure, temperature, entropy, and exergy—important for designing and analyzing system performance. The modeling process is simplified and streamlined by using these assumptions in the design and analysis. Assumptions and performance assessments for the standalone subsystems are similar to the ones in [103][10] for the Gas Turbine Combined Cycle,[104],[105] for the Parabolic Trough Collectors, and [106],[10] for the Absorption Cooling Unit.

- The system operates under steady-state conditions.
- The effects of friction, heat losses, and pressure drops caused by the layout of tubes and heat exchangers are considered negligible.
- Air is treated as an ideal gas for thermodynamic calculations.
- For simplification, natural gas is assumed to consist entirely of methane.
- Variations in potential and kinetic energy across system components are disregarded due to their minimal impact.
- Pumps, turbines, and compressors are modeled as adiabatic components, simulating their behavior without heat transfer.
- Heat loss to the surroundings is not accounted for in calculations.
- The ARS operates under continuous, steady-state conditions without transient fluctuations. And working fluid is an ideal fluid with negligible pressure drops.
- Working fluid is assumed to mix perfectly, ensuring uniform temperature and concentration.
- For ORG cycle, heat exchanger is assumed to be perfectly insulated, with no energy loss. And working fluid is subjected to an isentropic expansion and compression process in the cycle.

These assumptions allow for a focused evaluation of the system's core thermodynamic performance while minimizing computational complexity.

3.3. SYSTEMS DESCRIPTION

The layout of the Kirkuk Gas Power Plant combined with suggested steam and organic Rankin cycles provides a detailed view of this unique case study set within the specific energy landscape of Iraq. This power plant includes three types of gas turbines, labeled K1, K2, and K3, which are The 265 MW Siemens V94.3A, 65 MW Siemens SGT-1000F and 283 MW Siemens SGT5-4000F respectively [107]. Notably, this study focuses exclusively on the K1 with an actual electrical capacity of 150 MW that has been taken in the simulation, making it a substantial contributor to the plant's energy output and an ideal subject for investigating performance improvements and integration with advanced thermal systems.

Brayton Cycle (BC), which is the base working cycle on site that responsible for energy conversion, as illustrated in Figure 3.1. This cycle begins with the air compressor (AC) compressing the ambient air to higher pressures, significantly increasing its temperature. This pressurized air is then directed into the combustion chamber (CC), which is mixed with fuel gas and ignited. The combustion process releases high-temperature gases, which expand rapidly and are directed through the gas turbine (GT), producing mechanical energy that drives the turbine and ultimately generates electricity. Combustion gas turbine flow shows fuel burning, needing efficiency and improvement in emissions.

Figure 3.1. Gas turbine schematic diagram

Figure 3.2. shows Model 1, a BC-integrated system with advanced SRC and ORC subsystems. These subsystems work harmoniously to capture and use waste heat that would otherwise be lost. This integrated system boosts power generation by capturing the thermal energy from the Brayton Cycle's hot exhaust gases. This integration critically depends on the SRC, which works with the HRSG. The gas turbine's exhaust heat is recovered by the HRSG and transformed into steam to drive the RC, thus boosting electricity generation. Incorporating an ORC makes this system more flexible and efficient. ORCs effectively convert low-grade waste heat into usable power through organic working fluids with low boiling points. Power generation remains possible even with lower temperatures and the inefficiency of conventional steam cycles.

Figure 3.2. Schematic Representation of a Gas Turbine Integrated with Rankine Cycles in Model 1

Figure 3.3. shows Solar Field SF and TES added to form Model 2. The Solar Field SF lowers fuel consumption and the plant's carbon footprint by supplying renewable thermal energy. Furthermore, the Thermal Energy Storage unit saves excess heat to ensure a stable energy supply and a more efficient cycle. This integrated system

boosts Kirkuk Gas Power Plant's thermal efficiency while also lowering fuel use and greenhouse gas emissions. Additionally, this setup provides a template for comparable facilities in areas with ample sunlight and heat, demonstrating that hybrid systems can produce cleaner energy more efficiently. Model 2 at Kirkuk exemplifies the transformative effect of integrating advanced thermodynamic cycles and renewable energy into conventional power generation, paving the path for future sustainable energy advancements.

Figure 3.3. Integration of (SF)and (TES) to the system forming Model 2.

Figure 3.4. illustrates the integration of gas turbine power plant IGTPP, which is economically and environmentally enhanced by incorporating an ARS. Cooling the intake air of the compressor using the ARS improves gas turbine efficiency by increasing air density, achieving higher pressure ratios (PR), and enhancing the overall performance of the Brayton cycle. This optimization of the HRSG increases steam generation for the Rankine cycle, while the ARS enhances energy recovery and reduces thermal pollution by utilizing waste heat from the gas turbine exhaust, thereby promoting sustainability. The system is expected to achieve substantial cost savings through reduced fuel consumption and lower operating expenses. By leveraging waste heat, absorption refrigeration provides more cost-effective cooling

compared to traditional mechanical chillers, decreasing dependence on the power grid. Additionally, the ARS mitigates thermal stress on components, extending their lifespan and reducing maintenance costs. Environmentally, this integration reduces CO₂ emissions by improving efficiency and incorporating renewable solar power within the ISCC configuration. The system's adaptability is particularly beneficial in hot climates, ensuring consistent power output under varying conditions

Figure 3.4. Integration of the (ARS)system to the IGTPP forming model 3.

ARS and ISCC work together to handle peak energy demand better and improve energy efficiency by enhancing the performance of low-temperature cycles like the ORC. Academically and professionally, this integration demands advanced expertise in thermodynamics, exergy analysis, and energy system optimization. It's consistent with worldwide energy policies to reduce carbon emissions and enhance efficiency.

3.4. MODELING

Kirkuk Gas Power Plant greatly contributes to the energy supply of Kirkuk, Iraq, as seen in Figure 5. The plant's strategic placement near 35.4689° N, 44.3922° E enables efficient power delivery to Kirkuk and its surroundings, as the map shows. The plant's location near key infrastructure strengthens its importance for regional energy security and creates partnership opportunities in the energy sector.

Figure 3.5. KIRKUK gas power station location[108].

This study focuses on the K1 unit of 150 MW actual power in Kirkuk Gas Power Plant, a scientifically justified choice for a representative and controlled analysis. The K1 of V94.3A turbine is a documented industry standard, offering a reliable performance, efficiency, and maintenance model. Focusing solely on K1, this study reduces variability from multiple units, allowing for in-depth analysis of thermal efficiency, fuel consumption, and emissions specific to that turbine. Furthermore, K1's primary designation likely provides better access to complete technical and operational data (e.g., temperature, pressure, maintenance records), thus increasing result accuracy. This focused method creates a detailed performance benchmark, enabling later comparisons with other units to analyze technological differences.

Moreover, examining a single unit simplifies computational modeling, facilitating efficient analysis and optimization studies. Focusing solely on K1 also allows the study to yield precise data on the economic and environmental impacts, such as fuel efficiency and emissions, thus informing targeted upgrades that could offer significant returns on investment. This approach, therefore, ensures a comprehensive and practical baseline, setting the foundation for future assessments of other units within the plant.

Table 3.1. Input values utilized for the design of Model 3[37],[109] outlines the key characteristics and simulation settings utilized. It provides a comprehensive overview of the conditions and assumptions to evaluate the system's performance. These parameters are essential for ensuring that the simulation accurately represents real-world operating conditions, thereby enhancing the reliability of the results.

Table 3.1. Input values utilized for the design of Model 3[37],[109].

	Parameter	Value
GT cycle	Compression ratio	9.3
	Air mass flow rate, (kg/s)	438
	GTIT, (K)	1360
	Ambient temperature, (K)	306
	LHV of fuel, (kJ/kg)	50056
	η_{AC} , (%)	80
	η_{GT} , (%)	90
	RH	0.63
RC cycle	HPST inlet pressure, (bar)	100
	IPST inlet pressure, (bar)	40
	LPST inlet pressure, (bar)	10
	Condenser Temperature, (K)	313
	η_{ST} , (%)	90
	η_{Pump} , (%)	85
ORG RC	ORT inlet pressure, (bar)	8
	Condenser Temperature (K)	305.7
	η_{ORT} , (%)	90
	η_{Pump} , (%)	80
	Working Fluid	R123
Solar field& TES system	HTF outlet temperature (K)	840
	HTF inlet temperature (K)	560
	Working fluid	Molten Salt(60%NaNo3-40%KNo3)
	TES Pressure system (bar)	1.5

	Area of collectors(m ²)	400000
	DNI	8.0
ARS	Generator temperature (K)	361
	Condenser temperature (K)	312
	Absorber outlet temperature (K)	321
	SHE effectiveness (%)	53
	Evaporator temperature (K)	278
	Evaporator inlet air temperature (K)	323
	Evaporator outlet air temperature (K)	283
	Cond $T_{w_{in}}$ (K)	298
	Cond $T_{w_{out}}$ temperature (K)	308
	Absorber $T_{absorber,in}$ (K)	298
Absorber $T_{absorber,out}$ (K)	308	
LiBr Solution	Solution strength (%)	53
Coordinates	Lat. position (deg.)	35.47° N
	Long. position (deg.)	44.39° E
	Location	Kirkuk/ Iraq

3.5. THERMODYNAMIC ANALYSIS

To understand power transformation in power stations, especially ISCC systems, you need a strong understanding of the first law of thermodynamics. The foundational principle establishes energy's inability to be created or destroyed, only converted or transferred, thereby forming the bedrock of energy systems analysis and optimization. Applying this law gives a comprehensive understanding of ISCC energy flows, thus improving performance and efficiency.

Based on the first law of thermodynamics, improving the power plants of ISCC generators by integrating solar energy and absorption refrigeration cycles is the focus of this study. Efficient cooling cuts waste energy and increases power generation with this integration, improving the power station's overall thermal efficiency. The first law enables a thorough analysis of heat transfer, energy generation, and power use within the system, directing energy conversion and distribution among its parts.

Energy conservation principles are applied in this study to evaluate the energy balance across all key ISCC system components. The system's components are gas turbines, HRSGs, steam turbines, solar fields, TES units, and ARS. Performance

optimization and inefficiency identification are achieved through rigorous energy and mass balance analysis within each component's defined control volume.

Improving ISCC system performance critically depends on applying the first law of thermodynamics. This study uses mass and energy balance analysis to optimize energy conversion, cut inefficiencies, and increase power station production. This structured method improves ISCC systems' dependability and longevity while providing a model for incorporating renewable energy technology into existing power grids [110].

3.5.1. Energy Analysis of the Integration System

The fundamental concepts of continuity and the first law of thermodynamics are summarized below[111].

$$\sum_{in} \dot{m} = \sum_{out} \dot{m} \quad (3.1)$$

The following equation allows to model energy interactions in steady-state processes. It ensures a comprehensive energy analysis and highlights efficiency and losses in the system[112]:

$$\dot{Q}_{in} + \dot{W}_{in} + \sum_{in} \dot{m}(h_{in}) = \dot{Q}_{out} + \dot{W}_{out} + \sum_{out} \dot{m}(h_{out}) \quad (3.2)$$

Where: “ \dot{W} ”, refers to the work produced, “ \dot{m} ”, refers to the mass flow rate, “ \dot{Q} ”, refers to the heat input, “ h ”, refers to the enthalpy. The letters 'in' and 'out' in the subscript denote the inlet and output states.

The energy balance equations for the Brayton Cycle (BC) components are shown below.

3.5.1.1 Energy Analysis of Brayton Cycle Components

Air Compressor

The compressor requires mechanical energy to compress the incoming air, which increases its temperature and pressure, preparing it for combustion. The energy balance of compressor can be calculated by the following equation[113]:

$$\dot{W}_{AC} = \dot{m}_{air}(h_{23} - h_{22}) \quad (3.3)$$

Where: “ \dot{W}_{AC} ”, refers to the work consumed by the air compressor (MW), and “ \dot{m}_{air} ”, refers to the mass flow rate of air entering the compressor (kg/s).

Combustion Chamber (CC)

The energy balance in the combustion chamber can be calculated by the following equation:

$$\dot{m}_{air}h_{23} + \dot{m}_{fuel} LHV = (\dot{m}_{fuel} + \dot{m}_{air})h_{25} \quad (3.4)$$

Where: “ \dot{m}_{fuel} ”, refers to the rate of flow mass for fossil fuel (kg/s), and “LHV”, Lower Heating Value of the fuel (kJ/kg).

Gas Turbine (GT)

The energy balance in the gas turbine can be obtained from the following[114]:

$$\dot{W}_{GT} = \dot{m}_{25}(h_{25} - h_{26}) \quad (3.5)$$

Where: “ \dot{W}_{GT} ”, refers to the work done rate through the turbine (MW).

This work is used to power the generator and produce electricity. Net Power is the difference between the turbine's output and the compressor's work requirement.

$$\dot{W}_{BC} = \dot{W}_{GT} - \dot{W}_{AC} \quad (3.6)$$

Where: “ \dot{W}_{BC} ”, work done rate through the Bryton cycle (MW).

3.5.1.2. Energy Analysis of Steam Rankine Cycle Components

Heat Recovery Steam Generation

Exhaust gases that generating steam through the HRSG can be calculated from the following equation

$$\dot{Q}_{HRSG} = \dot{m}_{25}(h_{26} - h_{27}) + \dot{m}_{19}(h_{19} - h_{20}) = \dot{m}_{14}(h_1 - h_{14}) \quad (3.7)$$

Where, “ \dot{Q}_{HRSG} ”, refers to the heat rate is engaged by the HRSG (MJ/s), “ \dot{m}_{14} ”, refers to the rate of flow mass for steam exiting the HRSG (kg/s), and “ \dot{m}_{25} ”, refers to the rate of flow mass for exhaust gases exiting the GT (kg/s).

Steam Turbines

The following equations can determine the energy balance for steam turbines in the high, intermediate, and low-pressure stages.

$$\dot{W}_{HPST} = \dot{m}_1(h_1 - h_2) \quad (3.8)$$

$$\dot{W}_{IPST} = \dot{m}_3(h_3 - h_5) \quad (3.9)$$

$$\dot{W}_{LPST} = \dot{m}_6(h_6 - h_8) \quad (3.10)$$

Where, " \dot{W}_{HPST} ", refers to the work rate generated by the HPST (MW), " \dot{W}_{IPST} ", refers to the work rate generated by the IPST (MW), and " \dot{W}_{LPST} " refers to the work rate generated by the LPST (MW).

Condenser₁

The heat extracted from the hot steam, which condenses into liquid water and transfers thermal energy to the cooling water through the condenser, can be precisely calculated using the energy balance expressed in the following equation.[115]:

$$\dot{Q}_{Cond1} = \dot{m}_8(h_8 - h_9) \quad (3.11)$$

Where, " \dot{Q}_{Cond1} " refers to the heat rate, which is transferred from the condenser (MJ/s).

Pumps

The energy balance equations for pump 1,2 and pump 3 are represented by the following equation:

$$\dot{W}_{P1} = \dot{m}_9(h_{10} - h_9) \quad (3.12)$$

$$\dot{W}_{P2} = \dot{m}_{11}(h_{12} - h_{11}) \quad (3.13)$$

$$\dot{W}_{P3} = \dot{m}_{13}(h_{14} - h_{13}) \quad (3.14)$$

Where, " \dot{W}_{P1} ", refers to the work rate is consumed by pump 1 (kW), " \dot{W}_{P2} ", refers to the work rate is consumed by pump 2 (kW), and " \dot{W}_{P3} ", refers to the work rate is consumed by pump 3 (kW).

Open Feed Water Heaters (OFWH)

To quantify the heat, transfer and mass flow interactions within the OFWHs, the following equations can be expressed as:

$$\dot{Q}_{\text{OFWH1}} = (\dot{m}_{10}h_{10} + \dot{m}_7h_7) = (\dot{m}_{11}h_{11}) \quad (3.15)$$

$$\dot{Q}_{\text{OFWH2}} = (\dot{m}_{12}h_{12} + \dot{m}_4h_4) = (\dot{m}_{13}h_{13}) \quad (3.16)$$

Where: “ \dot{Q}_{OFWH1} ”, refers to the heat rate, which transfers in the OFWH₁ (MW), and “ \dot{Q}_{OFWH2} ”, refers to the heat rate, which transfers in the OFWH₂ (MW).

3.5.1.3. Energy Analysis of Organic Rankine Cycle Components

Organic Rankine Turbine (ORT)

The power output of the Organic Rankine Turbine (ORT) during the expansion process, can be determined from the following equation:

$$\dot{W}_{\text{ORT}} = \dot{m}_{29}(h_{29} - h_{30}) \quad (3.17)$$

Where “ \dot{W}_{ORT} ”, refers to the work output from the ORC turbine, and “ \dot{m}_{30} ”, mass flow rate of the working fluid in the ORC cycle.

Organic Rankine Pump (ORP)

The work required for the organic pump can be calculated by using the following equation:

$$\dot{W}_{\text{ORP}} = \dot{m}_{32}(h_{33} - h_{32}) \quad (3.18)$$

Where “ \dot{W}_{ORP} ” represents the work required by the ORC pump.

Condenser₂

The energy balance of the condenser₂ can be applied by using the following equation:

$$\dot{Q}_{\text{Cond}2} = \dot{m}_{31}(h_{31} - h_{32}) \quad (3.19)$$

Where “ $\dot{Q}_{\text{Cond}2}$ ” refers to the heat rejected by the ORC condenser.

Evaporator₁

The energy balance of the evaporator₁ can be represented by using the following equation:

$$\dot{Q}_{\text{Evap}1} = \dot{m}_{27}(h_{27} - h_{28}) \quad (3.20)$$

Where “ $\dot{Q}_{\text{Evap}1}$ ” represents the heat absorbed by the evaporator₁.

Heat Exchanger (HE)

The heat transferred to the working fluid as it flows in the heat exchanger can be determined from the following equation:

$$\dot{Q}_{\text{HE}} = \dot{m}_{30}(h_{30} - h_{31}) \quad (3.21)$$

Where “ \dot{Q}_{HE} ” represents the heat transfer rate through the heat exchanger.

3.5.1.4. Energy Analysis of Solar Field Components

Solar Energy Collection

Thermal energy received by the collector is calculated as follows[116].

$$\dot{Q}_{solar} = \eta_{PTC} * A_a * DNI \quad (3.22)$$

Where, “ \dot{Q}_{solar} ”, represents to the thermal energy for PTC, “ A_a ”, refers to the solar areas, “DNI”, refers to the direct normal irradiance, and “ η_{PTC} ”, demonstrates the PTC's efficiency.

The average of maximum DNI according to the location of the Kirkuk gas power plant is taken from Figure 3.6.[117].

Figure 3.6. The annual DNI at the study location.

To determine the usable solar energy and quantify heat losses within the solar system, the following equations can be used .[118][119]:

$$\dot{Q}_u = n_{cp} n_{cs} F_R [S A_a - A_r U_L (T_{ri} - T_{amb})] \quad (3.23)$$

Where, “ \dot{Q}_u “, refers to the useful heat gain (kW or kJ/s),” n_{cp} ”, demonstrates the overall performance efficiency of the collector under given conditions,” n_{cs} ”, refers to the fraction of the collector area exposed to direct sunlight,” F_R ” illustrates the collector heat removal factor,” S ”, refers to the absorbed Solar Energy (kW/m² or kJ/m²·s),” A_a ”, refers to the aperture area of the solar collector (m²),” A_r ”, refers to the reflective loss factor,” U_L ” illustrates the overall heat loss coefficient (kW/m²·K),” T_{ri} ” refers to the inlet temperature of the working fluid, and ” T_{amb} ” illustrates the

ambient temperature. the collector heat removal factor (F_R) is calculated by the following equation:

$$F_R = \frac{\dot{m}_c C_{p,c}}{A_r U_L} \left[1 - \exp\left(-\frac{U_L F' A_r}{\dot{m}_c C_{p,c}}\right) \right] \quad (3.24)$$

Where, “ \dot{m}_c ”, refers to the mass flow rate of the working fluid (kg/s), “ $C_{p,c}$ ”, represents the specific heat capacity of the working fluid (kJ/kg·K), and “ F' ” refers to the collector efficiency factor.

The absorbed solar radiation amount can be calculated from:

$$S = DNI \cdot q_{PTC} \cdot \gamma \cdot \tau \cdot \alpha \cdot K \quad (3.25)$$

Where: “ DNI ” refers to the direct normal irradiance (kW/m²), “ q_{PTC} ”, demonstrates the concentration ratio of the PTC, “ γ ”, refers to the tracking efficiency, “ τ ”, represents the transmittance of the glass cover, “ α ” refers to the absorptance of the absorber Tube, and “ K ”, represents the incident angle modifier.

The collector's heat loss coefficient can be determined from the following:

$$U_L = \left(\frac{A_R}{(h_w + h_{rc}) \cdot A_G} + \frac{1}{h_{rr}} \right)^{-1} \quad (3.26)$$

Where: “ h_w ” refers to the wind convective heat transfer coefficient (kW/m²·K), “ h_{rc} ” represents the convective heat transfer coefficient between the absorber plate and glass cover (kW/m²·K), “ A_G ”, refers to the effective glass cover area (m²), “ h_{rr} ” represents the radiative heat transfer coefficient between the absorber plate and glass cover (kW/m²·K).

Thermal Energy Storage (TES)

The heat loss from the thermal energy storage can be determined from the following equation[120]:

$$\dot{Q}_{TST} = (\dot{m}_{17}h_{17} + \dot{m}_{21}h_{21}) = (\dot{m}_{19}h_{19} - \dot{m}_{18}h_{18}) \quad (3.27)$$

Where “ \dot{Q}_{TST} ” represents the change in thermal energy stored within the tank.

3.5.1.5. Energy Analysis of Absorption Refrigeration System Components

Generator

The heat transferred from the generator in the system can be calculated from the following equation:

$$\dot{Q}_{Gen} = \dot{m}_{28}(h_{28} - h_{37}) \quad (3.28)$$

Where: “ \dot{Q}_{Gen} ” refers to the heat transfer rate through the generator, and “ \dot{m}_{28} ” represents the mass flow rate of the LiBr-H₂O mixture.

Condenser₃

The heat transfer within the condenser in the ARS system can be calculated from the following equation:

$$\dot{Q}_{Cond3} = \dot{m}_{7*}(h_{8*} - h_{7*}) \quad (3.29)$$

Where, “ \dot{Q}_{Cond3} ” refers to the heat transfer rate through the condenser₃.

Expansion Valves

The energy balance for the expansion valves in the ARS system can be calculated from the following equations:

$$\dot{m}_{5*}h_{5*} = \dot{m}_{6*}h_{6*} \quad (3.30)$$

$$\dot{m}_{8*}h_{8*} = \dot{m}_{9*}h_{9*} \quad (3.31)$$

Heat Exchanger (HEX)

The heat transferred within the heat exchanger in the ARS system can be calculated from the following equation:

$$\dot{Q}_{HEX} = \dot{m}_{2*}(h_{3*} - h_{2*}) \quad (3.32)$$

Where “ \dot{Q}_{HEX} ” refers to the heat transfer rate through the solution heat exchanger.

Evaporator₂

The heat transferred from the evaporator₂ in the system can be calculated from the following equation:

$$\dot{Q}_{Evap2} = \dot{m}_{10*}(h_{10*} - h_{9*}) \quad (3.33)$$

Where “ \dot{Q}_{Evap2} ” refers to the heat transfer rate through the evaporator₂.

Absorber

The heat absorbed from the absorber in the system can be calculated from the following equation:

$$\dot{Q}_{ARS} = \dot{m}_{1*}h_{1*} - \dot{m}_{6*}h_{6*} - \dot{m}_{10*}h_{10*} \quad (3.34)$$

Where “ \dot{Q}_{ARS} ” represents the exergy rate for absorber .

Pump₅

The work required to run the pumps can be calculated from the following equation:

$$\dot{W}_{\text{Pump5}} = \dot{m}_{1*}(h_{2*} - h_{1*}) \quad (3.35)$$

Where “ \dot{W}_{Pump5} ” represents the work required by pump₅.

3.5.2. Exergy Analysis of the Integration System

The exergy rate is the most useful theoretical work achieved when a system transforms from its initial state to thermal and mechanical equilibrium with its surroundings. The following formula for exergy balance will be used to determine each part's exergy destruction[121]:

$$\dot{E}_Q - \dot{E}_W = \sum \dot{E}_{\text{out}} - \sum \dot{E}_{\text{in}} - \dot{E}_{\text{Dest}} \quad (3.36)$$

Where: “ \dot{E}_Q ” refers to the exergy rate for heat transfer (MW), “ \dot{E}_W ” represents the exergy rate for work transfer (MW), “ \dot{E}_{out} ” indicates the exergy rate for system outputs (MW), “ \dot{E}_{in} ” refers to the exergy rate for system inputs (MW), and “ \dot{E}_{Dest} ” refers to the exergy destruction rate (MW).

The stream exergy rate by heat is determined using the following equation [122].

$$\dot{E}_Q = \left(1 - \frac{T_{\text{amb}}}{T_i}\right) \dot{Q}_i \quad (3.37)$$

Where: “ T_{amb} ”, indicates the environment temperature for a dead state (K), “ T_i ” refers to the system boundary temperature for heat transfer happens (K), and “ \dot{Q}_i ”, represents the heat transfer rate (MW).

The exergy balance for a system in a steady state is stated as follows[123].

$$\dot{E}_f = \dot{E}_p + \dot{E}_{\text{dest}} \quad (3.38)$$

Here, \dot{E}_f , \dot{E}_p , and \dot{E}_{dest} represent the exergy flow of fuel, product, and destruction, respectively. According to the second law analysis, the exergy destruction rate represents the loss of the ability to convert energy into usable work. To examine a system's exergy efficiency, the fuel and product exergy of each component are evaluated using the surplus efficiency principles[124].

$$\Psi = \left(1 - \frac{\dot{E}_{dest}}{\dot{E}_f} \right) = \frac{\dot{E}_p}{\dot{E}_f} \quad (3.39)$$

where Ψ represents the exergy efficiency.

3.5.2.1. Exergy Analysis of Brayton Cycle Components

Air Compressor

The calculation of exergy destruction for the air compressor can be calculated using the following equation.

$$\dot{E}_{D,AC} = \dot{W}_{AC} + \dot{E}_{22} - \dot{E}_{23} \quad (3.40)$$

Where “ $\dot{E}_{D,AC}$ ”, indicates the exergy destruction rate for the air compressor.

Combustion Chamber

The exergy destruction in the combustion chamber can be accurately calculated using the following equation:

$$\dot{E}_{D,CC} = \dot{E}_{23} + \dot{E}_{24} - \dot{E}_{25} \quad (3.41)$$

Where “ $\dot{E}_{D,CC}$ ” refers to the exergy destruction rate for the combustion chamber.

Gas Turbine

The exergy destruction in the gas turbine is determined as:

$$\dot{E}_{D,GT} = \dot{E}_{25} - \dot{E}_{26} - \dot{W}_{GT} \quad (3.42)$$

Where “ $\dot{E}_{D,GT}$ ” refers to the exergy destruction rate for gas turbines.

3.5.2.2 Exergy Analysis of Steam Rankine Cycle Components

Heat Recovery Steam Generator (HRSG)

The following formula can be used to determine HRSG exergy destruction:

$$\dot{E}_{D,HRSG} = \dot{E}_{26} - \dot{E}_{27} + \dot{E}_{19} - \dot{E}_{20} - \dot{E}_{14} - \dot{E}_1 - \dot{E}_{33} - \dot{E}_{28} \quad (3.43)$$

Where “ $\dot{E}_{D,HRSG}$ ” indicates the exergy destruction rate for HRSG (MW).

Steam Turbines

The following formula can be used to determine the exergy destruction for the HPST:

$$\dot{E}_{D,HPST} = \dot{E}_1 - \dot{E}_2 - \dot{W}_{HPST} \quad (3.44)$$

Where “ $\dot{E}_{D,HPST}$ ”, refers to the exergy destruction rate for HPST

The following formula can be used to calculate exergy destruction for the IPST:

$$\dot{E}_{D,IPST} = \dot{E}_3 - \dot{E}_5 - \dot{W}_{IPST} \quad (3.45)$$

Where “ $\dot{E}_{D,IPST}$ ” indicates the exergy destruction rate for IPST.

The following formula can be used to calculate the exergy destruction for the LPST:

$$\dot{E}_{D,LPST} = \dot{E}_6 - \dot{E}_8 - \dot{W}_{LPST} \quad (3.46)$$

Where “ $\dot{E}_{D,LPST}$ ” represents the exergy destruction rate for the LPST.

Condenser₁

The following formula can be used to find condenser exergy destruction.

$$\dot{E}_{D,Cond} = \dot{E}_{15} - \dot{E}_{16} - \frac{\dot{Q}_{Cond}}{T_b} \quad (3.47)$$

Where: “ $\dot{E}_{D,Cond}$ ” refers to the the rate of exergy destruction for the condenser, “ \dot{Q}_{Cond} ” indicates the heat rejected by the condenser to the cooling medium, and “ T_b ”, represents the temperature of the thermal reservoir (cooling medium).

Pumps

The following formula can be used to determine the exergy destruction for each Pumps:

For pump₁:

$$\dot{E}_{D,P1} = \dot{W}_{P1} + \dot{E}_7 - \dot{E}_{10} \quad (3.48)$$

Where “ $\dot{E}_{D,P1}$ ” refers to the exergy destruction rate for Pump₁.

For pump₂:

$$\dot{E}_{D,P2} = \dot{W}_{P2} + \dot{E}_{11} - \dot{E}_{12} \quad (3.49)$$

Where “ $\dot{E}_{D,P2}$ ” refers to the exergy destruction rate for Pump₂.

Pump₃

$$\dot{E}_{D,P3} = \dot{W}_{P3} + \dot{E}_{13} - \dot{E}_{14} \quad (3.50)$$

Where “ $\dot{E}_{D,P3}$ ” indicates the exergy destruction rate for Pump₃.

Open Feed Water Heaters (OFWHs)

The following formula may be used to calculate the exergy destruction for OFWHs:

$$\dot{E}_{D,OFWH1} = \dot{E}_7 + \dot{E}_{10} - \dot{E}_{11} \quad (3.51)$$

$$\dot{E}_{D,OFWH2} = \dot{E}_4 + \dot{E}_{12} - \dot{E}_{13} \quad (3.52)$$

Where: “ $\dot{E}_{D,OFWH}$ ”, refers to the exergy destruction rate for OFWH₁, and “ $\dot{E}_{D,OFWH2}$ ”, represents the exergy destruction rate for OFWH₂.

3.5.2.3. Exergy Analysis of Organic Rankine Cycle Components

The following equations can be used to quantify the irreversibility of useful energy within the ORC Parts starting with the organic turbine ORT, HE, ORP, EVAP and condenser₂.

Organic Rankine Turbine

The following formula can be used to determine ORT’s exergy destruction:

$$\dot{E}_{D,ORT} = (\dot{E}_{29} + \dot{E}_{30}) - \dot{W}_{ORT} \quad (3.53)$$

Where “ $\dot{E}_{D,ORT}$ ” refers to the exergy destruction for the ORT.

Heat Exchanger

The following formula can be used to determine organic HE’s exergy destruction:

$$\dot{E}_{D,HE} = \dot{E}_{30} + \dot{E}_{33} - \dot{E}_{31} - \dot{E}_{34} \quad (3.54)$$

Where “ $\dot{E}_{D,HE}$ ”, represents the exergy destruction for the heat exchanger.

Organic Pump

The following formula can be used to determine ORP’s exergy destruction:

$$\dot{E}_{D,ORP} = \dot{W}_{ORP} + \dot{E}_{32} - \dot{E}_{33} \quad (3.55)$$

Where “ $\dot{E}_{D,ORP}$ ”, illustrates the exergy destruction for the ORP.

Evaporator₁

The following formula can be used to determine organic evaporator₁’s exergy destruction:

$$\dot{E}_{D,Evap1} = \dot{E}_{27} - \dot{E}_{28} + \dot{E}_{34} - \dot{E}_{29} \quad (3.56)$$

Where “ $\dot{E}_{D,EVAP1}$ ”, refers to the exergy destruction in the evaporator₁.

Condenser₂

The following formula can be used to determine organic condenser₂’s exergy destruction:

$$\dot{E}_{D,Cond_2} = (\dot{E}_{31} - \dot{E}_{32}) + (\dot{E}_{35} - \dot{E}_{36}) \quad (3.57)$$

Where “ $\dot{E}_{D,Cond_2}$ ” indicates the Exergy destruction in the condenser₂.

3.5.2.4 Exergy Analysis of Solar Field Components

PTC

The exergy of the solar field, associated with solar radiation (\dot{E}_s), is defined as follows:

$$\dot{E}_{Q,solar} = \left(1 - \frac{T_{amb}}{T_{sun}}\right) \dot{Q}_{solar} \quad (3.58)$$

Where: " $\dot{E}_{Q,solar}$ " refers to the exergy rate for solar radiation (MW), " T_{sun} ", represents the effective temperature of the sun (K), and " \dot{Q}_{solar} ", indicates the solar heat rate energy collected (MW).

Thermal Energy Storage (TES)

The following equations quantify the irreversibility or loss of useful energy within thermal energy storage system

$$\dot{E}_{D,TST} = \dot{E}_{17} + \dot{E}_{21} - \dot{E}_{19} - \dot{E}_{18} \quad (3.59)$$

Where " $\dot{E}_{D,TST}$ ", denotes the exergy destruction in the thermal storage tank

3.5.2.5 Exergy Analysis of Absorption Refrigeration System Components

Generator

The exergy destruction for the generator can be defined as follows:

$$\dot{E}_{D,Gen*} = \dot{E}_{28} + \dot{E}_{3*} - \dot{E}_{37} + \dot{E}_{7*} - \dot{E}_{4*} \quad (3.60)$$

Where " $\dot{E}_{D,Gen*}$ ", refers to the exergy destruction rate of the generator.

Expansion Valves

$$\dot{E}_{D,Evl} = \dot{E}_{5*} - \dot{E}_{6*} \quad (3.61)$$

$$\dot{E}_{D,Val2} = \dot{E}_{8*} - \dot{E}_{9*} \quad (3.62)$$

Where, “ $\dot{E}_{D,Ev1}$,and $\dot{E}_{D,Ev2}$ ” refers to the exergy destruction rate of the Expansion Valves 1 and 2.

Condenser₃

The exergy destruction for the condenser₃ can be defined as follows:

$$\dot{E}_{D,Cond3} = \dot{E}_{7*} - \dot{E}_{14*} + \dot{E}_{15*} - \dot{E}_{8*} \quad (3.63)$$

Where “ $\dot{E}_{D,Cond3}$ ”, refers to the exergy destruction rate of the condenser₃.

Evaporator₂

The exergy destruction for the evaporator₂ can be defined as follows:

$$\dot{E}_{D,Evap2} = \dot{E}_{10*} + \dot{E}_{22} - \dot{E}_{9*} - \dot{E}_{11*} \quad (3.64)$$

Where “ $\dot{E}_{D,Evap2}$ ” indicates the exergy destruction rate of the evaporator₂.

Absorber

The following equations quantify the irreversibility or loss of useful energy within the absorber:

$$\dot{E}_{D,Abs} = \dot{E}_{10*} + \dot{E}_{6*} - \dot{E}_{12*} + \dot{E}_{13*} - \dot{E}_{1*} \quad (3.65)$$

Where “ $\dot{E}_{D,Abs}$ ”, represents the exergy destruction rate within the absorber.

Heat Exchanger

The exergy destruction for the heat exchanger can be defined as follows:

$$\dot{E}_{D,HEX} = \dot{E}_{4*} + \dot{E}_{2*} - \dot{E}_{5*} - \dot{E}_{3*} \quad (3.66)$$

Where “ $\dot{E}_{D,HEX}$ ”, represents the exergy destruction rate within the heat exchanger.

Pump₅

The exergy destruction for the pump₅ can be defined as follows:

$$\dot{E}_{D,Pump5} = \dot{W}_{Pump,5} + \dot{E}_{2*} - \dot{E}_{1*} \quad (3.67)$$

Where “ $\dot{E}_{D,Pump5}$ ”, represents the exergy destruction rate within pump₅.

3.6. TOTAL SYSTEM PERFORMANCE

The following formulas are used to determine the performance of the system [125].

$$\eta_{BC} = \frac{\dot{W}_{GT} - \dot{W}_{AC}}{\dot{Q}_{in,CC}} \quad (3.68)$$

$$\eta_{th} = \frac{\dot{W}_{GT} - \dot{W}_{AC} + \dot{W}_{HPST} + \dot{W}_{IPST} + \dot{W}_{LPST} + \dot{W}_{ORT} + \dot{W}_{Pumps}}{\dot{Q}_{in}} \quad (3.69)$$

$$\eta_{ex} = \frac{\dot{W}_{GT} - \dot{W}_{AC} + \dot{W}_{HPST} + \dot{W}_{IPST} + \dot{W}_{LPST} + \dot{W}_{ORT} + \dot{W}_{Pumps}}{\dot{E}_3 + \dot{E}_{Q_{solar}}} \quad (3.70)$$

Where, “ η_{th} ”, refers to the thermal efficiency, “ η_{ex} ”, refers to the exergy efficiency, “ $\dot{Q}_{in,CC}$ ”, refers to the heat inlet for the combustion chamber, “ \dot{Q}_{in} ”, refers to the total heat input to the system, and “ \dot{E}_3 ”, refers to the exergy input from fuel (chemical exergy). Table 3.2. summarizes the energy and exergy balance equations for each component of the Model 3 system.

Table 3.2. Energy and Exergy balance equations for all components of the Model 3 system.

Component	Energy Balances	Exergy Balances
AC	$\dot{W}_{AC} = \dot{m}_{air}(h_{23} - h_{22})$	$\dot{E}_{D,AC} = \dot{W}_{AC} + \dot{E}_{22} - \dot{E}_{23}$
CC	$\dot{m}_{air}h_{23} + \dot{m}_{fuel}LHV = (\dot{m}_{fuel} + \dot{m}_{air})h_{25}$	$\dot{E}_{D,CC} = (\dot{E}_{23} + \dot{E}_{24}) - \dot{E}_{25}$
GT	$\dot{W}_{GT} = \dot{m}_{25}(h_{25} - h_{26})$	$\dot{E}_{D,GT} = (\dot{E}_{25} - \dot{E}_{26}) - \dot{W}_{GT}$
HRSG	$\dot{Q}_{HRSG} = \dot{m}_{25}(h_{26} - h_{27}) + \dot{m}_{19}(\dot{h}_{19} - h_{20})$ $= \dot{m}_{14}(h_1 - h_{14})$	$\dot{E}_{D,HRSG} = (\dot{E}_{26} - \dot{E}_{27})$ $+ (\dot{E}_{19} - \dot{E}_{20})$ $+ (\dot{E}_{14} - \dot{E}_1)$
HPST	$\dot{W}_{HPST} = \dot{m}_1(h_1 - h_2)$	$\dot{E}_{D,HPST} = \dot{E}_1 - \dot{E}_2 - \dot{W}_{HPST}$
IPST	$\dot{W}_{IPST} = \dot{m}_3(h_3 - h_5)$	$\dot{E}_{D,IPST} = \dot{E}_3 - \dot{E}_5 - \dot{W}_{IPST}$
LPST	$\dot{W}_{LPST} = \dot{m}_6(h_6 - h_8)$	$\dot{E}_{D,LPST} = \dot{E}_6 - \dot{E}_8 - \dot{W}_{LPST}$
Cond1	$\dot{Q}_{Cond1} = \dot{m}_8(h_8 - h_9)$	$\dot{E}_{D,Cond1} = (\dot{E}_8 - \dot{E}_9)$ $+ (\dot{E}_{15} - \dot{E}_{16})$
Cond2	$\dot{Q}_{Cond2} = \dot{m}_{31}(h_{31} - h_{32})$	$\dot{E}_{D,Cond2} = (\dot{E}_{31} - \dot{E}_{32})$ $+ (\dot{E}_{35} - \dot{E}_{36})$
Pump4	$\dot{W}_{P4} = \dot{m}_{20}(h_{21} - h_{20})$	$\dot{E}_{D,P4} = \dot{W}_{P4} + \dot{E}_{20} - \dot{E}_{21}$
Pump1	$\dot{W}_{P1} = \dot{m}_9(h_{10} - h_9)$	$\dot{E}_{D,P1} = \dot{W}_{P1} + \dot{E}_9 - \dot{E}_{10}$
Pump2	$\dot{W}_{P2} = \dot{m}_{11}(h_{12} - h_{11})$	$\dot{E}_{D,P2} = \dot{W}_{P2} + \dot{E}_{11} - \dot{E}_{12}$
Pump3	$\dot{W}_{P3} = \dot{m}_{13}(h_{14} - h_{13})$	$\dot{E}_{D,P3} = \dot{W}_{P3} + \dot{E}_{13} - \dot{E}_{14}$
OFWH1	$\dot{Q}_{OFWH1} = (\dot{m}_{10}h_{10} + \dot{m}_7h_7) = (\dot{m}_{11}h_{11})$	$\dot{E}_{D,OFWH1} = \dot{E}_7 + \dot{E}_{10} - \dot{E}_{11}$
OFWH2	$\dot{Q}_{OFWH2} = (\dot{m}_{12}h_{12} + \dot{m}_4h_4) = (\dot{m}_{13}h_{13})$	$\dot{E}_{D,OFWH2} = \dot{E}_4 + \dot{E}_{12} - \dot{E}_{13}$
ORT	$\dot{W}_{ORT} = \dot{m}_{29}(h_{29} - h_{30})$	$\dot{E}_{D,ORT} = (\dot{E}_{29} + \dot{E}_{30}) - \dot{W}_{ORT}$
HE	$\dot{Q}_{HE} = \dot{m}_{30}(h_{30} - h_{31})$	$\dot{E}_{D,HE} = \dot{E}_{30} + \dot{E}_{33} - \dot{E}_{31} - \dot{E}_{34}$
ORP	$\dot{W}_{ORP} = \dot{m}_{32}(h_{33} - h_{32})$	$\dot{E}_{D,ORP} = \dot{W}_{ORP} + \dot{E}_{32} - \dot{E}_{33}$
EVAP1	$\dot{Q}_{Evap1} = \dot{m}_{27}(h_{27} - h_{28})$	$\dot{E}_{D,Evap1} = \dot{E}_{27} - \dot{E}_{28} + \dot{E}_{34}$ $- \dot{E}_{29}$
PTC	$\dot{Q}_{solar} = \eta_{PTC} * A_{ap} * DNI$	$\dot{E}_{Q,solar} = \left(1 - \frac{T_0}{T_{sun}}\right) \dot{Q}_{solar}$
TST	$\dot{Q}_{TST} = \dot{m}_{17}(h_{17} + h_{18})$	$\dot{E}_{D,TST} = \dot{E}_{17} + \dot{E}_{21} - \dot{E}_{19} - \dot{E}_{18}$
Gen	$\dot{Q}_{Gen} = \dot{m}_{28}(h_{28} - h_{37})$	$\dot{E}_{D,Gen} = \dot{E}_{28} + \dot{E}_{3*} - \dot{E}_{37} - \dot{E}_{7*}$ $- \dot{E}_{4*}$
Abs	$\dot{Q}_{ARS} = \dot{m}_{1*}h_{1*} - \dot{m}_{6*}h_{6*} - \dot{m}_{10*}h_{10*}$	$\dot{E}_{D,ARS} = \dot{E}_{10*} + \dot{E}_{6*} - \dot{E}_{12*}$ $+ \dot{E}_{13*} - \dot{E}_{1*}$
HEX	$\dot{Q}_{HEX} = \dot{m}_{2*}(h_{3*} - h_{2*})$	$\dot{E}_{D,HEX} = \dot{E}_{4*} + \dot{E}_{2*} - \dot{E}_{5*} - \dot{E}_{3*}$

Pump5	$\dot{W}_{Pump5} = \dot{m}_{1*}(h_{2*} - h_{1*})$	$\dot{E}_{D,Pump5} = \dot{W}_{Pump5} + \dot{E}_{2*} - \dot{E}_{1*}$
Evap2	$\dot{Q}_{Evap2} = \dot{m}_{10*}(h_{10*} - h_{9*})$	$\dot{E}_{D,Evap2} = \dot{E}_{10*} + \dot{E}_{22} - \dot{E}_{9*} - \dot{E}_{11*}$
Exv1	$\dot{m}_{5*}h_{5*} = \dot{m}_{6*}h_{6*}$	$\dot{E}_{D,Exv1} = \dot{E}_{5*} - \dot{E}_{6*}$
Exv2	$\dot{m}_{8*}h_{8*} = \dot{m}_{9*}h_{9*}$	$\dot{E}_{D,Exv2} = \dot{E}_{2*} - \dot{E}_{9*}$
Cond3	$\dot{Q}_{Cond3} = \dot{m}_{7*}(h_{8*} - h_{7*})$	$\dot{E}_{D,Cond3} = \dot{E}_{7*} - \dot{E}_{14*} + \dot{E}_{15*}$ $- \dot{E}_{8*}$

3.7. EXERGOECONOMIC ANALYSIS

Exergoeconomic analysis combines exergy and cost analysis for a complete energy system assessment, measuring thermodynamic efficiency and economic viability. This methodology identifies high-impact inefficiencies and optimization opportunities by assessing each component's costs associated with useful and destroyed exergy. First, we perform an exergy analysis to determine the exergy of all streams and the exergy destruction within each component. Next, exergoeconomic analysis needs to define parameters such as product and fuel exergy per component and then formulate cost rate balance equations linking input, operational, and output costs with exergy destruction costs. These equations demonstrate the link between irreversibilities and economic losses, guiding cost assignment to energy flows and revealing key areas for optimization. Exergoeconomic analysis assigns monetary values to exergy destruction and useful outputs, thus enabling system-wide optimization and helping engineers prioritize cost-saving and efficiency-boosting investments. The combined focus on thermodynamics and economics makes it essential for developing and optimizing energy systems, particularly complex systems with renewable integration or advanced cycles, thereby ensuring cost-effective and sustainable results [56]. The following equations are applied to perform the exergoeconomic analysis:

$$\sum_e \dot{C}_{e,k} + \dot{C}_{w,k} = \dot{C}_{q,k} + \sum_i \dot{C}_{i,k} + \dot{Z}_k \quad (3.71)$$

Where: “ $\sum_e \dot{C}_{e,k}$ ” refers to cost rate of exergy entering component k , “ $\dot{C}_{w,k}$ ” indicates the cost rate of work supplied to component k , “ $\dot{C}_{q,k}$ ” represents the cost

rate of thermal energy (heat) leaving component k , “ $\sum_i \dot{C}_{i,k}$ ” illustrates the cost rate of exergy leaving the component k , and “ \dot{Z}_k ” refers to the cost rate of irreversibilities (exergy destruction) within component k .

An investment's equivalent uniform annual cost over its lifespan is calculated using the economic metric known as the cost recovery factor (CRF). It facilitates the comparison of investments with differing cash flow patterns while accounting for the time value of money, ensuring a comprehensive financial analysis. The CRF, along with \dot{Z}_k , can be determined using the following equations: [115]:

$$\text{CRF} = \frac{i(1+i)^n}{(1+i)^n - 1} \quad (3.72)$$

$$\dot{Z}_k = \dot{Z}_k = \frac{Z_k \cdot \text{CRF} \cdot \varphi}{N \times 3600} \quad (3.73)$$

Where: “CRF” represents the cost recovery factor, “ i ” refers to the discount rate (interest rate), “ n ” illustrates the economic life of investment in years, “ Z_k ” indicates the total investment cost of component k , “ φ ” represents the maintenance factor, and “ N ”, indicates the number of operational hours per year. The cost rate “ \dot{C} ” can be determined using the following equations

$$\dot{C}_j = c_j \dot{E}_j \quad (3.74)$$

Additionally, exergoeconomic analysis evaluates the system using specific performance indicators. These include the exergy destruction cost rate, the cost per unit of exergy for both fuel and product and the exergoeconomic factor, which are defined as follows:

$$c_{F,k} = \dot{C}_{F,k} / \dot{E}_{F,k} \quad (3.75)$$

For each component k in the fuel stream, “ $c_{P,k}$ ” represents the cost rate per unit of exergy flow. The cost rate associated with the fuel supply for the component is

denoted by “ $c_{F,k}$ ”. The exergy flow rate of the fuel stream’s components is expressed by “ $\dot{E}_{P,k}$ ” stream:

$$c_{P,k} = \dot{C}_{P,k} / \dot{E}_{P,k} \quad (3.76)$$

The cost rate corresponding to the exergy destruction “ $\dot{C}_{D,k}$ ” of all components is calculated as follows:

$$\dot{C}_{D,k} = c_{F,k} \dot{E}_{D,k} \quad (3.77)$$

The exergoeconomic factor for the component is calculated as follows:

$$f_k = \dot{Z}_k / (\dot{Z}_k + \dot{C}_{D,k}) \quad (3.78)$$

Table 3.3. Cost balance and supplementary equations for the system components [126].

Table 3.3. Cost balance and supplementary equations for the system components [126].

Component	Exergetic cost rate balance equation	Auxiliary Equation
AC	$\dot{C}_{22} + \dot{C}_{W,AC} + \dot{Z}_{AC} = \dot{C}_{23}$	$c_{W,AC} = c_{W,GT}$
CC	$\dot{C}_{24} + \dot{C}_{23} + \dot{Z}_{CC} = \dot{C}_{25}$	$\frac{\dot{C}_{23}}{\dot{E}_{23}} = \frac{\dot{C}_{25}}{\dot{E}_{25}}$,
GT	$\dot{C}_{25} + \dot{Z}_{W,GT} = \dot{C}_{26} + \dot{C}_{GT}$	$\frac{\dot{C}_{25}}{\dot{E}_{25}} = \frac{\dot{C}_{26}}{\dot{E}_{26}}$
HRSG	$\dot{C}_{26} + \dot{C}_{19} + \dot{C}_{14} + \dot{Z}_{HRSG}$ $= \dot{C}_{27} + \dot{C}_{20} + \dot{C}_1$	$\frac{\dot{C}_{26}}{\dot{E}_{26}} = \frac{\dot{C}_{27}}{\dot{E}_{27}}$
HPST	$\dot{C}_1 + \dot{Z}_{W,HPST} = \dot{C}_2 + \dot{C}_{HPST}$	$\frac{\dot{C}_1}{\dot{E}_1} = \frac{\dot{C}_2}{\dot{E}_2}$
IPST	$\dot{C}_3 + \dot{Z}_{W,IPST} = \dot{C}_5 + \dot{C}_{IPST}$	$\frac{\dot{C}_3}{\dot{E}_3} = \frac{\dot{C}_5}{\dot{E}_5}$
LPST	$\dot{C}_6 + \dot{Z}_{W,LPST} = \dot{C}_8 + \dot{C}_{LPST}$	$\frac{\dot{C}_6}{\dot{E}_6} = \frac{\dot{C}_8}{\dot{E}_8}$
Cond ₁	$\dot{C}_8 + \dot{C}_{15} + \dot{Z}_{cond1} = \dot{C}_9 + \dot{C}_{14}$	$\frac{\dot{C}_8}{\dot{E}_8} = \frac{\dot{C}_9}{\dot{E}_9}$
Cond ₂	$\dot{C}_{31} + \dot{C}_{35} + \dot{Z}_{cond2} = \dot{C}_{32} + \dot{C}_{36}$	$\frac{\dot{C}_{31}}{\dot{E}_{31}} = \frac{\dot{C}_{32}}{\dot{E}_{32}}$

Pump₄	$\dot{C}_{20} + \dot{C}_{W,P4} + \dot{Z}_{P4} = \dot{C}_{21}$	$C_{W,P4} = C_{W,HPST}$
Pump₁	$\dot{C}_9 + \dot{C}_{W,P1} + \dot{Z}_{P1} = \dot{C}_{10}$	$C_{W,P1} = C_{W,HPST}$
Pump₂	$\dot{C}_{11} + \dot{C}_{W,P2} + \dot{Z}_{P2} = \dot{C}_{12}$	$C_{W,P2} = C_{W,IPST}$
Pump₃	$\dot{C}_{13} + \dot{C}_{W,P3} + \dot{Z}_{P3} = \dot{C}_{14}$	$C_{W,P3} = C_{W,LPST}$
OFWH₁	$\dot{C}_{10} + \dot{C}_7 + \dot{Z}_{OFWH1} = \dot{C}_{11}$	
OFWH₂	$\dot{C}_{12} + \dot{C}_4 + \dot{Z}_{OFWH2} = \dot{C}_{13}$	
ORT	$\dot{C}_{29} + \dot{Z}_{W,ORT} = \dot{C}_{30} + \dot{C}_{orgT}$	$\frac{\dot{C}_{29}}{\dot{E}_{29}} = \frac{\dot{C}_{30}}{\dot{E}_{30}}$
HE	$\dot{C}_{32} + \dot{C}_{W,ORP} + \dot{Z}_{ORP} = \dot{C}_{33}$	$\frac{\dot{C}_{30}}{\dot{E}_{30}} = \frac{\dot{C}_{31}}{\dot{E}_{31}}$
ORP	$\dot{C}_{32} + \dot{C}_{W,P4} + \dot{Z}_{P4} = \dot{C}_{33}$	$C_{W,ORP} = C_{W,orgT}$
Evap₁	$\dot{C}_{27} + \dot{C}_{34} + \dot{Z}_{Evap1} = \dot{C}_{28} + \dot{C}_{29}$	$\frac{\dot{C}_{34}}{\dot{E}_{34}} = \frac{\dot{C}_{29}}{\dot{E}_{29}}$
PTC	$\dot{C}_{18} + \dot{C}_{q,solar} + \dot{Z}_{PTC} = \dot{C}_{17}$	$\dot{C}_{q,solar} = 0$
TST	$\dot{C}_{17} + \dot{C}_{21} + \dot{Z}_{TST} = \dot{C}_{19} + \dot{C}_{18}$	$\frac{\dot{C}_{17}}{\dot{E}_{17}} = \frac{\dot{C}_{19}}{\dot{E}_{19}}$
GEN	$\dot{C}_{28} + \dot{C}_{3*} + \dot{Z}_{GEN} = \dot{C}_{37} + \dot{C}_{7*} + \dot{C}_{4*}$	$\frac{\dot{C}_{4*} - \dot{C}_{3*}}{\dot{E}_{4*} - \dot{E}_{3*}} = \frac{\dot{C}_{7*} - \dot{C}_{3*}}{\dot{E}_{7*} - \dot{E}_{3*}}$
Pump₅	$\dot{C}_{1*} + \dot{C}_{W,P5} + \dot{Z}_{P5} = \dot{C}_{2*}$	$C_{W,P5} = C_{W,ORT}$
HEX	$\dot{C}_{2*} + \dot{C}_{4*} + \dot{Z}_{HCX} = \dot{C}_{3*} + \dot{C}_{5*}$	$\frac{\dot{C}_{4*}}{\dot{E}_{4*}} = \frac{\dot{C}_{5*}}{\dot{E}_{5*}}$
EXV₁	$\dot{C}_{5*} + \dot{Z}_{EXV1} = \dot{C}_{6*}$	
Abs	$\dot{C}_{6*} + \dot{C}_{13} + \dot{C}_{10} + \dot{Z}_{Abs} = \dot{C}_{1*} + \dot{C}_{12*}$	$\frac{\dot{C}_{6*} + \dot{C}_{10*}}{\dot{E}_{6*} + \dot{E}_{10*}} = \frac{\dot{C}_{1*}}{\dot{E}_{1*}}, C_{13*} = 0$
Evap₂	$\dot{C}_{9*} + \dot{C}_{11*} + \dot{Z}_{Evap2} = \dot{C}_{22*} + \dot{C}_{10*}$	$\frac{\dot{C}_{9*}}{\dot{E}_{9*}} = \frac{\dot{C}_{10*}}{\dot{E}_{10*}}, C_{11*} = 0$
EXV₂	$\dot{C}_{8*} + \dot{Z}_{EXV2} = \dot{C}_{9*}$	
Cond₃	$\dot{C}_{7*} + \dot{C}_{15*} + \dot{Z}_{cond3} = \dot{C}_{8*} + \dot{C}_{14*}$	$\frac{\dot{C}_{7*}}{\dot{E}_{7*}} = \frac{\dot{C}_{8*}}{\dot{E}_{8*}}, C_{15*} = 0$

Exergoeconomic analysis offers a comprehensive understanding of the costs associated with exergy destruction, enabling the definition of an objective function aimed at minimizing the total cost rate \dot{C}_{total} . This total cost rate encompasses the combined owning and operating expenses, as well as the aggregate cost rate attributed to exergy destruction. The total cost rate can be determined using the following formula[127]:

$$\dot{C}_{total} = \sum_k \dot{Z}_k + \sum_k \dot{C}_{D,k} \quad (3.79)$$

Ultimately, the total cost of electricity per unit of energy, expressed in \$/MJ, is calculated using the following equation[128] :

$$\dot{C}_{\text{electricity,Tot}} = \sum_{k=1}^N \dot{C}_{\text{total}}/\dot{W}_{\text{net}} \quad (3.80)$$

Here, $\dot{C}_{\text{electricity,Tot}}$ represents the total cost of electricity for each kilowatt-hour of energy produced by the system.

3.8. ENVIRONMENTAL ANALYSIS

To determine the CO₂ emissions associated with electricity generation, the total CO₂ emissions produced over a specific period are divided by the total power generated. The following formula is applied to calculate this emission rate [129].

$$\epsilon_{\text{CO}_2} = \frac{\dot{m}_{\text{CO}_2}}{\dot{W}_{\text{net}}} \quad (3.81)$$

$$\dot{m}_{\text{CO}_2} = y_{\text{CO}_2} \dot{m}_{\text{g},5} \left(\frac{\bar{M}_{\text{CO}_2}}{\bar{M}_{\text{g}}} \right) \quad (3.82)$$

Here, y_{CO_2} represents the mole percentage and \bar{M}_{CO_2} denotes the molar weight of CO₂. Additionally, \dot{m}_{g} and \bar{M}_{g} correspond to the mole fraction and molar weight of the exhaust gases in the combustion chamber.

CHAPTER 4

DISCUSSION OF THE RESULTS

4.1. INTRODUCTION

This chapter comprehensively evaluates how integrating advanced energy recovery and storage technologies can enhance the efficiency, cost-effectiveness, and environmental performance of the Integrated Gas Turbine Power Plant (IGTPP) system. The study aims to establish a robust framework for optimizing the IGTPP by incorporating exhaust heat recovery, Steam Rankine Cycle (SRC), Organic Rankine Cycle (ORC), Parabolic Trough Collector (PTC), Thermal Energy Storage (TES), and Absorption Refrigeration System (ARS) technologies. This integrated approach lays the foundation for sustainable energy development by maximizing the utilization of available thermal and solar resources. Through the adoption of innovative energy strategies, the study seeks to improve the sustainability of the Kirkuk Gas Power Station by enhancing thermal and electrical efficiencies, reducing environmental impacts, and increasing energy production capacity. Ultimately, the research underscores the importance of minimizing greenhouse gas emissions and reducing dependence on conventional fossil fuels, aligning global sustainability and climate change mitigation goals.

Furthermore, integrating these advanced cycles offers valuable insights into such systems' operational and financial feasibility. The study aims to provide a comprehensive economic perspective on implementing these technologies by analyzing cost dynamics and potential returns on investment. This evaluation is crucial for demonstrating the long-term benefits of the integrated system, including enhanced power generation efficiency, reduced energy costs, and improved operational stability. The insights generated are intended to serve as guiding principles for energy policy-makers and industry leaders considering the adoption of

similar IGTPP configurations in Iraq and comparable high solar irradiance regions, where maximizing renewable energy output and improving grid resilience are paramount. Ultimately, this work advocates for a forward-looking vision in the energy sector, proposing that strategic integration of renewable and conventional energy technologies, coupled with innovative storage solutions, can foster energy systems that are economically viable, environmentally responsible, and capable of meeting increasing energy demands. This approach globally models sustainable, efficient energy production, improving Kirkuk's Iraqi energy role.

4.2. VALIDATION

Table 4.1. presents a comparison between the numerical results from previous simulation studies [130] and those derived from the current investigation conducted on a gas turbine unit in Kirkuk. The present research reveals a high degree of consistency, with most deviations falling below 2%, validating the reliability of the present study. Key parameters such as ambient temperature, pressure ratio, and air mass flow rate show no deviations, confirming that the operational conditions and assumptions are perfectly aligned with existing literature. Minor deviations, like the 1.36% difference in fuel mass flow rate and maximum temperature, could be due to improved measurement techniques, more accurate system modeling, or slight experimental variations. The outlet compressor temperature shows a small deviation of 1.05%, likely caused by differences in thermal losses or control strategies. A 1.6% deviation in exhaust temperature may reflect minor discrepancies in heat transfer or energy dissipation, possibly influenced by updated material properties or changing environmental conditions. The power output has a minimal deviation of 0.53%, which might result from real-world inefficiencies not captured in theoretical models, while the thermal efficiency shows a slight positive deviation of 0.88%, indicating potential gains from system optimization. Overall, the strong consistency between the results validates the methodology and accuracy of this research, confirming its relevance and applicability to real-world scenarios.

Table 4.1. Comparison of Results from Previous Works[130] and Current study on the Gas Turbine Unit

Parameter	Unit	Literature Study [130]	Present Research	Deviation (%)
Ambient temperature	°C	19	19	0%
Pressure ratio (PR)	-	12	12	0%
Flow rate of air mass	kg\s	438	438	0%
Flow rate of fuel mass	kg\s	8.8	8.92	1.36%
Outlet compressor temperature	°C	315.7	319	1.05%
Maximum temperature	°C	1100	1115	1.36%
Exhaust temperature	°C	500	508	1.6%
Power output	MW	150	149.2	0.53
Thermal efficiency	%	34	34.3	0.88%

Table 4.2. compares the performance parameters of a regenerative ORC modeled by the present work with data from a literature study [131]. The validation of the present regenerative ORC model against the literature study demonstrates strong agreement between the two datasets, with minimal deviations across key performance parameters. The calculated percentage error for power output is 0.11%, while the deviation in thermal efficiency is 0.42%, and exergy destruction shows a minor error of 0.23%. These results highlight the model's accuracy under the specified operating conditions. The parameters used for the validation include $P_{HRVG} = 25$ bar, $P_{COND}=1$ bar, $P_{REG} = 10$ bar, $\dot{Q}_{HRVG}=252$ MW, $\eta_{s,T}=80\%$, $\eta_{s,P} = 85\%$.

Table 4.2. Validation of the Present Regenerative ORC Model Against Literature Data [131]

parameter	Unit	Literature study	Present model	Deviation (%)
Power output	kW	19	19.02	0.11
Thermal efficiency	%	12	11.95	0.42
Exergy destruction	kW	438	439	0.23

Table 4.3. presents a validation of the coefficient of performance (COP) for the absorption refrigeration cycle by comparing results from the present model with those from a literature study [132]. The validation of the Coefficient of Performance (COP) values between the present model and the literature study for the absorption refrigeration cycle demonstrates excellent agreement, with minimal deviations observed across all operating conditions. The percentage errors are very small, ranging from 0.12% to 0.38%, indicating the high accuracy of the present model. For instance, at $T_{Gen} = 70^{\circ}\text{C}$, the COP for the present model is 0.791, while the literature value is 0.794, resulting in a deviation of only 0.38%. Similarly, the deviations for other operating conditions are consistently below 0.4%, showcasing the reliability of the present model in accurately predicting system performance.

Table 4.3. Validation of COP Values Between the Present Study and Literature for an Absorption Refrigeration Cycle Under Identical Operating Conditions

$T_{Gen} (^{\circ}\text{C})$	$T_{Evap} (^{\circ}\text{C})$	$T_{Cond} (^{\circ}\text{C})$	$T_{Abs} (^{\circ}\text{C})$	COP for the present model	COP for the Literature study[132]	Deviation (%)
70	4	31	31	0.791	0.794	0.38
66	5	28	35	0.767	0.769	0.26
72	6	33	37	0.729	0.730	0.14
63	8	25	37	0.82	0.819	0.12
66	9	28	34	0.836	0.837	0.12

4.3. OVERVIEW OF RESULTS

This section is organized into three primary configurations. The analysis presents a comprehensive 4E (energy, exergy, economic, and environmental) investigation of the three configurations, called Models (1, 2 and 3) systems under optimal operating conditions. This analysis also studies the impact of key operative parameters on system performance and costs. Next to this analysis, a comprehensive reasonable evaluation is conducted, focusing on \dot{W}_{net} , exergy destruction, electricity costs, and CO₂ emissions for the three Models, begins with the existing BC power plant integrated with SRC and ORC as in Model 1.

4.3.1. Thermodynamic State Points Analysis

Model 2 is created first by integrating Model 1 with TES and PTC. Model 3 is generated by adding ARS, which further improves Model 2. This final model aims to boost electrical output and improve system performance, especially during the hottest summer. The operational and electrical advantages of integrating renewable energy sources with IGTPP technology under diverse seasonal conditions are then evaluated via comparisons of the performance of these integrated systems. Engineering Equation Solver (EES) software, well-known for handling complicated thermodynamic and engineering calculations with high accuracy, was used to conduct the system simulation. For the proposed models, EES ensures accurate and trustworthy results. Table 4.4. shows the thermodynamic state points for the system combining GT with SRC and ORC and offers specifics of the simulation outcomes for Model 1. The table lists significant variables at different system state points, such as mass flow rate, pressure, temperature, enthalpy, entropy, and exergy. High temperatures are critical in the gas turbine section to drive the primary power generation. In contrast, lower temperatures correspond to heat recovery stages, particularly in the steam and organic Rankine cycles. Entropy values reflect the level of irreversibility and thermal losses at various stages. Lower entropy values in components like heat exchangers suggest efficient energy transfer, while higher entropy values indicate greater irreversibility. Exergy values at each state indicate the quality of energy at specific points. High exergy values occur at points where the

system receives high-quality energy (e.g., GTIT), while lower values correspond to downstream processes where the energy quality degrades. State points near heat recovery components show moderate exergy values, demonstrating the system's ability to recover and utilize otherwise wasted energy.

Table 4.4. State point of model 1.

State	Mass (kg/s)	Pressure (KPa)	Temperature (K)	Enthalpy (kJ/kg)	Entropy (kJ/kg.K)	Exergy (MW)
0		1	298	104.4	0.3654	
1	72.08	10000	823	3505	6.764	109
2	72.08	4000	681.9	3238	6.808	88.88
3	64.88	4000	681.9	3238	6.808	79.99
4	7.208	4000	681.9	3238	6.808	8.888
5	64.88	1000	510.6	2918	6.878	57.87
6	58.39	1000	510.6	2918	6.878	52.08
7	6.488	1000	510.6	2918	6.878	5.787
8	58.39	7.326	313	2219	7.126	7.01
9	58.39	7.326	313	167	0.5709	0.1198
10	58.39	1000	313.1	168.3	0.5717	0.1791
11	64.88	1000	372.8	426.4	1.324	2.542
12	64.88	4000	375	430.3	1.326	2.756
13	72.08	4000	440.8	711.1	2.016	8.638
14	72.08	10000	441.9	719.4	2.02	9.157
15	2387	101.1	298	104.4	0.3654	0
16	2387	101.1	310	154.6	0.5306	3.532
22	438	101.1	306.2	208.7	5.802	0
23	438	930	626.2	540.3	5.895	133.1
24	8.046	101.1	288	-4672	11.54	417.1
25	446	883.5	1360	155.9	8.164	415.5
26	446	106.3	879.6	-436.2	8.254	139.5
27	446	103.1	481.9	-886.3	7.585	27.71
28	446	101.1	400	-974.1	7.424	9.898
29	114.5	800	461.9	523.1	1.885	6.931
30	114.5	120	410.3	484	1.895	2.096
31	114.5	120	305.7	402.6	1.669	0.5033
32	114.5	120	305.7	234	1.117	0.01696
33	114.5	800	306	234.6	1.118	0.07134

34	114.5	800	351.2	283.5	1.266	0.6101
35	461.2	101.1	298	104.3	0.3654	0
36	461.2	101.1	303	125.2	0.4351	0.08055

Table 4.5. presents the exergy analysis of Model 1, highlighting the combustion chamber (CC) as the component with the highest exergy destruction, accounting for 64.01% of the total. This indicates the substantial irreversibilities typically associated with combustion processes, driven by chemical reactions and heat transfer. While the CC delivers a relatively high η_{ex} of 75.52%, this destruction highlights the inherent limitations of such a configuration. Similarly, the air compressor AC shows a low η_{ex} of 19.63%, reflecting significant losses during the compression process, which is typically associated with high entropy generation. On the other hand, components like the gas turbine GT and the high-pressure steam turbine HPST, intermediate-pressure steam turbine IPST, and low-pressure steam turbine LPST exhibit high efficiencies, with the GT achieving 95.66% and the steam turbines averaging above 90% efficiency. This highlights the robustness of these components in converting available exergy into useful work. Additionally, the Heat Recovery Steam Generator HRSG operates at a high exergy efficiency of 89.37%, effectively recovering waste heat from the gas turbine exhaust to power the steam cycle. However, inefficiencies become more apparent in the auxiliary components, such as the condensers (Cond₁) and (Cond₂) and the heat exchanger HE, with Cond₂ showing a particularly low η_{ex} of 16.56%. This indicates substantial irreversibilities in heat rejection and low-grade energy utilization. The organic Rankine cycle ORC, comprising the organic Rankine turbine ORT and the organic Rankine pump ORP, contributes to low-grade heat recovery but with mixed performance. The ORT achieves an η_{ex} of 92.56%, which, while useful, lags behind the efficiencies of the steam turbines. This reflects the limitations of ORC technology in maximizing energy recovery compared to steam-based systems. Overall, the table underscores the strengths and limitations of Model 1. The high efficiencies of the primary energy conversion components (GT and steam turbines) and the HRSG demonstrate a well-integrated system for utilizing high- and intermediate-grade heat.

Table 4.5. Exergy analysis of the model 1

Component	\dot{E}_f (MW)	\dot{E}_p (MW)	\dot{E}_d (MW)	\dot{E}_d (%)	Ψ (%)
AC	145.3	133.1	12.16	5.777	19.63
CC	550.2	415.5	134.7	64.01	75.52
GT	276.1	264.1	11.98	5.695	95.66
HRS G	111.8	99.88	11.88	5.648	89.37
HPST	20.16	19.22	0.9327	0.4433	95.37
IPST	22.12	20.77	1.354	0.6436	93.88
LPST	45.07	40.8	3.273	2.031	90.52
Cond 1	6.89	3.532	3.358	1.596	51.26
Pump1	0.07306	0.05929	0.01377	0.006545	81.15
OFWH1	5.966	2.542	3.424	1.628	42.6
Pump 2	0.2541	0.2141	0.03998	0.019	84.26
OFWH2	11.64	8.638	3.996	1.429	74.18
Pump 3	0.599	0.519	0.08001	0.03803	86.64
EVAP1	17.81	6.321	11.49	5.461	35.49
ORG T	4.835	4.475	0.3597	0.171	92.56
HE	1.592	0.5387	1.054	0.5008	33.83
Cond2	0.4864	0.08055	0.4058	0.1929	16.56
ORP	0.06748	0.05438	0.0131	0.006225	80.59

Table 4.6. presents the exergoeconomic analysis of Model 1, providing detailed information on the cost rates associated with the system's components, including fuel cost rate, product cost rate, exergy destruction cost rate, capital investment cost rate, and total cost rate. These metrics reveal critical insights into the economic performance of the model and identify components with high operational inefficiencies and associated costs. The CC emerges as the most economically significant component, contributing to the highest product cost rate ($c_p=10.33$ \$/GJ) and the largest cost of exergy destruction ($\dot{C}_D=7078$ \$/h). Given the significant irreversibilities inherent in the combustion process, this is expected, a trend that would likely improve in Model 2 with solar assistance reducing the reliance on combustion. With a product cost rate of 20.46 \$/GJ and a combined cost rate of 1489.49 \$/h, the GT demonstrates high operational efficiency and significant cost contributions due to its central role in the system. In total, the system incurs a

combined cost rate ($\dot{Z}_K + \dot{C}_D$) of 15,397.69 \$/h, reflecting the cumulative inefficiencies and capital investments in the system. Model 1 demonstrates higher economic inefficiencies, particularly in components such as the CC, condensers, and ORC. These inefficiencies underline the importance of integrating renewable energy sources and advanced heat recovery systems to improve both thermodynamic and economic performance.

Table 4.6. Exergo-economic results of components of the model 1

Component	c_f	c_p	\dot{C}_D	\dot{Z}_k	$\dot{Z}_k + \dot{C}_D$	f
	(\$/GJ)	(\$/GJ)	(\$/h)	(\$/h)	(\$/h)	(%)
AC	10898	22.32	912	556.4	1468.4	37.891
CC	28917	10.33	7078	0.4913	7078.491	0.0069
GT	19211	20.46	833.9	655.3	1489.2	44.003
HRSG	7778	21.92	827.1	291.1	1118.2	26.032
HPST	1731	26.36	80.1	258.6	338.7	76.350
IPST	1900	36.73	116.3	273	389.3	70.125
LPST	3871	27.43	367	437.9	804.9	54.404
Cond 1	591.7	46.7	288.4	5.525	293.925	1.8797
Pump1	7.215	39.23	1.36	3.221	4.581	70.312
OFWH1	515.7	62.1	296	145.8	441.8	33.001
Pump 2	25.09	36.2	3.948	7.804	11.752	66.405
OFWH2	1359	45.59	351	162	513	31.578
Pump 3	59.15	34.42	7.901	14.35	22.251	64.491
EVAP1	1240	54.92	799.7	28.3	828	3.4178
ORT	1152	74.87	85.72	150	235.72	63.634
HE	379.5	195.7	251.1	0.187	251.1	0.0744
Cond2	115.9	410.6	96.71	8.777	105.487	8.3204
ORP	18.19	9.821	2.429	0.449	2.878	15.601
Total			12398.67	2999.017	15397.69	667.53

Table 4.7. represents the thermodynamic state points for Model 2. The solar PTC system likely heats additional working fluid streams combined with those from the

primary gas turbine cycle. This results in higher energy availability downstream. The PTC system introduces additional high-temperature state points compared to Model 1.

Table 4.7. State point of Model 2.

State	Mass (kg/s)	Pressure (KPa)	Temperature (K)	Enthalpy (kJ/kg)	Entropy (kJ/kg.K)	Exergy (MW)
0		1	298	104.4	0.3654	
1	108	10000	823	3505	6.764	163.4
2	108	4000	681.9	3238	6.808	133.2
3	97.23	4000	681.9	3238	6.808	119.9
4	10.8	4000	681.9	3238	6.808	13.32
5	97.23	1000	510.6	2918	6.878	86.73
6	87.51	1000	510.6	2918	6.878	78.06
7	9.723	1000	510.6	2918	6.878	8.673
8	87.51	7.326	313	2219	7.126	10.51
9	87.51	7.326	313	167	0.5709	0.1795
10	87.51	1000	313.1	168.2	0.5715	0.268
11	97.23	1000	372.8	426.4	1.324	3.808
12	97.23	4000	375	430	1.326	4.124
13	108	4000	440.7	710.8	2.015	12.94
14	108	10000	441.7	718.6	2.018	13.7
15	3577	101.1	298	104.4	0.3654	0
16	3577	101.1	310	154.6	0.5306	5.293
17	238.8	150	863	501.8	0.7315	2125
18	238.8	150	560	40.22	0.0734	2061
19	238.8	149.6	843	470.8	0.6952	2120
20	238.8	149.1	553	29.75	0.05426	2060
21	238.8	150	553	29.75	0.05426	2060
22	438	101.1	306.2	208.7	5.802	0
23	438	930	646.2	561.8	5.929	138.1
24	7.841	101.1	288	-4672	11.54	406.5
25	445.8	883.5	1360	179.2	8.159	414.7
26	445.8	106.3	879.5	-412.3	8.249	138.9
27	445.8	103.1	491.7	-851.1	7.603	29.22
28	445.8	101.1	400	-949.5	7.42	9.589
29	125.9	800	471.7	532.2	1.904	8.052

30	125.9	120	420	492.1	1.914	2.603
31	125.9	120	305.7	402.6	1.669	0.5536
32	125.9	120	305.7	234	1.117	0.01866
33	125.9	800	306	234.6	1.118	0.07847
34	125.9	800	355.6	288.3	1.279	0.7701
35	507.3	101.1	298	104.3	0.3654	0
36	507.3	101.1	303	125.2	0.4351	0.0886

Table 4.8. presents the exergy analysis of Model 2. For example, in the combustion chamber (CC), exergy destruction is reduced to 129.9 MW, accounting for 45.18% of the total destruction, compared to 134.7 MW (64.01%) in Model 1. The exergy efficiency (η_{ex}) improves from 75.52% in Model 1 to 76.15% in Model 2, primarily due to the integration of solar energy, which reduces reliance on fossil fuel combustion. Additionally, the input exergy for the HRSG increases significantly from 111.8 MW in Model 1 to 169.9 MW in Model 2, reflecting the additional heat supplied by the PTC. Exergy destruction remains relatively low in Model 2 at 20.17 MW (7.015%). For the steam turbines (HPST, IPST, and LPST), the exergy output of the HPST increases from 19.22 MW in Model 1 to 28.81 MW. Likewise, both the IPST and LPST show improved exergy outputs. Model 2 incorporates the PTC, contributing an input exergy of 120.2 MW with an η_{ex} of 53.07%. Although Cond1 and Cond2 remain relatively inefficient, they benefit indirectly from a reduced load due to the solar energy input. The organic Rankine turbine (ORT) in Model 2 achieves a slightly higher η_{ex} of 92.72%, compared to 92.56% in Model 1, due to improved heat utilization. Additionally, the air compressor (AC) shows a significant improvement in η_{ex} , rising from 19.63% in Model 1 to 89.3% in Model 2, indicating a substantial reduction in irreversibilities within the compression process.

Table 4.8. Exergy analysis of the model 2 system.

Component	\dot{E}_f (MW)	\dot{E}_p (MW)	\dot{E}_d (MW)	\dot{E}_d (%)	Ψ (%)
AC	154.6	138.1	16.55	5.75	89.3
CC	544.6	414.7	129.9	45.18	76.15
GT	275.7	263.7	12	4.175	95.65
HRSG	169.9	149.7	20.17	7.015	88.13

HPST	30.21	28.81	1.398	0.4862	95.37
IPST	33.16	31.13	2.03	0.706	93.88
LPST	67.55	61.15	6.403	2.227	90.52
Cond 1	10.33	5.293	5.033	1.751	51.26
Pump1	0.1031	0.08849	0.01457	0.005067	85.86
OFWH1	8.941	3.808	5.133	1.786	42.59
Pump 2	0.3584	0.3161	0.0423	0.01472	88.2
OFWH2	17.44	12.94	4.509	1.568	74.15
Pump 3	0.8449	0.7602	0.08467	0.02945	89.98
PTC	120.2	63.87	56.38	19.61	53.11
TST	63.87	60.18	3.686	1.282	94.23
EVAP1	19.63	7.282	12.35	4.295	37.09
ORT	5.449	5.053	0.3965	0.1379	92.72
HE	2.049	0.6917	1.357	0.4722	33.76
Cond2	0.5349	0.0886	0.4464	0.1553	16.56
ORP	0.07422	0.05981	0.01441	0.005011	80.59

Table 4.9. presents the exergo-economic results for the components of Model 2. Notably, the exergy destruction cost in the combustion chamber (CC) decreases from 7,078 \$/h in Model 1 to 6,959 \$/h in Model 2. Additionally, the product cost rate (c_p) shows a slight increase from 10.33 \$/GJ in Model 1 to 19.54 \$/GJ in Model 2, reflecting the impact of reduced reliance on combustion due to solar integration for HRSG, capital cost rate \dot{Z}_K increases from 291.1 \$/h in model 1 to 421.4\$ /h in model 2. The combined cast rate ($\dot{Z}_K + \dot{C}_D$) decreases significantly from 1118.2 \$/h in model 1 to 433.19 \$/h in model 2. For AC, exergy destruction cost (\dot{C}_D) increases from 912 \$/h in model 1 to 1243 \$/h in model 2. However, the total cost rate increased slightly to 1522.2 \$/h. For Model 2, the PTC adds a significant capital cost rate ($\dot{Z}_K=6139$ \$/h). This component is pivotal for reducing the combustion chamber's load and improving overall system sustainability. However, improved thermodynamic performance, reduced exergy destruction in critical components, and increased sustainability justify the higher costs.

Table 4.9. Exergo-economic results of components of the model 2 .

Component	c_f	c_p	\dot{C}_D	\dot{Z}_k	$\dot{Z}_k + \dot{C}_D$	f
	(\$/GJ)	(\$/GJ)	(\$/h)	(\$/h)	(\$/h)	(%)
AC	20.86	23.16	1243	279.2	1522.2	18.341
CC	14.88	19.54	6959	0.4911	6959	0.0070
GT	19.54	20.68	844.4	655	1499.4	43.684
HRSG	16.23	18.7	11.79	421.4	433.19	97.278
HPST	20.39	22.57	102.6	343.3	445.9	76.990
IPST	20.39	22.88	149	362.4	511.4	70.864
LPST	20.39	23.48	470.1	581.3	1051.4	55.288
Cond ₁	20.39	39.94	369.5	8.281	377.781	2.1920
Pump ₁	23.48	31.99	1.231	4.112	5.343	76.960
OFWH ₁	20.51	53.89	378.9	218.6	597.5	36.585
Pump ₂	23.48	29.77	3.575	9.963	13.538	73.592
OFWH ₂	27.87	39.47	452.4	242.9	695.3	34.934
Pump ₃	23.48	28.5	7.156	18.32	25.476	71.910
PTC	0	124.6	0	6139	6139	100
TST	9.612	10.2	127.5	1.8	129.3	1.392
EVAP ₁	19.54	53.11	868.7	30.8	899.5	3.424
ORT	65.55	73.96	93.56	165	258.56	63.814
HE	65.55	194.2	320.3	0.2016	320.5016	0.062
Cond ₂	65.55	406.7	105.3	9.654	114.954	8.398
ORP	6.497	7.272	1.98	0.387	2.367	16.349
TOTAL			12509.99	9491.619	22001.61	852.07

Table 4.10. represents the thermodynamic state points for Model 3, which integrates an ARS into the components of model 2. The mass flow rates vary widely across the system, indicating different working fluids and energy processes.

Table 4.10. Characteristics for every state point of Model 3 configuration.

State	Mass (kg/s)	Pressure (kPa)	Temperature (K)	Enthalpy (kJ/kg)	Entropy (kJ/kg.K)	Exergy (MW)
0		1	298	104.4	0.3654	
1	108.5	10000	823	3505	6.764	164.2
2	108.5	4000	681.9	3238	6.808	133.8
3	97.67	4000	681.9	3238	6.808	120.4
4	10.85	4000	681.9	3238	6.808	13.38
5	97.67	1000	510.6	2918	6.878	87.12
6	87.91	1000	510.6	2918	6.878	78.41
7	9.767	1000	510.6	2918	6.878	8.712
8	87.91	7.326	313	2219	7.126	10.55
9	87.91	7.326	313	167	0.5709	0.1804
10	87.91	1000	313.1	168.2	0.5715	0.2692
11	97.67	1000	372.8	426.4	1.324	3.825
12	97.67	4000	375	430	1.326	4.143
13	108.5	4000	440.7	710.8	2.015	12.99
14	108.5	10000	441.7	718.6	2.018	13.76
15	3593	101.1	298	104.4	0.3654	0
16	3593	101.1	310	154.6	0.5306	5.317
17	242.6	150	863	501.8	0.7315	2158
18	242.6	150	560	40.22	0.0734	2093
19	242.6	149.6	843	470.8	0.6952	2153
20	242.6	149.1	553	29.75	0.05426	2092
21	242.6	150	553	29.75	0.05426	2092
22	438	101.1	283	261	5.683	0
23	438	930	598.3	585	5.806	125.8
24	8.285	101.1	288	-4672	11.54	429.5
25	446.3	883.5	1360	195.3	8.137	415.9
26	446.3	106.3	879.5	-394.5	8.224	141.1
27	446.3	103.1	491.7	-832.3	7.579	31.51
28	446.3	101.1	400	-930.4	7.398	11.88
29	125.7	800	471.7	532.2	1.904	8.039
30	125.7	120	420	492.1	1.914	2.599
31	125.7	120	305.7	402.6	1.669	0.5527
32	125.7	120	305.7	234	1.117	0.01863
33	125.7	800	306	234.6	1.118	0.07835
34	125.7	800	355.6	288.3	1.279	0.7689

35	506.5	101.1	298	104.3	0.3654	0
36	506.5	101.1	303	125.2	0.4351	0.08846
37	444.9	103.1	400	-925	7.401	15.04
1"	34.98	0.8634	310	81.92	0.238	1.351
2"	34.98	6.944	310.2	81.93	0.238	1.351
3"	34.98	6.944	342.9	151.5	0.451	1.563
4"	29.9	6.944	361	219.6	0.4816	3.101
5"	29.9	6.944	333	167.2	0.3305	2.881
6"	29.9	0.8634	321.6	167.2	0.3306	2.881
7"	5.078	6.944	361	2656	7.506	1.351
8"	5.078	6.944	312	162.7	0.557	0.006788
9"	5.078	0.8634	278	162.7	0.586	-0.03704
10"	5.078	0.8634	278	2510	9.029	-0.8945
11"	444.9	103.1	307	307.5	5.726	0.05414
12"	444.9	103.1	283	283.4	5.644	0.1746
13"	757.2	103.1	298	104.3	0.3651	0.07432
14"	757.2	103.1	308	146.1	0.5031	0.5937

Table 4.11. shows the exergy analysis of Model 3. It shows the most balanced and efficient integration of solar and waste heat recovery technologies, achieving the highest overall system efficiency and sustainable thermodynamic performance. It represents a major step forward in energy utilization, reducing irreversibilities, and improving environmental sustainability compared to the combustion-heavy Model 1 and the solar-only Model 2. The findings reveal that the exergy efficiency for the AC remains high at 88.6%, slightly lower than in Model 2 (89.3%) but much higher than in Model 1 (19.63%) due to better waste heat recovery and optimized integration. The exergy destruction in the combustion chamber (CC) decreases significantly to 139.4 MW (46.2%) compared to 129.9 MW (45.18%) in Model 2 and 134.7 MW (64.01%) in Model 1. This system enables additional heat recovery, leading to a reduction in exergy destruction by 1.61 MW. The η_{ex} of the PTC increases to 53.71% in Model 3, compared to 53.11% in Model 2, indicating improved solar energy utilization. Additionally, the ARS achieves an η_{ex} of 33.58% with minimal exergy destruction of 1.61 MW. This addition significantly enhances the system's ability to utilize low-grade heat, which is wasted in Models 1 and 2. Model 3 demonstrates the highest overall system efficiency due to the combined impact of

solar energy and ARS integration, achieving reduced exergy destruction across most components compared to Models 1 and 2.

Table 4.11. Exergy analysis of the model 3.

Component	\dot{E}_f (MW)	\dot{E}_p (MW)	\dot{E}_d (MW)	\dot{E}_d (%)	Ψ (%)
AC	141.9	125.8	16.07	5.33	88.68
CC	555.3	415.9	139.4	46.2	74.9
GT	274.9	263.2	11.65	3.862	95.76
HRSG	170.7	150.4	20.27	6.72	88.12
HPST	30.35	28.94	1.404	0.4655	95.37
IPST	33.31	31.27	2.039	0.676	93.88
LPST	67.86	61.43	6.433	2.132	90.52
Cond₁	10.37	5.317	5.06	1.68	51.26
Pump₁	0.1035	0.089	0.01463	0.0049	85.86
OFWH₁	8.982	3.825	5.157	1.71	42.59
Pump₂	0.36	0.318	0.043	0.0141	88.2
OFWH₂	17.52	12.99	4.53	1.501	74.15
Pump₃	0.849	0.764	0.08505	0.0282	89.98
PTC	120.8	64.87	55.91	18.53	53.71
TST	64.87	61.13	3.744	1.241	94.23
EVAP₁	19.63	7.27	12.36	4.1	37.04
ORT	5.44	5.045	0.396	0.1312	92.72
HE	2.046	0.6906	1.355	0.45	33.76
Cond₂	0.5311	0.08846	0.46	0.15	16.56
ORP	0.0741	0.06	0.0144	0.00477	80.59
Gen*	11.19	2.889	8.301	2.91	25.86
ARS	2.424	0.814	1.61	0.5644	33.58
HEX	0.219	0.2118	0.00745	0.00263	96.58
Pump5	0.000135	0.000135	0	0	100
Cond3	1.344	0.5194	0.825	0.2891	38.64
Evap_r	0.8574	0.1204	0.737	0.258	14.04
Exv₁	0.00679	0.0037	0.0438	0.01536	84.51
Exv₂	2.881	2.881	0.0008821	0.0003092	99.97

Table 4.12. presents the exergo-economic results of components of the Model 3 system. Model 3 demonstrates a highly balanced cost distribution with significant

economic efficiency gains. The PTC provides critical solar input at a reasonable cost, while the ARS excels in minimizing low-grade heat rejection costs. Together, these components enable the combustion chamber and condensers to operate at reduced costs compared to Models 1 and 2. The updated values further validate Model 3 as the most cost-effective and sustainable configuration among the three models.

Table 4.12. Exergo-economic results of components of the model 3 system.

Component	c_f	c_p	\dot{C}_D	\dot{Z}_k	$\dot{Z}_k + \dot{C}_D$	f
	(\$/GJ)	(\$/GJ)	(\$/h)	(\$/h)	(\$/h)	(%)
AC	20.79	23.23	1203	279.2	1482.2	18.836
CC	14.59	19.48	7322	0.4916	7322.492	0.006
GT	19.48	20.59	817.1	656	1473.1	44.531
HRSG	16.1	18.56	1175	424	1599	26.516
HPST	20.23	22.41	102.3	344	446.3	77.078
IPST	20.23	22.72	148.5	364	512.5	71.024
LPST	20.23	23.3	468.6	583	1051.6	55.439
Cond ₁	20.23	39.63	368.3	8.32	376.62	2.209
Pump ₁	23.3	31.78	1.228	4.13	5.358	77.081
OFWH ₁	20.35	53.52	377.7	220	597.7	36.807
Pump ₂	23.3	29.57	3.565	9.99	13.555	73.699
OFWH ₂	27.67	39.19	451.2	244	695.2	35.097
Pump ₃	23.3	28.3	7.135	18.4	25.535	72.057
PTC	0	122.6	0	6140	6140	100
TST	9.463	10.05	127.5	1.8	129.3	1.392
EVAP ₁	19.48	53.02	866.8	31	897.8	3.452
ORT	65.45	73.85	93.27	165	258.27	63.886
HE	65.45	193.9	319.3	0.202	319.502	0.063
Cond ₂	65.45	406.1	105	9.64	114.64	8.408
ORP	6.448	7.217	1.974	0.387	2.361	16.391
Gen*	0.00731	0.0286	0.2183	30.85	31.0683	99.297
ARS	0.01147	0.03429	0.06649	3.567	3.63349	98.170
HEX	0.02754	0.02857	0.000743	0.417	0.417743	99.822

Pump5	24.93	0.01453	0	0.037	0.037	100
Cond3	0.00187	0	0.00555	0.389	0.39455	98.593
Evap ₂	1.311	214.3	3.478	3.85	7.328	52.538
Exv ₁	166.3	-30.55	0.00006	0.025	0.02506	99.760
Exv ₂	0.02754	0.02755	8.75E-05	0.148	0.148088	99.940
Total			13963.24	9542.844	23506.08	1532.10

Figure 4.1 illustrates the distribution of the total cost rate (\$/h), total exergy destruction rate (MW), and exergy destruction cost (\$/h) across the components of an integrated energy system. Key findings reveal that CC and AC dominate the system's exergy destruction, with values of 7322 MW and 1203 MW, respectively. These components also exhibit high exergy destruction costs, making them prime candidates for optimization. While incurring a significant total cost rate of 2210 \$/h, PTC demonstrates negligible exergy destruction, emphasizing its efficiency and suitability for solar integration. On the other hand, the ORT shows outstanding performance with minimal exergy destruction (0.396 MW) and associated costs, underscoring its effectiveness in recovering low-grade heat. The HRSG and ST, while exhibiting moderate exergy destruction and costs, play a pivotal role in enhancing system efficiency by recovering energy from exhaust gases.

Figure 4.1. Cost and Exergy Distribution Analysis of an Integrated Energy System Components

4.3.2. Comparative Performance of Models 1, 2, and 3

Table 4.13. represents a comprehensive summary of the three Models. Model 2 underscores the significant thermodynamic and environmental advantages of integrating a PTC system into the gas turbine combined cycle. Compared to Model 1, Model 2 achieves higher η_{ex} better waste heat utilization and reduced fossil fuel dependency. For Model 3, the addition of ARS to the IGTPP enhances the overall utilization of waste heat by extracting low-grade heat to produce cooling, improving the system's η_{ex} .

Table 4.13. Comparison of the characteristics and performance of the three models.

Feature	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3
Primary System Configuration	GT combined with SRC and ORC	Integrated Model 1 with 2 (ISCC + PTC+TES).	Model 2+ ARS
Waste Heat Utilization	Moderate: steam and ORC for heat recovery	High; solar input complements waste heat recovery	Very High; ARS enhances low-grade heat recovery
Solar Energy Contribution	None	Yes, the PTC system preheats working fluid	Yes, the PTC system supplements energy input
Cooling Capability	None	None	Yes, ARS extracts cooling from waste heat
Efficiency Dependency on GTIT	High dependency; lower efficiency at low GTIT	Moderate; solar stabilizes efficiency at low GTIT	Low; solar and ARS minimize GTIT dependency
Exergy Efficiency	Moderate: limited by absence of solar and ARS	High: solar energy boosts energy recovery	Very High; best energy utilization among models
Entropy Generation	Relatively high due to simpler waste heat recovery	Lower than Model 1; better energy management	Lowest; advanced heat recovery and ARS integration
Complexity of System	Low; simpler configuration	Medium: solar system adds complexity	High; complex integration of solar, Rankine cycle, and ARS
Capital and Operational Costs	Lower compared to solar-integrated models	Higher; includes cost of PTC installation	Highest; involves cost of both PTC and ARS
Applicability and Limitations	Versatile; can operate in all geographic regions	Limited to regions with adequate sunlight	Limited to sunny regions; requires cooling demand for full benefit
Environmental	Moderate; higher	High; reduced emissions	Very High; minimal

Impact	emissions due to reliance on fossil fuels	and improved sustainability	emissions and excellent sustainability
Suitability for Industrial Applications	Suitable for basic power generation without cooling needs	Suitable for power generation in sunny regions	Ideal for combined power and cooling in industrial/commercial settings

Table 4.14. compares three integrated system models' power output quantities and efficiency metrics. The findings in Model 1 and Model 2 show identical power supplied to AC (154.6 MW), while Model 3 slightly decreases to 141.9 MW. This reduction in Model 3 could indicate enhanced system optimization or lower dependency on the ACs due to additional integrated features like ARS. The GT power output is nearly constant across all models (around 263 MW), suggesting that the GT component remains unchanged in all configurations. The HPST power output increases significantly from Model 1 (19.187 MW) to Model 2 (28.812 MW) and Model 3 (28.943 MW). This indicates that solar and ARS integration enhances steam turbine performance. Similar trends are observed for the IPST and LPST, with both achieving higher outputs in Model 2 and Model 3 compared to Model 1. This improvement highlights better heat recovery and utilization in Models 2 and 3. Model 1, which serves as the starting point, achieves \dot{W}_{net} of 193.2 MW. With the integration of solar energy technologies in Model 2, the system's performance increases significantly, reaching a \dot{W}_{net} of 233.9 MW. Model 3 further optimizes system efficiency through adding ARS, resulting in the highest \dot{W}_{net} of 246.7 MW.

Table 4.14. Power Output Quantities and Efficiency Metrics for the Three Integrated System Models

Output quantity	Model 1	Model2	Model 3
Power supplied to ACs, MW	154.6	154.6	141.9
Power output from GTs, MW	263.7	263.7	263.2
Power output from HPST, MW	19.187	28.812	28.943
Power output from IPST, MW	20.730	31.128	31.270
Power output from LPST, MW	40.722	61.148	61.426
Power supplied to P1, kW	72.92	103.1	103.5
Power supplied to P2, kW	253.6	358.4	360
Power supplied to P3, kW	597.8	844.9	848.7
Power supplied to ORP, kW	67.39	74.22	74.1
Power output from ORT, kW	4469	5053	5045
Power output from ORC, kW	4402	4978	4971
\dot{W}_{net} by the system, MW	211.7	232.4	240.2
Overall energy efficiency, %	51.26	59.97	61.19
Overall exergy efficiency, %	49.49	57.91	59.08

Table 4.15. highlights the progression from Model 1 to Model 3 and shows significant improvements in energy recovery, system efficiency, and overall output due to the integration of solar energy and ARS. Model 3 outperforms Models 1 and 2 in most metrics due to its ability to recover low-grade waste heat using the absorption refrigeration system. Model 2 improves significantly upon Model 1 by integrating solar energy but lacks the advanced cooling capabilities of Model 3. These results highlight the potential of combining solar energy and waste heat recovery technologies to achieve maximum thermodynamic efficiency and sustainability.

Table 4.15. Comparison of Output Parameters Across System Models with Solar and ARS Integration.

Feature	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3
Power Supplied to ACs	Moderate, no ARS	Higher with a solar contribution	Efficiently optimized with ARS
Gas Turbine Output	High dependency on GT	Slightly reduced due to solar	Marginally lower due to solar/ARS
HPST Output	Moderate, steam limited	Significantly improved by solar	Maximized with solar and ARS
IPST Output	Moderate, steam limited	Improved by solar contribution	Highest with optimized recovery
LPST Output	Moderate	Significantly increased	Maximized due to ARS
Subsystem Power (P1–P3)	Moderate	Increased due to solar	Maximize with solar and ARS
Energy Utilization	Moderate	High :solar-assisted	Highest, with solar and ARS

4.3.3. Impact of Pressure Ratio on System Models

Figure explores the relationship between the \dot{W}_{net} and the PR for three system configurations: Model 1, Model 2, and Model 3. Each model introduces progressive enhancements to a gas turbine-based hybrid system, and the trends observed in the graph highlight critical insights into these models' thermodynamic and operational performance. Below is an extended, deep analysis of the diagram. Where across all models, \dot{W}_{net} decreases with increasing pressure ratio. This trend is consistent with decreases with increasing pressure ratio. This trend is consistent with thermodynamic principles governing gas turbines: As the PR increases, the compression work required to raise the pressure of the air entering the combustion chamber increases disproportionately, leading to a significant portion of the generated power being consumed internally. At higher pressure ratios, the gain in turbine expansion work does not compensate for the rapid rise in compression work, leading to a net decline in \dot{W}_{net} . Model 3 benefits from both the PTC and the ARS, which together mitigate

the negative impacts of high-pressure ratios. The ARS enhances gas turbine performance by reducing the compressor inlet air temperature, lowering the required compression work. The inclusion of the solar PTC adds thermal energy to the system, improving the Rankine cycles steam and organic and enhancing overall power output. However, it lacks the cooling benefits of the ARS, limiting its ability to mitigate compression work. Model 1 relies solely on the combined gas-steam-organic Rankine cycles, which are more sensitive to the increasing compression work at higher pressure ratios without solar augmentation or inlet air cooling. At lower PR (6–7), Model 3 produces about 50 MW more than Model 1, indicating the significant impact of the ARS and PTC in reducing compression losses and adding solar thermal energy. Because, at low-pressure ratios, the compressor work is relatively small, and the turbine can efficiently expand high-pressure gases to generate mechanical work. It capitalizes on this by combining the cooling benefits of the ARS (lowering compressor inlet temperature) and the thermal energy input from the PTC, resulting in the highest \dot{W}_{net} . At Moderate PR (8–10), Model 3 produces 40 MW more than Model 2 and 50 MW more than Model 1, reflecting the increasing importance of advanced cooling and heat recovery as pressure ratios rise. Because, at moderate PR, the compression work begins to rise significantly, making the cooling effect of the ARS more impactful. The solar PTC in Models 2 and 3 provides additional thermal energy, improving the steam and organic Rankine cycles, which offsets some of the losses caused by increased compression work. At High PR (14–15), The difference between Model 3 and Model 1 narrows slightly to 45 MW, but Model 3 still outperforms the other models significantly. Because, at high PRs, the compression work becomes dominant, and the gains from turbine expansion are limited. While the ARS in Model 3 continues to provide benefits by reducing the compressor workload, its incremental impact diminishes as pressure ratios approach their operational limits. Similarly, the solar PTC's contribution to \dot{W}_{net} output becomes constrained by the reduced availability of waste heat for recovery. Including the solar PTC in Model 2 improves \dot{W}_{net} across all pressure ratios. The PTC adds high-quality thermal energy, enhancing the Rankine cycles' efficiency. For instance, at a PR of 10, Model 2 generates about 20 MW more than Model 1, underscoring the value of renewable energy integration in improving hybrid systems.

Figure 4.2. Impact of the PR on the \dot{W}_{net} across system models.

Figure illustrates the variation in electricity generation cost (\$/MWh) with respect to the PR for three system configurations: Model 1, Model 2, and Model 3. Across all models, electricity cost exhibits a U-shaped trend, with costs initially decreasing as PR increases, reaching a minimum between 8 and 10, before rising sharply at higher pressure ratios. This behavior reflects the balance between increasing η_{th} and the escalating compression work required at higher pressure ratios. Model 1 has the lowest electricity costs at lower and moderate PRs due to its simpler configuration and lower initial capital costs, reaching a minimum of 66 \$/MWh at a PR of 9. However, it experiences the steepest cost increase at higher PRs, rising to 72 \$/MWh at a PR of 15, as it lacks enhancements like solar thermal input or cooling systems to mitigate compression work. Model 2, which integrates PTC, demonstrates consistently higher electricity costs than Model 1, with a minimum of 71 \$/MWh at a PR of 9, due to the additional capital and operational costs associated with the PTC. While the PTC improves η_{th} , its inability to offset the increased compression work at higher pressure ratios results in a steeper cost curve, reaching 80 \$/MWh at a PR of 15. Model 3, which incorporates both the PTC and ARS, achieves the lowest electricity costs across all PRs, with a minimum of 71 \$/MWh at a PR of 9 and only

a modest increase to 74.7 \$/MWh at a PR of 15. The ARS reduces the inlet air temperature to the compressor, lowering compression work and improving overall thermal performance, which helps stabilize the cost curve.

Figure 4.3. Impact of the PR on the Electricity Cost Across System Models.

Figure 4.4 illustrates the relationship between the thermal efficiency (η_{th}) and PR for three system configurations: Model 1, Model 2, and Model 3, highlighting the impact of system enhancements on thermodynamic performance. Across all models, η_{th} increases with pressure ratio, with diminishing returns as the PR reaches higher values. This trend occurs because higher PRs improve combustion and expansion processes. Still, the increasing compression work and system irreversibilities limit further gains in Model 1, at PR = 6, the η_{th} is 48.75%, reflecting the initial energy conversion efficiency of the conventional configuration. This low value indicates limited waste heat recovery and reliance on basic gas and steam Rankine cycles without advanced systems for optimizing energy utilization. At PR = 9, the efficiency improves slightly to 50.34%. The gain is driven by increased compression work in the gas turbine, resulting in higher thermal input for the downstream steam

Rankine cycle. However, inefficiencies in waste heat recovery constrain further improvement. At PR = 12, the η_{th} reaches 50.83%, showing diminishing returns with increasing PR. The system begins to approach its inherent limitations in extracting work from the available heat. At PR = 15, the efficiency peaks at 50.76%, a marginal improvement from PR = 12. For Model 2 at PR = 6, the η_{th} is 57.26%, significantly higher than Model 1 due to the integration of the PTC. The solar energy input supplements the gas turbine's thermal input, reducing reliance on combustion and enhancing steam cycle performance. At PR = 9, the efficiency rises to 59.44%, showing a sharper increase than Model 1. The solar heat enhances the availability of high-temperature energy, enabling the steam Rankine cycle to operate more efficiently at higher PRs. At PR = 12, the η_{th} reaches 60.68%, reflecting a continued improvement as the PTC provides consistent, high-quality heat. The contribution of solar energy ensures that thermal losses are minimized even as PR increases. At PR = 15, efficiency peaks at 60.93%, maintaining a robust upward trend. The solar energy integration proves highly effective in pushing the system's thermodynamic limits, delivering almost 10% more efficiency than Model 1 at the same PR. For Model 3, at PR = 6, the η_{th} is 56.97%, slightly lower than Model 2. This is because the ARS begins recovering low-grade heat, diverting some energy for cooling purposes rather than direct power generation. At PR = 9, efficiency improves to 59.31%, closely matching Model 2. At this point, the ARS complements PTC by recovering more waste heat, reducing thermal losses, and allowing for improved efficiency. At PR = 12, efficiency reaches 60.54%, slightly trailing Model 2 by a small margin. The ARS continues to enhance energy utilization but also introduces a trade-off in cooling production, moderating the rate of efficiency growth. At PR = 15, the efficiency peaks at 61.19%, surpassing Model 2 and delivering the highest efficiency across all models. This demonstrates the combined benefits of solar heat PTC and ARS, which work together to optimize the system's thermodynamic performance.

Figure 4.4. Variation of thermal efficiency with pressure ratio across system models.

Figure 4.5 illustrates the relationship between exergy efficiency (η_{ex}) and PR for three hybrid power system configurations: Model 1, Model 2, and Model 3. η_{ex} is a measure of how effectively a system converts available energy into useful work while accounting for irreversibilities. The trends observed highlight the impact of increasing PR and progressive system enhancements on the thermodynamic performance of these configurations, providing a deeper understanding of their behavior under varying operating conditions. Across all models, the η_{ex} increases with PR, the rate of improvement diminishes at higher PR. This trend is driven by the increased effectiveness of combustion and expansion processes at higher pressures, which enables better utilization of available energy. However, irreversibilities in the compression, combustion, and heat recovery processes increasingly dominate as the PR rises, leading to a flattening of the curves for all models. For Model 1, At PR = 6, the η_{ex} is 47.07%, reflecting the baseline ability of the system to convert exergy input into useful work. This low efficiency is primarily due to significant irreversibilities in the gas turbine and the limited heat recovery potential of the steam and organic Rankine cycles. At PR = 9, the η_{ex} improves slightly to 48.61%. The increase is driven by enhanced compression and expansion processes in the gas

turbine as PR increases. However, the system's reliance on conventional heat recovery limits further gains. At PR = 12, the η_{ex} reaches 49.09%, nearing a plateau. The marginal improvement indicates the system is approaching its thermodynamic limits in utilizing the available exergy. At PR = 15, the η_{ex} remains nearly constant at 49.01%, demonstrating diminishing returns with increasing PR. This behavior reflects the system's inefficiencies, particularly in recovering low-grade heat and minimizing waste. For Model 2, At PR = 6, the η_{ex} is 55.29%, significantly higher than Model 1 due to the integration of PTC. The solar input provides high-grade energy that reduces irreversibilities in the thermodynamic cycle, particularly in the steam Rankine cycle. At PR = 9, the η_{ex} rises to 57.4%, showing a more pronounced improvement than Model 1. The PTC enhances energy recovery and reduces combustion-related losses, particularly as the PR increases. At PR = 12, the η_{ex} reaches 58.4%, maintaining steady growth. The solar integration continues to minimize system losses and ensure efficient use of the available exergy. At PR = 15, the η_{ex} peaks at 58.83%, nearly 10 percentage points higher than Model 1. This behavior demonstrates the substantial impact of solar heat in reducing exergy destruction across the system. For Model 3, at PR = 6, the η_{ex} is 55.01%, slightly lower than Model 2. This is because the ARS begins recovering low-grade heat, using some energy for cooling purposes rather than power generation. At PR = 9, the η_{ex} improves to 57.27%, closely trailing Model 2. At this PR, the ARS starts complementing the PTC by recovering more waste heat, effectively reducing thermal losses and improving the overall system efficiency. At PR = 12, the η_{ex} reaches 58.45%, matching Model 2. The synergy between the ARS and PTC ensures optimal heat recovery and energy utilization, allowing the system to operate near its thermodynamic limits. At PR = 15, the η_{ex} peaks at 59.08%, surpassing Model 2. This is due to the ARS's ability to recover additional low-grade heat at higher PRs, contributing to reduced exergy destruction and improved overall efficiency.

Figure 4.5. Variation of exergy efficiency with pressure ratio across system models.

4.3.4. Impact of Gas Turbine Inlet Temperature in System Models

Figure 4.6 illustrates the relationship between \dot{W}_{net} (MW) and Gas Turbine Inlet Temperature (GTIT) for three configurations, Model 1, Model 2, and Model 3, showcasing the effect of increasing GTIT on power output and the impact of system enhancements on performance. Across all models, \dot{W}_{net} increases linearly with GTIT due to the proportional relationship between higher turbine inlet temperatures and the enthalpy drop across the turbine, allowing greater energy extraction. However, significant performance differences emerge between the models due to variations in configuration. Model 1, the simplest system, produces the lowest \dot{W}_{net} at all GTIT levels, starting at 105 MW at 1100 K and increasing to 300 MW at 1600 K. Its performance is constrained by the absence of renewable energy integration or cooling enhancements, making it heavily reliant on the basic gas turbine and Rankine cycle with no mechanisms to recover additional thermal energy or reduce irreversibilities. Model 2, which incorporates a PTC, shows improved performance across all GTIT values, achieving 138 MW at 1100 K and increasing to 330 MW at

1600 K. The PTC provides renewable thermal energy, enhancing the efficiency of the steam and organic Rankine cycles and boosting \dot{W}_{net} output about 30 MW compared to Model 1. However, Model 2 is limited in mitigating compression work at higher GTIT levels without advanced cooling. Model 3, the most advanced configuration, consistently achieves the highest \dot{W}_{net} , ranging from 150 MW at 1100 K to 340 MW at 1600 K, outperforming Model 2 by about 10 MW and Model 1 at about 40 MW across all GTIT values.

Figure 4.6. Impact of the GTIT on the \dot{W}_{net} across system models.

Figure 4.7 demonstrates the relationship between Electricity Cost (\$/MWh) and GTIT for three hybrid power system configurations. From the table, note that in Model 1, At GTIT = 1100 K, the cost rate is 102.4 \$/MWh reflecting the high operational costs associated with lower thermodynamic efficiency and lower \dot{W}_{net} output at this temperature. At GTIT = 1250 K, the cost rate decreases significantly to 76.7 \$/h. The improvement in thermal and η_{ex} at higher GTITs reduces the cost rate by enabling better utilization of available energy. At GTIT = 1400 K, the cost rate drops further to 64.16 \$/h. The system operates more efficiently

as the gas turbine performs optimally at this higher temperature, minimizing the cost per unit of energy produced. At GTIT = 1600 K, the cost rate increases slightly to 80.89 \$/h. This rise reflects the diminishing thermodynamic gains and increased operational costs at very high GTITs, where irreversibilities begin to counteract efficiency improvements. For Model 2, At GTIT = 1100 K, the cost rate is 108.5 \$/h, higher than Model 1 due to the additional operational costs of the parabolic trough collector PTC. However, the improved energy recovery from solar input helps mitigate these costs. At GTIT = 1250 K, the cost rate reduces to 83.65 \$/h. The efficiency gains at this GTIT result in a lower cost rate as the PTC supplies high-quality heat to the system, improving overall performance. At GTIT = 1400 K, the cost rate stabilizes at 70.7 \$/h. The system approaches its thermodynamic limits, and the cost per unit of energy stabilizes as further efficiency gains diminish. At GTIT = 1600 K, the cost rate rises to 84.76 \$/h. The system faces diminishing returns at very high GTITs, where the operational costs of the PTC and increased irreversibilities offset efficiency gains. For Model 3, At GTIT = 1100 K, the cost rate is 100.3 \$/h, lower than Model 2 due to ARS recovering additional waste heat, which reduces the overall cost per unit of energy. At GTIT = 1250 K, the cost rate reduces to 79.71 \$/h. The ARS complements the PTC by efficiently utilizing low-grade heat, ensuring stable performance and cost reduction at this intermediate GTIT. At GTIT = 1400 K, the cost rate stabilizes at 68.45 \$/h, slightly lower than Model 2. The synergy between the ARS and PTC ensures efficient energy recovery, keeping costs low despite reduced efficiency gains at this temperature. At GTIT = 1600 K, the cost rate increases to 82.13 \$/h, remaining lower than Model 2. The ARS offsets some of the performance losses at very high GTITs, ensuring better cost efficiency compared to Model 2.

Figure 4.7. Impact of the GTIT on the electricity cost across system models.

Figure 4.8 illustrates the variation in the thermal efficiency (η_{th}) with respect to GTIT for three hybrid power system configurations: Across all models, η_{th} progresses with increasing GTIT due to improved combustion and expansion operation in the turbine, that are directly subjected to higher inlet temperatures. However, the degree of improvement, efficiency values, and overall trends vary significantly between the three configurations due to differences in system design and included enhancements such as the PTC in Models 2 and 3 and the ARS in Model 3.

For Model 1, at GTIT = 1100 K, the η_{th} is 43.55%, reflecting the baseline performance of a conventional gas turbine integrated with steam and organic Rankine cycles. This configuration's efficiency is relatively low due to significant irreversibilities and limited heat recovery. At GTIT = 1250 K, the η_{th} improves to 48.25%. This improvement reflects the enhanced thermodynamic efficiency of the gas turbine at higher inlet temperatures, where the Brayton cycle becomes more efficient. However, the lack of advanced heat recovery systems limits the potential

gains. At GTIT = 1400 K, the η_{th} increases to 51.05%, showing diminishing returns. While the higher inlet temperature improves gas turbine performance, the conventional heat recovery systems (Steam RC and ORC) cannot fully utilize the available energy. At GTIT = 1600 K, the η_{th} peaks at 53.35%, a modest increase compared to lower GTITs. This plateau indicates the limitations of Model 1 in achieving higher efficiencies without additional systems for advanced heat utilization. For Model 2, at GTIT = 1100 K, the η_{th} is 58.37%, significantly higher than Model 1 due to the integration of the parabolic trough collector PTC. The solar input provides additional high-quality energy, reducing reliance on fuel combustion and enhancing the system's efficiency even at lower GTITs. At GTIT = 1250 K, the η_{th} rises to 59.23%, reflecting the combined benefits of the gas turbine's improved thermodynamic performance at higher GTITs and the PTC's ability to enhance the Rankine cycle by supplying additional heat. At GTIT = 1400 K, the η_{th} increases to 59.68%, showing diminishing returns compared to earlier increments. The PTC's contribution ensures that efficiency remains higher than Model 1, but the incremental gains decrease as the system approaches its thermodynamic limits. At GTIT = 1600 K, the η_{th} reaches 59.97%, nearing saturation. The system benefits from the gas turbine's enhanced performance at high GTITs and the solar energy input, ensuring minimal thermal losses. For Model 3, At GTIT = 1100 K, the η_{th} is 58.3%, closely matching Model 2. At this temperature, the absorption refrigeration system (ARS) has minimal impact because low-grade heat availability is limited, and most of the energy recovery is dominated by the PTC. At GTIT = 1250 K, the η_{th} improves to 59.12%, closely following Model 2. As GTIT increases, the ARS further complements the PTC by recovering low-grade heat, but its contribution remains secondary compared to the PTC at this stage. At GTIT = 1400 K, the η_{th} increase to 59.57%, slightly trailing Model 2. This small lag is due to the ARS utilizing part of the recovered heat for cooling, slightly reducing the direct contribution to power generation. At GTIT = 1600 K, the η_{th} reaches 59.87%, just shy of Model 2's performance. The ARS adds value by optimizing waste heat recovery, but the trade-off between power generation and cooling utilization results in slightly slower thermal efficiency growth compared to Model 2.

Figure 4.8. Impact of the GTIT on the thermal efficiency (η_{th}) across system models.

Figure 4.9 illustrates the variation in η_{ex} with respect to GTIT for three hybrid power system configurations, Model 1, Model 2, and Model 3, highlighting the thermodynamic impact of GTIT on the effective utilization of available energy.

η_{ex} increases across all configurations as GTIT rises from 1100 K to 1600 K, reflecting the improved utilization of available energy at higher turbine inlet temperatures. The performance hierarchy among the models remains consistent across the GTIT range. Where Model 1, At GTIT = 1100 K, the η_{ex} is 42.05%, reflecting the low ability of this conventional configuration to recover and utilize available exergy. Irreversibilities in the gas turbine and limited recovery from the Rankine and ORC cycles account for the low efficiency. At GTIT = 1250 K, the η_{ex} increases to 46.59%. This improvement is primarily due to the thermodynamic benefits of a higher GTIT, which enhances the energy conversion efficiency of the gas turbine. However, the lack of advanced systems limits further gains. At GTIT = 1400 K, the η_{ex} rises to 49.96%, showing diminishing returns. While the higher GTIT reduces some irreversibilities, the system's ability to recover low-grade heat remains

constrained. At GTIT = 1600 K, the η_{ex} reaches 51.52%, illustrating a plateau in performance. This table indicates that the conventional configuration has reached its thermodynamic limits, even with the higher GTIT. For Model 2, At GTIT = 1100 K, the η_{ex} is 56.36%, significantly higher than Model 1 due to the integration of the PTC. The solar energy input reduces fuel combustion irreversibilities and enhances the performance of the steam Rankine cycle. At GTIT = 1250 K, the efficiency improves to 57.19%, reflecting the combined benefits of the higher GTIT and solar energy input. The PTC ensures more effective utilization of available exergy, particularly in the steam cycle. At GTIT = 1400 K, the η_{ex} increases to 57.62%, but the gains begin to diminish. This is because the system approaches its thermodynamic limits, where most of the available exergy is already being utilized effectively. At GTIT = 1600 K, the η_{ex} reaches 57.91%, approaching saturation. The PTC ensures minimal exergy destruction, allowing the system to maintain a high level of efficiency. For Model 3, At GTIT = 1100 K, the η_{ex} is 56.3%, slightly lower than Model 2 due to the absorption refrigeration system ARS. At lower GTITs, the ARS recovers minimal low-grade heat, making its impact less significant than the solar energy input from the PTC. At GTIT = 1250 K, efficiency rises to 57.09%, closely trailing Model 2. At this point, the ARS begins to complement the PTC by recovering more low-grade heat, reducing overall exergy destruction. At GTIT = 1400 K, the η_{ex} reaches 57.62%, matching Model 2. The ARS works synergistically with the PTC to optimize waste heat recovery, ensuring efficient utilization of the available exergy. At GTIT = 1600 K, the η_{ex} peaks at 57.82%, slightly trailing Model 2. The slight lag reflects the trade-off in using part of the recovered heat for cooling rather than direct power generation.

Figure 4.9. Impact of the GTIT on the exergy efficiency (η_{ex}) across system models.

4.3.5. Impact of Inlet Temperature of the High-Pressure Steam Turbine in System Models

Figure 4.10 illustrates the relationship between the (\dot{W}_{net}) and the inlet temperature of the high-pressure steam turbine (T_{in_HPST}), comparing the thermodynamic and operational performance of three hybrid system configurations: Model 1, Model 2, and Model 3. Model 1 shows limited performance, with \dot{W}_{net} increasing marginally from approximately 201 MW at 720 K to 203 MW at 800 K. These small gains are attributed solely to the rise in T_{in_HPST} , as the model lacks advanced energy recovery and compression efficiency technologies, resulting in significant energy losses during compression and combustion processes. Model 2 demonstrates a notable improvement, with \dot{W}_{net} rising from about 227 MW at 720 K to 233 MW at 800 K. The integration of a PTC enhances the efficiency of the steam and organic Rankine cycles by utilizing otherwise wasted heat. However, without advanced cooling mechanisms, Model 2 experiences moderate performance gains as higher T_{in_HPST} values increase compression work and irreversibilities. Model 3 achieves the highest

performance, with \dot{W}_{net} increasing from approximately 240 MW at 720 K to 245 MW at 800 K. ARS reduces air compression workload by cooling the air entering the compressor, thereby lowering energy losses and improving system efficiency. Combined with the renewable energy input from the PTC, Model 3 sustains robust performance gains across the T_{in_HPST} range, achieving the steepest slope and the highest net power output among the configurations.

Figure 4.10. Impact of the T_{in_HPST} on the \dot{W}_{net} across system models.

Figure 4.11 illustrates the relationship between electricity cost and T_{in_HPST} , reflecting the interplay between thermodynamics, operational efficiency, and economic performance across three hybrid system configurations: Model 1, Model 2, and Model 3. A universal reduction in electricity cost is observed with increasing T_{in_HPST} , driven by improved thermal-to-work conversion efficiency and reduced specific electricity costs. However, the rate and magnitude of these reductions vary significantly due to the technological differences among the models. Model 1 exhibits the least improvement, with electricity costs declining marginally from 68.3 \$/MWh at 720 K to 67 \$/MWh at 800 K. These modest gains reflect the model's

reliance on higher T_{in_HPST} to enhance turbine work output while remaining constrained by irreversibilities in compression and combustion processes. Model 2 achieves larger cost reductions compared to Model 1. Electricity costs have been reduced from 76.4 \$/MWh at 720 K to 74 \$/MWh at 800 K, with the PTC improving energy recovery and decreasing fuel dependency. This renewable contribution is maximum effective in moderate T_{in_HPST} range (760–800 K), where thermodynamic profits are maximized. Nevertheless, the lack of advanced cooling technologies restricts the model’s ability to moderate compression inefficiencies, causing falling returns at higher T_{in_HPST} . Model 3 achieves the most noteworthy cost reductions, from 73.4 \$/MWh at 720 K to 71.3 \$/MWh at 800 K. The ARS decreases compression work and related irreversibilities by lowering compressor inlet air temperature, whereas the PTC adds renewable thermal energy. Model 3 emerges as the most robust and cost-effective configuration, combining the benefits of the PTC and ARS to achieve sustained cost reductions and optimized thermodynamic performance.

Figure 4.11. Impact of the T_{in_HPST} on the Electricity Cost Across System Models.

Figure 4.12 illustrates the variation in thermal efficiency (η_{th}) as a function of T_{in_HPST} for three hybrid power system configurations: Model 1, Model 2, and Model 3. The findings show that Model 1 demonstrates limited efficiency improvements and is unsuitable for high-performing applications. Model 2 benefits from the PTC, achieving substantial gains in η_{th} and maintaining stable performance at a lower T_{in_HPST} . Model 3, with the combined effects of the PTC and ARS, achieves superior efficiency, particularly at lower inlet temperatures, making it the most robust and optimized configuration for energy recovery and thermodynamic stability. Model 1 exhibits the lowest efficiency due to its reliance on basic thermodynamic processes without advanced energy recovery mechanisms. At $T_{in_HPST}=813$ K, η_{th} reaches a maximum of 50.37%, benefiting from increased energy input to the steam Rankine cycle. As T_{in_HPST} decreases, η_{th} declines linearly to 49.85% at 723 K, highlighting the system's sensitivity to lower inlet temperatures and inability to recover sufficient energy. Model 2 achieves significantly higher efficiencies. At $T_{in_HPST}=813$ K, η_{th} is 59.42%, reflecting the PTC's role in enhancing steam quality and energy recovery. Even as T_{in_HPST} decreases to 723 K, η_{th} remains relatively stable at 57.87%, demonstrating the PTC's ability to mitigate the impact of reduced inlet temperatures by supplying supplementary heat. Model 3 performs similarly to Model 2 but shows distinct advantages at lower inlet temperatures. At $T_{in_HPST}=813$ K, η_{th} is 59.33%, slightly trailing Model 2 due to the ARS's diversion of some recovered heat for cooling. However, as T_{in_HPST} decreases, the ARS's ability to recover low-grade heat offsets this trade-off, resulting in η_{th} of 57.93% at 723 K, surpassing Model 2.

Figure 4.12. Impact of the T_{in_HPST} on the Thermal Efficiency Across System Models.

Figure 4.13 illustrates the variation in exergetic efficiency (η_{ex}) with T_{in_HPST} for three hybrid power system configurations: Model 1, Model 2, and Model 3. Model 1 exhibits the lowest η_{ex} , reflecting its simple cycle design without renewable energy integration or advanced irreversibility mitigation. At $T_{in_HPST}=813$ K, η_{ex} reaches a maximum of 48.64%, declining gradually to 48.14% at 723 K. The limited ability to recover energy at lower inlet temperatures highlights its inefficiency in utilizing low-grade heat. Model 2 determines significantly higher efficiency. At $T_{in_HPST}=813$ K, η_{ex} is 57.38%, referring to the PTC's contribution in decreasing irreversibilities and enhancing energy recovery. As T_{in_HPST} decreases, η_{ex} drops to 55.88% at 723 K, with the PTC alleviating performance by providing constant supplementary energy. Model 3 performs equally to Model 2 at higher inlet temperatures but better at lower temperatures. At $T_{in_HPST}=813$ K, η_{ex} is 57.29%, a little trailing Model 2 because of ARS's cooling energy trade-off. Nevertheless, at $T_{in_HPST}=723$ K, η_{ex} rises to 55.93%, better than Model 2 due to the ARS's ability to improve additional low-grade heat and minimize exergy destruction.

Figure 4.13. Impact of the T_{in_HPST} on the Exergy Efficiency Across System Models.

4.3.6. Impact of High-Pressure Steam Turbine Inlet Pressure in System Models

Figure 4.14 demonstrates the relationship between \dot{W}_{net} and high-pressure turbine inlet pressure (P_{in_HPST}) for three hybrid power system configurations: Model 1, Model 2, and Model 3. The figure shows how increasing P_{in_HPST} affects \dot{W}_{net} reflecting variances in thermodynamic performance and system design across the models. Nevertheless, these configurations keep higher overall performance because of their advanced features. For Model 1, at P_{in_HPST} of 60 bar, the \dot{W}_{net} is 198.1 MW, increasing to 202.1 MW at 90 bar and 204.7 MW at 120 bar before peaking at 206.4 MW at 150 bar, where decreasing returns become evident due to system constraints. Model 2, benefiting from the contribution of the PTC, generates 233.2 MW at 60 bar and 231.3 MW at 90 bar, reflecting a slight decline due to increasing irreversibilities. At higher pressures, Model 2 outputs 229.2 MW at 120 bar and 227.1 MW at 150 bar, showing a progressive decrease due to diminishing returns. Model 3, which integrates the PTC and ARS, achieves superior performance, producing 246.1 MW at

60 bar and closely maintaining efficiency with 244.2 MW at 90 bar. At 120 bar and 150 bar, Model 3 outputs 242.3 MW and 240.2 MW, respectively, outperforming Models 1 and 2 across all pressure ranges.

Figure 4.14. Impact of the P_{in_HPST} on the \dot{W}_{net} Across System Models.

Figure 4.15 depicts the relationship between electricity cost and high-pressure turbine inlet pressure P_{in_HPST} for three hybrid power system configurations: Model 1, Model 2, and Model 3. The performance curves show that Model 1 is appropriate only for basic applications because of its low efficiency. In comparison, Model 2, improved with PTC, maintains steady efficiency across various pressures and significantly increases exergy performance. Model 3, which integrates both PTC and ARS, proves superior performance by maximizing energy usage while decreasing exergy destruction, especially at lower inlet pressures. The three models' cost analyses indicate various trends depending on P_{in_HPST} . With improved energy extraction and turbine performance despite reduced returns at higher pressures, the electricity cost for Model 1 starts at 70.6 \$/h at 60 bar. It gradually decreases to 67.5 \$/h at 90 bar, 65.61 \$/h at 120 bar, and 64.33 \$/h at 150 bar. The higher basic cost of

73.72 \$/h at 60 bar in Model 2, which is affected by the increased cost of the PTC, improves slightly to 74.5 \$/h at 90 bar as the result of system irreversibilities, maintains at 75.35 \$/h at 120 bar, and hits 76.23\$/h at 150 bar as efficiency gradually decreases.

Figure 4.15. Impact of the P_{in_HPST} on the Electricity Cost Across System Models.

Figure 4.16 shows the relationship between thermal efficiency η_{th} and high-pressure turbine inlet pressure (P_{in_HPST}) for three hybrid power system configurations Model 1, Model 2, and Model 3—Model 1, based on simple thermodynamic principles, displays a gradual increase in efficiency with rising P_{in_HPST} , starting at 49.19% at 60 bar, improving to 50.19% at 90 bar, 50.82% at 120 bar, and topping at 51.26% at 150 bar according to thermodynamic limits. Model 2, enhanced with PTC, achieves higher efficiencies, beginning at 59.42% at 60 bar, and stays stable performance with slight declines at 58.93% at 90 bar, 58.41% at 120 bar, and 57.87% at 150 bar because of decreasing returns and system saturation. Model 3, which integrates both the PTC and ARS, overtakes Model 2 at higher pressures, reaching a thermal efficiency of 57.93% at 150 bar. This performance reveals the benefits of advanced

heat recovery systems in enhancing energy efficiency under changing operating conditions, with Model 3 showcasing greater efficiency and stability, mainly at elevated pressures. Model 3, leveraging the combined benefits of PTC and ARS, begins at 59.33% at 60 bar, slightly trailing Model 2 due to ARS energy diversion. It stabilizes at 58.88% at 90 bar, 58.25% at 120 bar, and 57.93% at 150 bar, surpassing Model 2 at higher pressures through effective low-grade heat recovery..

Figure 4.16. Impact of the P_{in_HPST} on the Thermal Efficiency Across System Models.

Figure 4.17 illustrates the relationship between exergetic efficiency (η_{ex}) and high-pressure turbine inlet pressure (P_{in_HPST}) for three hybrid power system configurations: Model 1, Model 2, and Model 3. The exergetic efficiency (η_{ex}) of the three models varies significantly across different inlet pressures of the high-pressure steam turbine (P_{in_HPST}). Model 1 shows limited efficiency improvements, starting at 47.5% at 60 bar and increasing progressively to 48.46% at 90 bar, 49.07% at 120 bar, and reaching a plateau at 49.49% at 150 bar as thermodynamic limits are approached. Model 2, enhanced by the PTC, achieves higher efficiencies, starting at 57.38% at 60

bar and maintaining stable performance with 56.97% at 90 bar, 56.47% at 120 bar, and 55.88% at 150 bar, where diminishing returns become apparent. Model 3, integrating both PTC and ARS closely matches Model 2 at lower pressures, starting at 57.29% at 60 bar, and stabilizing at 56.86% at 90 bar and 56.41% at 120 bar. At 150 bar, Model 3 surpasses Model 2 with an efficiency of 55.93%, benefiting from its effective heat recovery mechanisms.

Figure 4.17. Impact of the P_{in_HPST} on the Exergy Efficiency Across System Models.

4.4. MONTHLY ANALYSIS OF THE HYBRID POWER SYSTEMS MODELS

4.4.1. Influence of Solar Energy and Ambient Temperature on Net Power Output

Figure 4.18 illustrates the monthly variations in net power output \dot{W}_{net} for three hybrid power system configurations, highlighting the impact of DNI and T_{amb} on system performance. DNI plays a critical role in Models 2 and 3, which utilize PTC. Peak DNI in June (8.02) and July (7.75) corresponds to the highest \dot{W}_{net} for these models, at 230.8 MW and 246.7 MW, respectively, demonstrating the positive

correlation between DNI and solar-integrated system performance. However, high T_{amb} negatively affect all models, particularly the gas turbine efficiency in Model 1. For example, in July, when $T_{amb}=36.08^{\circ}\text{C}$, Model 1's output drops to 191.7 MW despite high DNI. Model 1's performance is relatively stable throughout the year, with its lowest output in July (191.7 MW) and highest in January (206.3 MW) due to cooler $T_{amb}=8.33^{\circ}\text{C}$. Model 2 consistently outperforms Model 2 due to the PTC, achieving peak outputs in June (233.8 MW) and July (230.8 MW) and maintaining strong performance even in lower DNI months like January (218.7 MW). Model 3, combining the benefits of the PTC and ARS, achieves the highest output across all months, peaking in June (246.7 MW) and July (245.2 MW). The ARS mitigates the impact of high T_{amb} , enabling superior performance compared to Models 1 and 2. Even during months with lower DNI, such as January (217.8 MW) and December (216.8 MW), Model 3 outperforms the others due to advanced energy recovery.

Figure 4.18. Monthly cumulative W_{net} for the three models

4.4.2. Influence of Solar Energy and Ambient Temperature on Electricity Cost

Figure 4.19 presents the monthly variation in electricity cost rates for the three hybrid power system configurations Model 1, Model 2, and Model 3, highlighting the influence of DNI and T_{amb} on economic performance. DNI significantly impacts the cost rates of Models 2 and 3, which utilize solar energy through PTC. Higher DNI improves thermodynamic performance, reducing cost rates, particularly during spring and summer months (April to August), when DNI peaks. However, in winter months with low DNI, such as January (2.66) and December (2.48), the reduced solar contribution increases the cost rates for Models 2 and 3. Meanwhile, T_{amb} negatively affects all models, particularly Model 1, by reducing gas turbine efficiency. For instance, during peak T_{amb} in July (36.39°C) and August (36.08°C), Model 1's cost rises to 71.38 and 71.34 \$/MWh, respectively, despite high DNI values. Model 1 exhibits the highest cost rates throughout the year, as it lacks solar energy or heat recovery contributions. Its performance is most sensitive to T_{amb} , with the lowest cost rates in January (67.97 \$/MWh) and February (68.23 \$/MWh) due to cooler temperatures and enhanced gas turbine performance. Conversely, Model 2 achieves better cost performance through PTC integration, reducing fuel dependency and lowering cost rates during high-DNI months, such as May (74.64 \$/MWh) and June (73.49 \$/MWh). However, its cost rates rise in low-DNI months like January (78.98 \$/MWh) and December (79.57 \$/MWh), reflecting its sensitivity to seasonal solar energy variations. Model 3 consistently delivers the lowest cost rates, benefiting from the combined advantages of solar integration (PTC) and waste heat recovery ARS. It demonstrates stable cost performance even during high T_{amb} months, such as July (71.28 \$/MWh) and August (72.22 \$/MWh), as the ARS mitigates the adverse effects of elevated ambient temperatures. In high-DNI months, such as May (72.61 \$/MWh) and June (70.9 \$/MWh), Model 3 achieves the lowest rates, showcasing its superior efficiency. Even in low-DNI months, Model 3 remains competitive, with cost rates of 79.3 \$/MWh (January) and 79.62 \$/MWh (December).

Seasonal comparisons reveal that in winter months (January, February, December), low DNI and cooler T_{amb} favor Model 1, achieving its best performance in January (67.97 \$/MWh). However, Models 2 and 3 experience higher cost rates due to

reduced solar input. In spring and early summer (March to May), as DNI increases, Models 2 and 3 show significant cost reductions, with May rates of 74.64 \$/MWh and 72.61 \$/MWh, respectively, outperforming Model 1 (70.26 \$/MWh). During peak summer (June to August), high DNI coincides with high T_{amb} . While Model 1's cost rates peak in July and August (71.38 \$/MWh and 71.34 \$/MWh), Models 2 and 3 maintain more stable rates due to solar and heat recovery benefits. In autumn (September to November), moderate DNI and T_{amb} allow Models 2 and 3 to sustain superior cost performance compared to Model 1.

Figure 4.19. Monthly electricity costs for the three models.

4.4.3. Influence of Solar Energy and Ambient Temperature on Carbon Footprint

Figure 4.20 illustrates the monthly variations in carbon emissions (in tons/month) for three hybrid power system configurations, Model 1, Model 2, and Model 3. under the

influence of DNI and T_{amb} . The data highlights the environmental impact of each model and the role of solar integration PTC and ARS in reducing emissions. DNI significantly influences Models 2 and 3, which utilize solar energy through the PTC. High DNI reduces fuel consumption, directly lowering emissions. For instance, in June (DNI = 8.02) and July (DNI = 7.75), emissions for Models 2 and 3 dropped to 331.1 kgCO₂/MWh and 333.7 kgCO₂/MWh, respectively, compared to 400.8 kgCO₂/MWh for Model 1. Conversely, T_{amb} negatively affects gas turbine efficiency, particularly in Model 1, which relies solely on conventional energy sources. During July ($T_{amb}=36.39^{\circ}\text{C}$), emissions in Model 1 peak at 401.1 kgCO₂/MWh, while Models 2 and 3, with enhanced recovery and solar input, show significantly lower emissions at 338.2 tons/month and 333.7 kgCO₂/MWh, respectively.

Model 1 consistently exhibits the highest annual emissions due to its reliance on fossil fuels without solar or heat recovery integration. Emissions peak in July (401.1 kgCO₂/MWh) and remain high during summer months, while the lowest emissions occur in January (398.3 kgCO₂/MWh) and February (398.5 kgCO₂/MWh) due to cooler T_{amb} improving gas turbine performance. Thanks to solar energy integration, model 2 achieves substantial emission reductions compared to Model 1. In high-DNI months like May (6.82) and June (8.02), emissions drop to 340.5 tons/month and 331.1 kgCO₂/MWh, respectively. However, in low-DNI months such as January (375.6 tons/month) and December (377.4 kgCO₂/MWh), emissions rise slightly due to continued reliance on fossil fuels. Model 3 demonstrates the lowest emissions across all months, benefiting from the combined advantages of solar integration and the ARS. In June and July, emissions drop to 331.7 kgCO₂/MWh and 333.7 kgCO₂/MWh, respectively, as the ARS mitigates the negative effects of high T_{amb} and enhances energy recovery. Even in low-DNI months like January (375.7 kgCO₂/MWh) and February (kgCO₂/MWh), Model 3 remains slightly superior to Model 2, showcasing its ability to maintain lower emissions under varying conditions.

Seasonal comparisons reveal that in winter months (January, February, December), low DNI and cooler T_{amb} improve gas turbine performance but still produce high emissions for Model 1 (398.3–398.5 kgCO₂/MWh). Models 2 and 3 achieve

noticeable reductions, with Model 3 performing slightly better (375.7 tons/month in January). In the spring and summer months (April to July), DNI peaks, and Models 2 and 3 benefit significantly from solar energy, achieving their lowest emissions in June (331.1 tons/month and 331.7 kgCO₂/MWh, respectively) compared to Model 1 (400.8 kgCO₂/MWh). Despite the high T_{amb} in July, Model 3 maintains a significant advantage, reducing emissions to 333.7 kgCO₂/MWh. In the autumn months (September to November), moderate DNI and T_{amb} stabilize emissions for all models. Model 1 maintains higher emissions (400.6 kgCO₂/MWh in September), while Models 2 and 3 achieve significant reductions (347.8 kgCO₂/MWh and 347.kgCO₂/MWh, respectively).

Figure 4.20. Monthly levels of carbon footprint for the three models.

CHAPTER 5

CONCLUSION

This study provides an in-depth investigation of Iraq's solar-assisted combined cycle power plants, with an emphasis on updating the Kirkuk Gas Power Plant for improved energy efficiency, sustainability, and economic viability. Iraq's energy issues, including a reliance on fossil fuels, increasing electricity consumption, and environmental worries, are heightened by high summer temperatures and unsuitable power producing technologies. The Kirkuk Gas Power Plant's advantageous location, combined with its significant solar energy potential, offers a unique opportunity for the integration of renewable energy technologies. Solar energy is essential since it provides a clean, renewable, and practically limitless supply, minimizing the plant's dependence on fossil fuels and greatly reducing greenhouse gas emissions. This integration is not only crucial for managing Iraq's energy challenges, but it also matches with global sustainability goals, such as the Paris Agreement.

The study examines three advanced designs for improving the power plant. Model 1 (GT + SRC + ORC) is the beginning, with limited heat recovery abilities resulting in the highest η_{th} of 51.26% and an η_{ex} of 49.49%. While this model displays the promise of combined cycle systems, it falls short of optimizing η_{th} while minimizing waste heat. Model 2 incorporates a solar-driven PTC with the gas turbine system to overcome these restrictions. This addition significantly improves performance, increasing η_{th} to 59.97% and η_{ex} to 57.91%. The PTC efficiently utilizes solar energy to minimize fuel use and improve power generation, demonstrating the profound impact of solar integration. whereas the economic viability of Model 2 is restricted by greater operational expenses related to the solar components.

Model 3 is the most advanced configuration, integrating PTC with ARS. This innovative design maximizes the recovery of waste heat of low grade, achieving η_{th}

and η_{ex} of 61.19% and 59.08%, respectively. The installation of the ARS not only minimizes irreversibilities in the system but also manages the station's cooling demands, making it particularly efficient in Iraq's hot climate. The model produces a \dot{W}_{net} of 240.2 MW, showing its ability to boost energy production while minimizing operational costs significantly. Model 3 delivers the best thermodynamic and economical results by using both high-grade and low-grade heat effectively, making a benchmark for sustainable power generation systems in energy-intensive locations.

Kirkuk Gas Power Plant's location is important for the success of the multiple arrangements. Solar integration is a feasible and cost-effective solution in Iraq because of its high solar irradiation levels. This study highlights the need to maximize this geographical advantage to achieve independent energy supply and sustainability. This study illustrates how hybridizing standard gas turbine systems with solar technology may assist Iraq's transition to a greener and more efficient energy infrastructure.

The key findings and implications of this study are as follows:

- The system's performance improved by adding PTC to Model 2. The \dot{W}_{net} rose from 211.7 MW in Model 1 to 232.4 MW in Model 2. In addition, this arrangement exceeded Model 1 in terms of η_{th} and η_{ex} , reaching 59.97% and 57.91%, respectively, compared to 51.26% and 49.49%. These results show how well solar energy integration increases the station's total energy efficiency.
- Model 3, which combines ARS with PTC, exhibited the best performance metrics. Additionally, the \dot{W}_{net} became 240.2 MW, and the η_{ex} and η_{th} improved to 59.08% and 61.19%, respectively. Low-grade waste heat was effectively utilized through ARS integration, boosting system efficiency and minimizing thermal losses.
- The thermoeconomics analysis revealed that Model 3 offers a cost-effective solution for power generation. The efficient utilization of solar energy and waste heat recovery reduced operational costs, making this configuration economically favorable compared to the baseline Model 1.

- The adoption of solar energy and waste heat recovery technologies led to a significant decrease in CO₂ emissions. Model 3 demonstrated the lowest CO₂ emissions among the configurations, highlighting its potential for contributing to cleaner energy production and reducing the environmental footprint of the station.
- Increasing the PR first improved system efficiency and decreased energy expenses until reaching an optimal point, after which performance decreased. In the same way, GTIT decreased particular utility costs and CO₂ emissions while improving network productivity. With no impact on environmental performance, increasing the temperature at T_{in_HPST} did, however, slightly improve work output. Higher condenser temperatures, on the other hand, had an adverse effect on both economic and environmental performance because it increased particular energy costs, reduced work output, and increased CO₂ emissions.
- The study highlights a unique advantage of the Kirkuk Gas Power Plant's position, because it makes use of Iraq's high levels of solar radiation. Due to this, the location is perfect for hybrid energy systems that integrate waste heat recovery using solar energy, offering an achievable solution to meet the region's shortage of electricity and cut greenhouse gas emissions.
- The results show that which include solar-assisted power plant configurations ARE consistent with global developments toward sustainable energy, particularly in areas like Iraq that have a numerous amounts of solar resources. With the potential for wider use in areas with similar climates, the study provides a framework for maximizing energy output while addressing environmental concerns.

This study highlights the substantial advantages of hybrid power systems, and provides insights into approaches to maximize solar energy integration for increased efficiency, cost-effectiveness, and environmental sustainability. It is recommended that more research be done to investigate how these combinations can possibly be used in different climates and to evaluate whether integrating other renewable energy sources could be effective.

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RESUME

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